

D 2.2

“From Theory to Practice” – operationalizing coevolutionary approach in research methodologies

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INTRODUCTION

This document examines the impact of the coevolutionary approach to Nature-based Solutions (henceforth: NBS) on methodology, both in a theoretical and practical sense. It distinguishes between theory-based *methodology* and practical *methods* based on empirical evidence and experience. This approach differs from other related documents in the COEVOLVERS project. Within WP2, it connects D 2.1 and D.2.3: The former elaborates on the theory of the coevolutionary approach to NBS as technology (henceforth, CEA-NBS), and the latter summarizes practical experiences in applying coevolutionary ideas and methods in the Living Labs. D 2.2 also relates to WP1 deliverable D 1.3, which provides an overview of co-creation methods for NBS relevant to the COEVOLVERS LL. Deliverable 2.2 also discusses specific methods, often presented in boxes, but does not aim to provide a comprehensive overview. We refer to exemplary methods to illustrate the general arguments presented here on the methodological implications of CEA-NBS.

This approach also suggests that we focus on including non-human species in NBS methods. The literature on co-creation methods is abundant in the fields of eco-social transformation, community resilience under environmental stress, and related project management. Many compilations of methods exist, particularly under European projects such as HORIZON. This report does not duplicate these variations but introduces a theoretically grounded systematic reflection on methods that includes not only the methods specific to those themes but also general social and behavioural research: We claim that the inclusion of non-human species in NBS research is also productive in suggesting new methodological thinking in transdisciplinary research beyond that specific theme. In this sense, our work joins the ongoing debate over how to overcome anthropocentrism in the social sciences and the humanities, sometimes dubbed “posthumanism” or “de-anthropocentrization”.

In this effort, we always aim to show how theoretical concerns and reflections translate into research practice. For example, we consider questions such as the design of

standard surveys about attitudes and beliefs and argue that CEA-NBS provides criteria for selecting some methods and sidelining others (for example, we argue that vignettes are a preferable way to ask questions in surveys). Our goal is to provide a systematic framework for building a coherent toolbox of CEA-NBS (for example, vignettes match the method of story-telling). Such practical recommendations follow from general reflections on which scientific categories, concepts and terms have “more-than-human” qualities and can, therefore, help to overcome the human/non-human divide in theorizing behaviour and practices, and thereby also in the concrete doing of the NBS on the ground.

In general, as argued in Chapter 1, CEA-NBS follows the premises of action research. Knowledge generation is seen as transformative itself, requiring the transdisciplinary inclusion of all perspectives, including non-human ones. The principle of co-evolution also applies to methodology: Methods evolve alongside their target applications, which are living beings. Science is part of human culture, and the concept of more-than-human culture implies that science is co-created in non-human formats. We see such developments in the realm of Artificial Intelligence. Why don't we consider a similar approach in the diverse worlds of living beings? This report champions overcoming the standard experimental approach to treating other beings as research objects and adopting the radically new approach to regard other beings as equal members of a community of inquiry. In this community of inquiry, experimentation is an experience shared by humans and other species in an effort to find ways of common flourishing. Work on the deliverable was complemented by additional writings focusing on specific aspects, which allowed for a more exploratory approach. Some of these writings have already been published in peer-reviewed journals. Feedback from the scientific community is crucial in ensuring that our chosen path is on the right track. The papers relevant to this deliverable are:

Published:

- Herrmann-Pillath, Carsten, Simo Sarkki, Timo Maran, Katriina Soini, und Juha Hiedanpää. "Nature-based solutions as more-than-human art: Co-evolutionary and co-creative design approaches". *Nature-Based Solutions* 4 (1. Dezember 2023): 100081.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbsj.2023.100081>. This paper has been selected for a special report in Science Featured: <https://sciencefeatured.com/2024/06/19/integrating-aesthetic-values-in-nature-based-ecological-designs/>. The paper was also cited in another high-profile paper in Science.

- Herrmann-Pillath, Carsten. "Rituals as Nature-Based Governance of Reciprocity between People and Nature". Open Research Europe 4 (12. April 2024): 66. <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.17206.1>. The paper underwent the productive open peer review report championed by the HORIZON program.
- Herrmann-Pillath, Carsten. Imagining Utopia in Eco-Social Transformation. More-Than-Human Property and Gift-Exchange Between People and Nature, invited book chapter in: Walter Otto Ötsch, Birger P. Priddat, Steffen W. Groß (Hg.), Das Imaginative der Politischen Ökonomie, Marburg: Metropolis 2024.

Under review / in preparation

- Simo Sarkki, Carsten Herrmann-Pillath & Juha Hiedanpää, The political constitution of multispecies society
- Simo Sarkki et al. Multispecies stakeholder analysis tailored for nature-based solutions
- Carsten Herrmann-Pillath, Juha Hiedanpää, Simo Sarkki, Indigenous Spirituality: Paradigm of Nature-based governance? An Ecosemiotic Approach (paper presented at Beskydy 2024 conference)

Chapter 1: General methodological principles of the co-evolutionary approach to NBS

1.0. Chapter summary

1. The coevolutionary approach to NBS (CEA-NBS) is radically normative, with a distinctive emphasis on the inclusion of non-human species and NBS as a technology of the multi-species society shaping landscapes and urban habitats.
2. Knowledge is co-produced by more-than-human actions and is embodied as shared habits of cohabitation. This grounds in epistemic justice, meaning recognition of diverse human and non-human views of the world.
3. NBS is a form of niche construction that CEA-NBS approaches as a duality of infrastructure (function) and landscape (meaning) (or duality ecosystem/Umwelts).
4. The central norm in doing NBS is reciprocity between humans and non-human species. This is achieved by interlocking doings such as place-shaping and care.
5. The methodology of CEA NBS is grounded in a set of fundamental concepts:
 - a. Practice: patterns of interlocking actions of humans and non-humans
 - b. Habit: embodied dispositions to sustain practices
 - c. Embodiment: Knowledge is embodied in feelings, emotions, cognitive stances etc. that relate to environmental patterns and cues
 - d. Meaning: Meaning is non-linguistic and is embodied interpretation expressed in action
 - e. Affordances are the analytical construct to understand the meaning-action dynamics.
 - f. Finality: Practices evolve towards goals of flourishing.
6. In designing specific research methodologies, CEA-NBS has three methodological pivots:
 - a. Individualization: Focus on individual experiences, cases, and contexts
 - b. Relationality: Focus on interlocking practices and Umwelt translations
 - c. Holism: Focus on embeddedness and context
7. CEA-NBS's methodology involves learning as a coevolutionary co-creation of embodied knowledge. The institutional forms are experimentation in living communities of learning (Living Labs) and multi-species democracy.

In this report, we delve into the implications of the co-evolutionary approach to NBS for methods. While the literature on NBS often references terms like "co-creation" or "co-production," the concept of co-evolution is seldom mentioned (Sarkki, 2024). As we have outlined in deliverable D 2.1, the notion of co-evolution encompasses two distinct dimensions. First, co-evolution firmly grounds the theory of NBS in the biological theory of evolution, albeit as extensions or even departures from the Neo-

Darwinian paradigm (Haider et al., 2021). Second, co-evolution stands apart from concepts like co-design, operating on two different conceptual levels: On the one hand, it serves as a general framework encompassing all other "co's," and on the other hand, it distinguishes co-evolutionary processes from other "co" processes, particularly co-design. For example, in the later case, "design" implicates intentional actions by a "designer", thus differing from evolution. One level up, however, designers are themselves parts of evolutionary processes. For conceptual clarity, we treat evolutionary theory as the primary framework, and co-evolution as distinct from other "co's" on the second level. However, through the reference to "evolution," co-evolution holds a preeminent position in the "co" consortium (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Conceptual hierarchy between "co"-concepts

The concept of co-evolution has various applications, including in the social sciences and anthropology (Goddard et al. 2019). When considering NBS as a technology, its relevance in economics becomes apparent (Dopfer et al., 2024). The underlying concept of evolution highlights three key elements of theorizing (Herrmann-Pillath and Hederer, 2023, p. 77ff):

- First, evolution occurs at the population level due to individual variation;
- second, accumulated knowledge is embodied in evolving populations and may not be directly accessible to individual agents as propositional knowledge;

- and third, evolution is a multi-level process where levels cannot be reduced to a basic process (such as genetic evolution).

Co-evolution involves the coupling of at least two independent evolutionary processes. A classic example is the co-evolution of genetic evolution and cultural evolution (Richerson and Boyd, 2008). In the social sciences, an important example relevant to NBS is the co-evolution of technology and social practices and structures, often emphasized in sustainability science (Zhang, 2020). "Independence" accompanies coupling, meaning that, for instance, cultural creativity is initially independent of technology but technology can also enable and influence cultural creativity. The same applies to gene-culture interactions (Jablonka et al., 2014).

For NBS methods, co-evolution encompasses various processes with similar logic, such as plant populations adapting to NBS design over generations impacted by climate change, and people's habits changing across different cohorts experiencing NBS environments, also impacted by climate change. Therefore, a key feature of co-evolutionary methods is considering a longer time frame than is typically prevalent in the implementation of NBS in local socio-politics. Time is also significant because different evolutionary processes have varying time structures, not only in terms of duration and pace of changes, but also in terms of temporal dynamics. An important example in sustainability sciences is the "tipping point" structure, where small changes accumulate over longer timespans, leading to rapid and comprehensive structural transformations (United Nations University - Institute for Environment and Human Security (UNU-EHS) et al., 2023). Such temporal complexities create high levels of uncertainty and ignorance for human decision-makers and NBS design.

The alternative interpretation of co-evolution stems from the combination of evolution and design in biological theory, as discussed in D 2.1. As said, in evolutionary theory design is seen as counterexample, as it is defined by intentional action of a "designer". Accordingly, co-design is often understood as involving deliberate and participatory processes that lead to specific design choices. This raises the question of whether such processes are truly evolutionary in the original sense, meaning that outcomes are open-ended and not predictable, and are beyond control of the collective designers. This can create tension with established methods in public planning that

prioritize accountability and transparency. These issues become more significant when considering the inclusion of other species, which introduces even more unpredictability and flexibility in domains traditionally focused on human planning and administration, such as in the context of rewilding. After all, nature is "unruly" (Grabowski et al. 2022). These tensions are also familiar in economics, where technology policies often fail to anticipate disruptive emerging technologies.

Co-evolutionary processes are also happening in other areas that involve "co-" prefixes. This explains why co-evolution is considered more important than the other "co-" processes. The different uses of "co-" can be systematically arranged within a multi-level framework. For example, intentional design processes that are not initially evolutionary are part of co-evolutionary processes driven by unintended design consequences, which lead to learning for the design actors. Therefore, learning can be thought of as a co-evolutionary process, and this has significant implications for methods. For example, interdisciplinary interactions among diverse groups with different knowledge bases can be seen as a co-evolutionary process where no perspective can claim epistemological priority, only in hindsight.

To sum up, the co-evolutionary approach offers a perspective on the design and implementation of NBS that goes beyond the usual discussions on co-creation and other collaborative efforts. It acknowledges the limitations of forward planning and explicit knowledge generation, taking a more open, "liberal" approach to developing NBS. This approach even includes an open democratic process that considers the input of non-human voices (Meijer, 2019). Ultimately, the co-evolutionary approach raises questions about fairness in knowledge-sharing among different species, highlighting the need for human actors in NBS design to recognize the knowledge-creating abilities of other co-evolving species (Winter, 2022).

This idea is significant because it challenges the belief that evolutionary theory is purely scientific and has no ethical values. This belief might have originated from the problematic history of applying evolutionary theory to social sciences, such as in Social Darwinism and eugenic thinking, when normative conclusions for social engineering were drawn from it. Hence, whether evolutionary theory has ethical implications has always been a highly contentious issue (FitzPatrick, 2020). However, the first chapter

of this report explores an alternative: establishing the co-evolutionary approach to NBS as a "normative science".

1.1. Normative sciences and performativity of techno-institutional assemblages

1.1.1. The normativity of referring to “nature” in NBS research

The coevolutionary approach to CEA-NB) is transdisciplinary, spanning from the sciences to the humanities and inclusive of local experts (later dubbed “local knowers”) and other-species actors. However, defining a specific methodology and set of methods poses significant challenges. In this report, we aim to address this challenge by adopting a particular philosophical stance based on Charles S. Peirce’s understanding of "normative sciences" (Peirce, 1992, p. 196ff; Short, 2012). A normative position is often taken in sustainability research, which aims to generate knowledge about achieving eco-social transformation while recognizing factual constraints and risks in our current economic and societal structures, as well as our concepts of justice, both social and multi-species (Clark and Miles, 2021; Cousins, 2021; Laurent, 2020; Lenzi et al., 2023). This approach aligns with the pragmatist tradition (Legg and Hookway, 2024) inaugurated by Peirce and prominent in the societal transformation engagement of Chicago pragmatists, especially Dewey, in the first half of the 20th century (Festenstein, 2023). It was also developed in specific methodologies such as action research introduced by Kurt Lewin (Reason and Bradbury, 2013). Our exposition introduces a new aspect, explicitly including other species in defining and practising methodologies for transformative research in a multi-species society, with a focus on NBS (Maller, 2021). This step is now widely seen as necessary because there is no necessary and unequivocal relationship between the well-being of human groups, even if realizing norms of justice, and the flourishing of ecosystems and other species.

The current research on NBS emphasizes the importance of normative concerns. At its core, this emphasizes the widely accepted notion that NBS should establish a principle of reciprocity between humans and nature (Ojeda et al., 2022; Roggema et

al., 2023) (we shall see, however, that the juxtaposition of humans and nature in conceptualizing reciprocity is itself problematic). Despite being designed and implemented by humans for specific purposes, NBS should contribute to nature by, for example, promoting biodiversity (IUCN, 2020). This concept of reciprocity is inherently normative as it involves considerations of distributive justice. How much should we give back to nature? For instance, if we expand wetland areas for flood control, to what extent should we restrict other human activities in these areas, and how much rewilding should we accept even if it conflicts with human interests? Phrasing the question in this manner also assumes that "nature" cannot have independent voice, which raises another aspect of justice, namely procedural. On the contrary, we acknowledge that NBS is a developing political structure, as accepting the idea of reciprocity between humans and nature leads to the conclusion that distributive justice can only be implemented within a multi-species political entity that deliberates on matters of fairness and compensation, among others (Celermajer et al., 2023).

The normativity of NBS has significant implications for designing research methodologies. We must avoid treating "nature" as an object of value-free sciences and instead recognize nature as having agency and autonomous interests, entering a dialogue with the researchers. This perspective contrasts with the engineering view of NBS, which treats natural entities as mere tools, lacking dignity and autonomy. Acknowledging the normativity of NBS means that we need to find ways to access, understand, and value the autonomous subjectivity of nature in relation to the living beings that constitute nature within specific ecosystems. As we see, this discussion eventually results in the deconstruction of "nature" that we discussed in D 2.1. Indeed, the use of the term "nature" creates many conceptual troubles, since it implies a binary between "nature" and "non-nature", with the latter typically associated with the human domain. We will discuss these issues in the next chapter.

Indeed, stating the challenge this way commits a fallacy that inheres the term of "nature-based" and many similar uses of "nature". Ecolinguistic research has shown that a key factor in humanity's strained relationship with nature is the use of mass terms, abstract concepts, or types of processes that conceal the agency of living

beings when referring to "nature" and factually destroy the possibility of genuine relationality which can only materialize in relationships between individualized subjectivities (Stibbe, 2021, p. 159ff). For example, when exploring the environmental values of humans related to NBS (such as people living near a forest developed as an NBS for coping with climate change), we should not inquire about attitudes towards "nature" in general, but instead ask how people experience interacting with trees and animals in the forest. Using the term "nature" is a standard practice in established tools of environmental psychology, such as the "Environmental Identity Scale" (Ariccio and Mosca, 2023), and thereby imports implicitly value-loaded stances into the research method.

The use of research methods has become an ethical issue, particularly in studies involving humans. This ethical concern also extends to the use of animals in human experiments, which is now being evaluated ethically, however, often by prioritizing human interests (Singer and Harari, 2023). Hence, ethical considerations should encompass a broader scope, such as the question of whether we should take an instrumental approach to nature, as implied by the term NBS. This ethical issue becomes a meta-ethical problem: What values should we uphold regarding nature, and how do we choose these values (Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, IPBES, 2022)? Should we prioritize instrumental values over intrinsic values, and does doing so violate ethical principles?

These ethical considerations have practical implications for research methods. For example, do we engage in epistemic violence against animals if we do not recognize them as autonomous and sentient actors in our understanding of "nature"? After all, this denial of recognition has been endemic in human-human relationships, such as the treatment of slaves or women in early Western modernity. Until today, feminist research challenges the alleged value-neutrality of science, and is often invoked in ecological and sustainability sciences as offering entirely new perspectives on issues such as relationality with "nature" (Haraway, 2016). Such controversies and tensions can be made productive in developing research methods on the ground, which is the task of this report (box 1.1.)

Box 1.1: Nature in common pool role board games

Role-based board games (RBG)* are a research method that traces back to Elinor Ostrom's work on common pool governance and performance ((Ostrom, 2015/1990). Ostrom argued that laboratory experiments can provide significant insights into how people interact and communicate about managing common pool resources in real-world environments, potentially leading to sustainable solutions (Ostrom, 2006; Poteete et al. 2011). Her work has inspired a substantial body of literature on combining laboratory approaches with field experiments (Janssen, 2010; Prediger et al., 2011)), further developed in various formats ((Falk et al., 2023; Tu et al., 2023)). In this general framework, RBG is a method grounded in agent-based modelling and seminally developed by the Arizona State University laboratory (<https://gamesforsustainability.org/>). In the COEVOLVERS team, RBG is further developed by the CETIP network and IFE SAS to study people's behaviour in the context of common pool resources and to raise awareness of the interdependencies of human actions, supporting collective learning (Špaček et al., 2019; Kluvankova et al. 2020) (see box 4.10)

The standard version of RBG assumes that the "nature" of the mechanisms driving the production of common pool resources is implicit. For instance, a forest used for logging exhibits certain growth mechanics of trees that interact with logging activities, and due to the incentive structure, there is a risk of over-harvesting the tree resource. In this scenario, various human "roles" are involved, such as businesspeople and environmental activists, each pursuing different strategies. Recognizing nature can take different forms, which are being explored in developing new versions of RBG in the COEVOLVERS WP 4 team as a tool for ecosemiotic modeling (Figure 2).

Figure 2: RBG with various human roles and inclusive of a forest iconic species representative CETIP / IFE SAS

One approach is to assign a separate role to "nature" that responds to people's actions according to specific parameters. This means assuming that nature takes on different states randomly or according to rules defined by the game designers. In this case, nature does not have agency or sentience. Another option is to introduce non-human entities

with agency, such as wild animals living in the forest or even trees that have agency in the long run (for example, migrating to other places). On this new RGB dubbed ECOPLY, see box 4.10.

As we will discuss later, one approach is to include an iconic species that is both ecologically and culturally significant (see box 2.6). The normativity of NBS requires adopting versions of RGB where non-humans have agency. In practice, this means that humans must be assigned to these roles since the non-humans cannot take part in the game without representation. For example, the ecological dynamics in a forest are often shaped by a keystone species such as a top predator. Overharvesting a forest can seriously affect those animals who may respond in various ways, such as approaching human settlements in search of food. In the RGB, a human may adopt the role of such an animal and autonomously decide on the strategy to be taken in the game. These roles can be constructed by combining general ecological knowledge and local citizens' familiarity with the species, hence their local ecological knowledge, in a meticulous manner, for example, by constructing roles as personas (such as individualizing the deer in figure 2 by telling about his biography, circumstances of living, kin relations and so on; for details, see box 4.7).

The example shows that the starting point of the methodological transformation is recognizing the value-loaded treatment of "nature" as a mere pool of resources that is managed and exploited by humans as the only entities with agency.

* The Role Board Game (RBG) has been developed by Tatiana Kluvankova, Martin Špaček, Marco A. Janssen et al, and it is now under co-development and operative modification to fit and address the multiple settings and circumstances studied in COEVOLVERS project.

In conclusion, we acknowledge that research methods are not value-free in CEA-NBS but are subject to ethical scrutiny far beyond the standard approaches to institutionalized research ethics, for example, when investigating vulnerable human groups affected by an NBS. More fundamentally, even the theoretical constructs underlying the design of specific methods have an ethical dimension. This is what we refer to as epistemic justice. This notion has been mostly referred to humans only, which is significant in the current context since epistemic injustice mostly affects vulnerable and marginalized groups (Samaržija and Cerovac, 2021). This report transcends these meanings to include other species.

1.1.2. Normative sciences, 2.0

How can we further develop the concept of normativity in research methodology? Charles S. Peirce's (1992, p. 196ff) normative sciences – ethics, aesthetics, and logic – are essential in our coevolutionary approach. More than a century later, we interpret these three terms in a more specific context, laying a theoretical foundation for CEA NBS methodology.

- *Logic* refers to the methodological standards of scientific inquiry informed by the modern philosophy of science and related fields. In practical terms, for example, this involves defining methods to compare qualitative research results in a way that can be understood and compared by different people. This encompasses questions about the validity of different observers' perspectives in achieving "objectivity" without claiming the position of an external observer with an "all-seeing eye" (the "view from nowhere" Nagel, 1989). This is particularly important when considering the divide between experts and non-experts, as well as incorporating non-human viewpoints.
- *Ethics* refers to general issues of justice across different species, based on an approach that avoids taking the "view from nowhere" and instead considers multiple perspectives of reality. In this approach, ethics plays a role in how our supposedly unbiased methods reconstruct non-human behaviour by imposing human categories, which establishes human epistemic hegemony (box 1.2).
- *Aesthetics* refers to how different viewpoints are expressed, displayed through actions, and can be appreciated by various observers in a multi-species context. In this research methodology, the focus is on creating an artistic representation of reality that acknowledges diverse perspectives. For example, humans cannot perceive the world in the same way as an earthworm, but artistic methods can help us imagine the earthworm's world. This aligns with the concept of "landscape" as discussed in D 2.1.

Box 1.2: Territoriality

The concept of epistemic hegemony involves the widespread belief that animal territoriality can be understood as a form of controlling resources, similar to exclusive property rights. This perspective is influenced by theories of behavioural ecology, which apply economic models such as game theory or foraging theory to animal behaviour (Gibson, 2021). However, this view has increasingly attracted criticism, arguing that it distorts the true meaning of territorial behaviour, particularly in birds (Despret, 2019; Prum, 2017). Researchers now recognize the autonomous agency and intentionality of animals, which do not necessarily operate according to the calculations assumed in economic models. For instance, rituals of territoriality can be seen as promoting inclusive cohabitation, and are even appreciated as aesthetic practices by humans. However, there is also the case of mutual reinforcement of human aesthetics and epistemic hegemony: When dogs leave marks in the environment, this is often misinterpreted as marking an

exclusive territory, motivating philosopher Michel Serres to speculate about the “dirty” origins of private property (Serres, 2012). In fact, this anthropocizes canine aesthetics and misinterprets what is in fact a medium of messaging among dogs, hence enabling co-habitation.

As a result, the research methodology not only adapts theory to better understand non-human behaviour, but also encourages an aesthetic approach in designs that incorporate this new understanding of territoriality. Territoriality is also crucial in many NBS that activate entire ecosystems to generate ecosystem services, such as Mangrove forests in coastal regions. Hence CEA-NBS suggests integrating aesthetic landscape thinking with an ecosemiotic approach to territoriality. One important precursor of this thinking was Heini Hediger and his approach to design zoological gardens in terms of the plurality of Umwelts of the animals that live in these territories (Chrulew, 2020).

An important consequence of adopting the normative sciences view is that the institutionalized boundaries between science and other forms of knowledge creation collapse. This position is fully elaborated in Dewey’s work on the arts (Dewey, 2005). This view originates from German idealism, where the arts were seen as a domain of human knowledge equal to, if not more powerful than science (Herrmann-Pillath, 2020). In the context of CEA NBS, these views become practically relevant when approaching knowledge held by local people, a topic well-developed in the literature on Indigenous knowledge and the forms of articulating and recording it (Alexander, 2013). Firstly, the media of Indigenous knowledge are often viewed as art from the perspective of hegemonic sciences, which implies that it is a matter of epistemic justice to recognize these media on par with established science, as in the “two-eyed seeing” methodology (Bartlett et al., 2012). Secondly, the representation of knowledge may itself require artful means beyond the standard formats of scientific publications, blurring the lines between scientific reports and media such as nature writing (Maran, 2020a; Wheeler, 2016). A key example is the mapping of a landscape as a territory: Maps never directly capture reality but are artistic means to capture what is defined as “objective” (Daston and Galison, 2010). In CEA-NBS, mapping the NBS landscape becomes a transdisciplinary venture that can be inspired by Indigenous mapping (Box 1.3) (on mapping in COEVOLVERS, see boxes 1.8, 2.12).

Box 1.3: Mapping Indigenous knowledge

An example of epistemic hegemony and even violence is the use of scientific mapping in dispossessing Indigenous people (Bhandar, 2018). Maps disembody the relationship

between living beings and land, and the related institution of property blanks out the possession of land by other species, which are just assigned to the abstract plots identified on maps (Vanuxem, 2022). These maps are static and do not reflect the actual life world of many species, including those humans who are not attached to a single piece of land, such as nomads or hunters who roam over wide territories. These activities generate knowledge that is not tied to specific places but opens the view on the mobility patterns over a larger range. Resulting from these insights, researchers have launched projects of alternative mapping by Indigenous people which appear to be artwork for eyes only trained to see scientific maps. The Indigenous maps show flows of events and fluid connectivities and downplay fixed assignments and boundaries of places. Tellingly, mapping becomes a political issue since until today the official scientific maps are used to fix property claims which clash with the different claims of Indigenous people (for a detailed case in West Papua, see (Chao, 2022). Modern digital technologies allow for creating multidimensional maps which reflect diverse experiences of place, such as in aboriginal spirituality (Povinelli, 2016, p. 158).

Figure 3: Indigenous mapping in West Papua

<https://www.sapiens.org/culture/indigenous-mapmaking/>

1.1.3. Co-evolutionary epistemology

Our CEA-NBS methodology is based on another Peircean idea that is fundamental to modern approaches to evolutionary epistemology (Nodelman, 2023). Evolutionary epistemology views epistemic processes as a population-level phenomenon following the logic of variation, selection, and retention, akin to Darwinian principles. This

perspective rejects the anthropocentric "genius" view of scientific discovery, instead arguing that new knowledge is generated collectively in epistemic communities, beyond the control or full awareness of individuals as members. Extending this logic, we conclude that knowledge is generated in various epistemic communities, not limited to human ones, and no community can claim dominance, despite modern science's current hegemony. Evolutionary epistemology proposes an ecological perspective on knowledge, emphasizing the distributed cognitive capabilities of specific collectives of actors over individual cognitive capacities. This view extends the notion of "epistemic community" to all forms of evolutionary and collective knowledge-generating processes, including other species and biological evolution. Biological evolution originally inspired evolutionary epistemology (Popper, 1979), and some scholars now even consider non-living materiality as part of what is called "planetary intelligence" (Frank et al., 2022).

This viewpoint addresses practical issues in designing NBS that arise from unintended consequences of human interventions in nature, particularly in relation to feedback mechanisms affecting biodiversity. There are several limitations to predicting the outcomes of interventions over longer time periods in the human sciences, and the evolutionary processes triggered by the intervention can themselves generate knowledge. One implication for the logic of inquiry is the use of experimental methods, similar to the randomized experiments employed in economics in recent decades (Duflo, 2020). Since interventions cannot be evaluated independently of the larger ecosystem context, it is important to conduct experimental NBS at different locations that share as many features as possible and to systematically employ longitudinal research over decades (as is the case with urban forests and other green spaces with trees as key elements of the NBS). The institutional form of such an approach is the Living Lab (see section 1.5).

The CEA-NBS emphasizes the importance of a co-evolutionary epistemology, which involves triggering and sustaining evolutionary processes of knowledge co-production among different epistemic communities co-habiting at the NBS location. The goal of CEA-NBS is to incorporate as many processes as possible and to make the resulting knowledge accessible and comparable across these communities. This methodology,

known as the transdisciplinary approach (Rigolot, 2020), extends the epistemic community beyond the scientific one, as expressed in "two-eyed seeing" that we mentioned previously. However, the evolutionary framework takes this normative stance further by recognizing many more-than-human epistemic communities, aligning with the normative idea of shared flourishing within the multi-species community.

1.1.4. Normativity and finality

Using evolutionary theory as a reference allows us to base our approach's normativity on certain ontological assumptions. Peirce argued that evolutionary processes cannot be fully understood without the notion of final causality, which is commonly avoided in modern sciences (Deacon, 2013; Short, 2007). However, when considering transformative claims in sustainability research, the crucial point is that we must find ways to create certain conditions today that result in evolutionary dynamics that we cannot fully control or even predict, yet move towards a certain desired goal. While we have general criteria, such as shared flourishing in a multi-species community, we cannot set specific goals. For example, we can aim to support future biodiversity, but we cannot determine the exact species composition of the community (see box 1.5). This means that even though the processes follow standard conceptions of efficient causality, finality plays a role in shaping the directness of the processes and the final outcome. As we evaluate the outcome normatively, research on such processes falls within the domain of normative sciences.

The concept of finality is the underlying idea behind flourishing (see below, section 1.3). In practical terms, finality defines the experimental approach on a small scale: Interventions do not directly aim for specific outcomes, but instead create conditions and leave the actual determination to autonomous and spontaneous forces (box 1.4).

Box 1.4: Miyawaki forests

The Miyawaki method of creating urban mini-forests is an excellent example of co-evolutionary design and knowledge generation (Lewis, 2022; Qi et al., 2024). This NBS provides various ecosystem services, such as helping to reduce heat waves in cities and

promoting the natural development of biodiversity as a knowledge-generating process. When planting the forest, the people involved may not know exactly which trees, bushes, and other plants are the best choices. However, experts can suggest a range of options that may suit the local micro-climate, soil conditions, and other factors. A wide variety of plant species is then chosen, and seedlings are planted in a trial pattern based on existing knowledge. The forest is then left to grow naturally, with minimal intervention in the early stages of growth (such as watering when necessary). This allows for a rapid evolutionary process, and the final result is not predetermined by human designers. As the plants grow, they attract animals, further enhancing biodiversity. Overall, the Miyawaki method promotes knowledge generation within the forest community while working towards the common goal of improving living conditions in cities. Typically, Miyawaki forests are transdisciplinary projects that engage neighbourhoods in planting and caring for the project, with expert advice at critical stages such as the initial selection of plants. The forests can become places of nurturing eco-stewardship, caring for biodiversity (box 4.8). Observing the forest evolving can become an educational activity for children, or harvesting fruits and berries can become a part of local festivals,

Figure 4: Miyawaki forest in Germany

<https://www.miya-forest.de/miyawaki>

1.1.5. Knowledge co-production, performativity of language and world making

The key challenge in engaging diverse communities and driving evolutionary processes is finding a way to communicate different types of knowledge in a manner that allows for generalization across communities. Ultimately, these communications lay the groundwork for coexisting within a shared ecosystem community. Translation plays a crucial role in this process and is a significant contribution by the human

knowledge community, particularly the community of experts engaging in transdisciplinarity (Cronin, 2017). In sustainability research, the important concept is the collaborative creation of knowledge, for which significant work has established basic rules and practical guidelines, albeit only for humans so far (Norström et al., 2020). This means that the discussion is still in human language, although in different idioms that may initially be incompatible, such as the languages of biology and indigenous spirituality when describing natural phenomena. The rules and practices of translation are themselves normative, both ethically and aesthetically. Without translation, transdisciplinarity is a distant goal.

The normative sciences' Peircean triad of ethics, logic and aesthetics becomes fully relevant at this point. This is further strengthened when considering the translation of non-human knowledge, such as species-specific views or even individual organisms' perspectives on certain NBS facts. There are principled challenges regarding the different physical features of sensing and expressing (Yong, 2022). These issues of translation are a major methodological concern of CEA-NBS. To revisit the Indigenous case, there is not only the issue of mutual translation with scientific language but also the point that Indigenous views often claim to be translations of other species' perspectives (Chao, 2022; Kohn, 2013). The extent to which scientific language can offer an alternative translation is a matter of dispute and is mostly done in fields deemed marginal to mainstream science, such as biosemiotics and Umwelt analysis (Maran, 2020a).

A key idea in semiotics (discussed in detail in chapter 2) is that translation is not limited to human languages but is a universal process (Kull, 2023). It begins with the translation between different molecular codes in genetic reproduction. Biotranslation refers to the translation between different semiotic systems beyond human language (Kull and Torop, 2003). However, as demonstrated by Quine (Quine, 2013), there are inherent limits to translation when aiming for a shared objective reference. Translation among humans and between humans and non-humans encounter the same challenge – there will always be something that cannot be translated, and therefore remains unknown and unfamiliar. Lotman (2009) sees this realm of the unknown as a source of creativity and evolutionary potential.

Translations, when they guide the practical design of NBS purposes, are deeply aesthetic. This is evident in the way a shared feeling and appreciation of the world reflects the shared flourishing of the multi-species community. This is epitomized quite literally in the shared flourishing of flowers, pollinators, and human gardeners (Kull, 2022). However, we cannot simply define specific binding aesthetic norms, as they also evolve alongside transformative changes (Prum, 2013). This process is political, involving dissent and conflict about norms, such as divergent views on the aesthetic features of the NBS in its specific location (Frantzeskaki, 2019; Saito, 2007). Therefore, CEA-NBS not only studies the socio-politics of NBS but becomes a part of it, following the Chicago tradition of progressive pragmatism. This raises a critical issue at the heart of the concept of normative science: Peirce claimed that normative science could be grounded in objectivity. This objectivity cannot be defined solely by hegemonic science standards. In a normative science, objectivity arises from the ethical commitments of researchers to impartiality, a topic we discuss in detail in section 2.3.1."

This observation touches on an important aspect of normative sciences in the context of modern philosophy of social science (seminally, Horkheimer, 2011). It emphasizes that normative sciences are performative in a strong sense, meaning that they have a significant impact on the way people behave and how they perceive the world: The now classical case is economics (Boldyrev and Svetlova, 2016). In essence, normative sciences contribute to shaping the world, rather than providing direct ethical instructions derived from a theory. This world-making is what ultimately drives behavioural change and less direct ethical and political prescriptions (Houston et al., 2018). This diagnosis, as in the case of economics, implies that in choosing a theory, even if aiming at "objectivity", we must consider its performative effects, which can only be evaluated from an ethical viewpoint, which CEA-NBS defines as multi-species justice.

We summarize the discussion with a case study in Box 1.5.

Box 1.5: Urban greenery

Urban greenery serves multiple functions and provides various ecosystem services. Designing urban greenery involves considering modern ecological and biological sciences. Advanced methods are used to assess the performance of tree species in delivering services such as shading and water retention (Behm et al., 2022). However, one challenge is to forecast the future conditions of urban ecology and the adaptability of tree species to these conditions in order to sustainably produce expected ecosystem services (Gulstrud et al., 2018). It is important to note that the current standards of NBS prioritize biodiversity goals. Hence, we cannot judge ecosystem services only by taking humans as stakeholders in the entire process (Hernandez-Santin et al., 2023). This complicates the research challenge as it requires understanding future multi-species ecosystem services and assessing the entire urban ecosystem in the context of interventions such as designing and planting street greenery. This knowledge can be produced by the scientific community, but also by evolutionary processes of species diffusion and selection, which interplay with the evolutionary epistemics of the scientific community observing the former: We arrange a setting for co-evolutionary processes in designing urban greenery. However, it is humans who create the context for these processes, and aesthetics play a role in this creation.

When designing urban settings such as buildings, roads, and greenery, we inadvertently create opportunities for other species. These species generate knowledge in response to the affordances we create. Urban aesthetics involve conflicting judgments from different observers, especially in the politics of implementing Nature-Based Solutions. The design of greenery is a political process in which only human voices are typically considered, often excluding the voices of the most vulnerable people. a wide range of ecosystem services.

Urban aesthetics involve conflicting judgments from various observers, particularly in the realm of NBS politics. Citizen preferences may differ from expert recommendations for greenery design, and they may feel disturbed or harmed by other species that emerge as a result of the evolutionary dynamic (Raymond et al., 2017a). Therefore, the design of urban greenery is a political process where human voices often take precedence, potentially influenced by local power dynamics and excluding the voices of the most vulnerable individuals.

1.2. NBS as co-evolutionary technology: Bridging D 2.1 and D 2.2

1.2.1. Niche construction

The traditional approach to NBS often views NBS as an engineering solution similar to green infrastructure (Chatzimentor et al., 2020). This means it is seen as a technological fix that prioritizes sustainability and involves living matter in solving specific human-defined problems. The delivery D 2.1 presented a different view, which is summarized in Figure 15 D 2.1 reproduced here as Fig. 5.

Figure 5: NBS as niche construction

In this perspective, NBS are seen as a form of human niche construction, often also referred to as “cultural niche construction” (Nagatsu et al., 2023). This concept goes beyond human intentional design. For example, consider a beaver community: Beavers build dams to ensure their own survival and reproduction, but the resulting ponds create complex ecosystems with many species that adapt to and thrive in this environment (of course, there are also trade-offs, since the niche transformation harms some incumbents). This transforms the beaver's niche into a co-evolutionary multi-species habitat. This natural model can be applied to NBS as human niche construction: The objective is to create an NBS as a multi-species habitat sustained by human-driven infrastructural activities, such as urban greening. In this context, the concept of infrastructure is linked to the idea of landscape as a more-than-human concept: a landscape represents the different environments of the various members of the NBS. This means that the landscape, while is actively shaped by human niche construction, is a multi-world across different scales and scopes. The greenery shapes the urban landscape as perceived by humans, while trees serve as landscapes for insects living on the leaves and bark. The challenge of D 2.2 is to develop a

methodological toolbox that enables us to approach the NBS as a multi-species habitat in this sense.

Box 1.6: Co-producing niches as NBS with beavers

In many countries, beavers are increasingly being recognized for their contribution to local water management and ecosystem design. They create ponds and support wetlands without cost measured in human monetary terms, apart from potential damage to human property. After two centuries of being treated as a resource for trapping and hunting, they are now seen as collaborators in human niche construction (Welden, 2023). However, there are significant differences in how beavers are treated as autonomous actors in the human community.

At one extreme, beavers are being reconceptualized from resources to tools, perhaps as workers similar to living robots or as cheap labor. This view emphasizes the functional aspect of infrastructure while also acknowledging the ecological needs of beavers. However, beavers can resist such exploitation by moving away from the location and not following human goals. They may perceive the functionality of the infrastructure differently from humans and express disagreement, leading to a process of co-evolutionary knowledge production.

At the other extreme, beavers can be recognized as full members of the local community, paving the way towards a multi-species community. This recognizes the diversity of Umwelts and the agencies involved. This means that humans collaborating with beavers in building the NBS take their interests into full consideration and may even act as representatives of beavers. Concrete issues where different conceptualizations are important include the size of ponds created by beaver dams and the permeability of the dams to water flows. In such cases, beaver interests may conflict with human interests, raising the question of how much weight should be given to the former. In a genuine multi-species community, beavers have a voice and contribute to knowledge-generating deliberation in institutionalized human politics. Eventually, humans can learn from beavers about water management, thus cohabitating in a community of inquiry.

Figure 6: Beaver dam and human learning from beavers

1.2.2. Doing the NBS

In a normative science, the methods chosen must relate to the doing of the NBS and its results in terms of the flourishing of the multi-species niche. In D 2.1 we have analyzed the doing of NBS in five interlocking steps (Fig. 18 D 2.1):

- *NbS are ways of place-shaping* for humans and other species, which implies practically that one cannot only consider single NbS but must adopt a holistic approach to landscape design and evolution.
- *NbS are artwork* in terms of activating the co-creative development of multi-species affordances directed at evolutionary potential in the future.
- *NbS are practices* engaging many actors, human and other species, in which function and meaning are integrated by specific expressive means, such as rituals.
- *NbS are care* in fostering attitudes of mutual recognition and peaceful co-habitation.
- *NbS are flourishing* in the sense of shared creation of future potentials for self-realization of all members of the more-than-human community, and of maintaining a rich and productive web of interactions.

Figure 7: Reciprocity and interlocking ways of doing an NBS

In the normative sciences knowing and doing are deeply and systematically intertwined. This means:

- Place-shaping is not just informed by the knowledge that is created by an external scientific expert but activates the knowledge immanent to the perspectives of the different actors engaging in the place-shaping. The landscape is not a physical object independent from the act of observation but only comes into being by looking at it from a specific position. We cannot know about the landscapes of other beings without interacting with them, which includes scientific methods but also, as outlined, the epistemic doings by non-experts and non-humans.
- The integration of these diverse perspectives is a creative act of its own methodological status and can only be done from a specific position without claiming epistemic hegemony; hence, it is a work of art. This approach is also essential in implementing the NBS so that functions identified scientifically can only be realized in aesthetic mediation.
- Artwork is a form of practice so that knowledge becomes embodied in the flow of interlaced actions of the NBS community. This is significant when considering the rationality traps that lurk in all human decision-making, such

as when trying to rely on cost-benefit analysis to choose actions in implementing an NBS.

- The beacon guiding practice is care which is essential in realizing reciprocity between people and nature. Care in doing reflects the normativity of the NBS and presupposes knowledge about needs and conditions of multi-species flourishing.
- The outcome of doing the NBS is shared flourishing of the multi-species community while the standard of flourishing is not defined by humans exclusively regarding other species.

The principle of reciprocity goes beyond just balancing costs and benefits; it also involves mutual recognition. An important challenge is that while other species may recognize us, we may not always recognize them in return. This concept is evident in domesticated animals like dogs and horses, and is appreciated by humans who value being recognized by these animals. Translating this concept to other situations is difficult, especially for animals that live near humans but remain wild, referred to as “liminal” by (Donaldson and Kymlicka, 2013). This becomes increasingly relevant as urban biodiversity changes, leading to more non-domesticated animals in urban areas (box 1.7). In fact, recent efforts to rewild cities even embrace this idea of liminality (Apfelbeck et al., 2020; World Economic Forum, 2022). Such initiatives reverse a fundamental secular trend starting in the early 19th century to conceive modern urbanity in terms of tightly regulating the presence of liminal animals, for example, in the decade-long battle against stray dogs which grounded in conceptions of civility of both humans and pet dogs, as opposed to the savage nature of stray dogs (Pearson, 2021) (see also box 3.1).

Box 1.7: Owls migrating to cities

In Australia, climate change is increasingly threatening the habitat of owls, particularly old trees that provide nesting places and an abundance of prey. As a result, owls are moving to cities and becoming a nuisance to some citizens. This shift is causing owls to become more prominent in urban areas, and it raises the question of how the human community will respond.

Figure 8: Owls meeting citizens (Parker et al. 2022a)

Researchers have developed an approach to attract owls by providing owl houses as nesting places (Parker et al., 2022a). This is a challenging task because the design of these houses must resemble natural nesting places, such as cavities in old trees (Parker et al., 2022b). Additionally, the owl houses are quite large and visible to citizens.

Figure 9: Artful design of owlhouse (ibid.)

Researchers are facing a threefold challenge: first, they need to engineer the owl houses; second, they need to make them visually appealing to humans; and third, they

need to ensure that both humans and owls recognize and accept these new nesting sites. It is not enough to just come up with an engineering solution, as the way humans and owls interact will determine whether the new nesting sites are successful. For example, some humans might disturb the owls, and the owls may leave debris that attracts rats. Therefore, simply building owl houses won't work without creating a community process where humans see the owls as part of the community, and the owls don't perceive humans as threats. In the case of owls, this process can involve creating narratives and artwork celebrating owls, as well as using behavioral science to establish norms for cohabitation (Ackerman, 2023).

1.3. Fundamental concepts of CEA-NBS

In this section, we will introduce important concepts that we will use in the following chapters. These concepts are meant to establish a foundation for an approach that considers multiple species in the normative sciences of NBS. The challenge is to ensure that these concepts do not inherently differentiate between human and non-human capabilities and properties. For instance, using language as the primary medium for shaping a place may hinder the perception of NBS as a community that includes multiple species. Instead, we should focus on non-cognitive and non-linguistic concepts (Raymond et al., 2017b).

An NBS is an assemblage of various objects and living beings that interact regularly to create a sustainable pattern of cohabitation. Therefore, all concepts must provide a cohesive view of the entirety of the NBS and should not be in conflict with each other, both theoretically and methodologically. For instance, when studying humans, we might be tempted to explore their subjective intentions, values, opinions about the NBS using language-based methods like interviews. While this information is interesting and important, the CEA-NBS considers it supplementary because people often express values and opinions that may contradict their actual behaviour. Additionally, the NBS performance is not primarily influenced by these factors, and it goes against principles of fairness to other species who do not communicate in human language. These perspectives are relevant when considering a specific human sub-sector of the NBS, such as the local administration's management of the NBS budget. However, insights into the co-evolution of the NBS will be limited as there will be many

unintended consequences of human actions, which in the long run also affect these actions.

Figure 10: Conceptual domains in CEA-NBS

It is important to define a set of non-speciesist concepts and avoid the epistemic enforcement of anthropocentric concepts on other species (see above, box 1.2). As shown in figure 10, this means that we must carefully distinguish between human and more-than-human concepts. Using “more-than-human” here implies that those concepts are inclusive of humans and non-humans, such that these concepts lay the ground to overcome epistemic injustice in NBS design and implementation. For example, employing the concept of embodiment means closing the human/nature gap (Merleau-Ponty, 2021). On the other hand, there are concepts that separate the human domain from non-humans: For example, values are mostly seen as being accessible to human reflexivity and are invoked in discourses as reasons explaining one’s opinions and actions (Mercier and Sperber, 2018). However, as we will see, in the co-evolutionary approach there is also the possibility of rethinking human concepts in more-than-human terms. For example, deliberation is mostly seen as linked to language, but we develop a notion of embodied deliberation. The co-evolutionary

approach does not take the boundaries between the two conceptual domains for granted (indicated by broken lines) and aims to orchestrate a shift away from anthropocentrism in scientific methods and terminologies (Braidotti, 2019). In doing so, we also recognize a transitory domain (smaller circle) where concepts are included that already travel across the domains, such as beauty (Nüsslein-Volhard, 2019) or ritual (Stephenson, 2015).

1.3.1. Practice

In our initial concept, we introduce the idea of practice (Voß et al., 2023). Practice refers to a pattern of action that is carried out and experienced by any type of actor at a specific place and time. A practice is a distributed pattern that may involve more than one actor. For instance, the practice of people walking with dogs in forests and other animals responding to these actions. Therefore, practice involves complex assemblages of actors and objects at the location where it occurs. Consequently, practice is an epistemic object with its own status and cannot be simply reduced to the human actor and intentionality (Bourdieu, 2019).

We are interested in practices that involve physical actions and engage multiple actors using all sensory media, and we do not make a conceptual distinction between human and non-human actions. For example, when humans play with dogs, it is a practice that involves both actors without prioritizing the human (Merritt, 2021). Many human-dog interactions are epistemically coercive in disregarding the specificity of embodied forms of canine cognition, thus constituting forms of epistemic violence, often even endorsed by supposedly scientific methods of behavioural sciences (Gibson, 2021, pp. 89f, 213f).

It is important that practice is not a one-time action but recurrent through time, though involving all kinds of changes. As such, a practice is an evolutionary phenomenon. The important methodological consequence is that we cannot capture the dynamic aspect of practice by statistical and, hence, quantitative methods. These methods require the identification of a fixed type of event that occurs in time and space with a certain probability. A practice is not such type of event as it can take many forms and

shapes and is evolving. These variations are random but not probabilistic, hence manifest propensities of occurrence, and they connect with each other not via a clearly defined category of event, but via family resemblances. For example, observers may categorize a certain practice as dog walking and record the observed frequencies. However, it is not clear whether a specific instance is indeed dog walking, despite we see a woman and a dog walking along a path in the forest. Perhaps they are conducting a dog training session, or the dog is taken to another home where she will stay for some time because the woman leaves for a business trip, and so forth. As we see, a crucial aspect of practice is its meaning, and meanings can evolve, such as changing the meaning of dog walking: Perhaps this has changed from a regular habit to a mandatory healing practice prescribed by a doctor.

It is important to understand that practice is not a one-time action but a recurring and evolving phenomenon. This means that practice involves various changes over time. Traditional statistical and quantitative methods cannot fully capture the dynamic aspect of practice because they rely on identifying fixed types of events with certain probabilities. However, practice can take many forms and shapes and is constantly evolving, making it difficult to categorize using traditional statistical methods. For example, observers may categorize a certain activity as "dog walking" based on their observations, but the true nature of the activity may be more complex, such as dog training or temporary care for the dog. Hence, it is not clear whether a specific instance is indeed dog walking, despite we see a woman and a dog walking along a path in the forest. The meaning of practices can evolve over time, leading to changes in how they are perceived and categorized. Perhaps what was dog-walking in the past is now a prescribed healing practice after the woman suffered from depression.

Practice can be approached in a non-anthropocentric way, which allows the integration of various research methods across disciplines (Box 1.8).

Box 1.8: Research of practices across species boundaries COEvolvers

In D.2.1 we already discussed the concept of affordances and its application in analyzing human and non-human interactions with the environment. It highlights that affordances are equally relevant to both human and non-human actions and, therefore, count as a

more-than-human concept of CEA-NBS (see below, 1.3.5.). For example, a landscape can be viewed as an assemblage of affordances for all species living there. Researchers use observational data and instruments such as heat maps to understand human activity patterns within the landscape, including activities like walking, picnicking, and bird-watching (Mishra et al., 2023). They also identify affordances that were not necessarily planned by designers. These methods rely on direct observations of actions and do not necessarily apply additional surveys and interviews. Similarly, researchers analyze the activities of animals in a given location and relate them to affordances, which is referred to as ecological repertoire analysis (Maran, 2020b). Both methods are interconnected when considering interactions between humans and other species, such as the practice of feeding birds.

In a transdisciplinary turn, the results of such research can be combined with experiential mapping by the members of an NBS which stays in line with Indigenous mapping discussed in box 1.3. Participants identify different layers of maps projected on an area that focus on specific aspects, such as walking, events in meeting other species, or auditory experiences (Fig. 11).

Figure 11: Participatory mapping at Murray Park (WP 5, Hutton Institute team)

The approach focuses on human experiences, but participants gain awareness of non-human activities and concerns through continuous reflection and discussion. The results can be further utilized by inputting them into a virtual nature tool (Fig. 12). This tool enables the evocation of embodied experiences from the perspectives of other species, such as the view of insects on the ground. It also allows human observers to activate elements of the soundscape associated with the visual flow by marking positions in the video. Participants can create other items, such as brief nature texts that evoke smells poetically, which can be downloaded at specific positions (see box 1.10).

Figure 12: Virtual nature tool: Murray Park (WP 5, Hutton Institute team)

1.3.2. Habit

How can we explain the generation and recurrence of practice? The key concept is habit (Robbins and Costa, 2017). Unlike practice, habit is a property of individuals that refers to their embodied motivations for carrying out actions. For example, I may have the habit of walking the dog every evening, which means that I feel the need to do so, and my dog expects me to do it as well. The mutual attunement is manifest in coordinated and synchronous actions, such as taking the lead, and moving around, which manifest the shared habit. It is important to note that habit is not related to unconscious mechanisms of action, as it involves awareness and anticipation. Habit is not automatism (a habit of driving a car is not the same as automatic driving it while talking to the fellow passenger). In the traditions of Peirce and Dewey, habits play an epistemological role in a dialectic of habit, prediction, and experience (Clark, 2023; Nöth, 2016). When individuals embody habits, they interact with the world and may encounter events that deviate from their habits, obstruct their actions, and challenge them. This negation of habit is the key mechanism for knowledge generation, as it prompts individuals to seek alternatives to fulfill the original function of the habit. Essentially, habits embody the world, and experiences that conflict with habits create feelings of uncertainty or even threat.

It is essential to avoid anthropocentrism when considering how different species respond to change. When habits are broken, it can lead to creative responses, but the specific mechanisms for these responses vary among species. For example, humans

may rely on individual rational thinking, while bees may search for information individually and communicate it to the hive through body movements in a pattern of distributed cognition. In this context, experimentation is an important more-than-human way of gaining knowledge that goes beyond habit. Experimentation can take on various forms, including the controlled experiments of the scientific method, trial-and-error problem-solving, and even individual actions that unintentionally lead to changes in group behavior.

Habits are a crucial concept in the CEA-NBS context because one of the aims of implementing the NBS is to change established habits in the community that contribute to unsustainable ways of life and violate principles of reciprocity between people and nature. Changing habits goes beyond simply agreeing to adopt a new practice, which often fails because of common rationality traps. Developing new habits means that the practice is embodied and therefore connects with the natural environment. This often requires transformative methods beyond conventional politics, such as creating and performing new rituals in relation to nature (Kimmerer, 2020) (box 1.9).

Box 1.9: Gardening as habit co-creating a world coevolvers

In the context of NBS, gardening serves as an important example of the influence of habit. Urban gardens, in various forms, are acknowledged as NBS that provide a wide range of ecosystem services, including environmental, social, and cultural benefits (Camps-Calvet et al., 2016; Sowińska-Świerkosz et al., 2021; van der Jagt et al., 2017) Unlike for-profit farming, gardening is guided by habits that develop from ongoing interactions between people and nature. The garden itself imposes practices on the gardener, who must adapt to local conditions, changing weather, and other factors. In essence, gardening represents a form of governance by nature, and habit embodies this governance through the creation of gardening practices (Herrmann-Pillath, 2024; Schwarz, 2023).

This interplay between habit and natural processes extends beyond institutionalized gardening. For instance, the cultivation of ecologically delicate forests in Japan aims to create conditions for the flourishing of Matsutake mushrooms (Tsing, 2017). The link between the practice and the outcome is fragile and unpredictable; people may even have to wait for decades for the Matsutake to appear. Consequently, the tending of the forest is not driven by a cost-benefit analysis, but rather by the nurturing of a habit, perhaps even as a ritual, against the backdrop of the spiritual significance of Matsutake. For more on this example, see box 4.12).

Figure 13 Gardening at Healing Garden Living Lab

COEVOLVERS Healing Garden Living Lab, Budapest, is exploring the potential of gardening to restore the mental health of patients at Boldog Gellért Hospital. Dementia can be seen as a disruption of habits and a disconnection from the world. Gardening can help to heal this by creating embodied experiences of the world and thereby regaining it. Patients engage in creating a garden and its elements, such as raised beds, through regular actions throughout the year. This process is accompanied by various methods to heighten awareness and experience of the garden's sensory environment, which lays the foundation for forming new habits in interaction with the plants and animals. One method currently being developed by the Healing Garden LL involves the sit-spot technique, where a person spends hours in one place, practicing mindfulness and automatic writing to notice sensory experiences without judgment. To aid in habit formation, this deliberate slowness is combined with time-lapse videos that showcase regular occurrences and activities throughout the year, enhanced with multiple sensory elements, such as sounds.

1.3.3. Embodiment

The concept of embodiment is fundamental in relation to other concepts such as habits and locates these terms in relation to specific schools of thought, such as ecological psychology. In the literature, there are different uses of the term, but we will focus only on commonalities (Read and Szokolszky, 2020). One point of divergence is the relationship between embodiment and distributed cognition, including external entities in the notion of embodiment. Distributed cognition can be seen as detached from the body, connecting an internal cognitive system with external entities in an emergent

computational system (Clark, 2011). To avoid falling back into disembodiment, as argued elsewhere, we differentiate between outward and inward embodiment (Basso and Herrmann-Pillath, 2024). This means that embodiment involves the external projection and expression of internal states of the body, such as in creating artifacts, and the integration of external entities and structures into the body. In the social sciences, an exemplary reference is Bourdieu's notion of "habitus" (Bourdieu, 2019). Embodiment relates to a wide range of literature, from phenomenology to neuroscience (Johnson, 2017). The latter reference is important for firmly grounding the concept in the biological sciences and hence collapsing the human/non-human divide (Damasio, 2019; Jasanoff, 2018)). The general meaning of the term is that all forms of cognition are grounded in sensorimotor circuits that link action and perception, and that arrange in ever more complex networks of reentry and multi-level processing such that all kinds of concepts are ultimately simulating actions in the world (Barsalou, 2008). Therefore, embodiment overcomes the popular distinction between the "two systems" of cognition, the intuitive and emotional versus the reflective and rational, which is especially strong in behavioural economics (Kahneman, 2012; Thaler, 2016), and which effectively internalizes the human/non-human divide in conceptualizing human behaviour as if a disembodied rational homunculus constantly struggles with a beast within.

These fundamental themes are important for CEA-NBS. Many methods and analytical perspectives on behaviour overlook the concept of embodiment. For example, some emphasize rational cognitive processes in planning and related public discourses (Manheim and Spackman, 2022). Others focus on linguistic and representational cognitive processes in understanding people's relationship with the natural environment. In practice, embodiment plays a significant role in themes such as the health effects of being in nature and interacting with other species (Marselle et al., 2019). This provides the rationale for the healing garden approach sketched in the previous box. Considering embodiment in methods suggests approaches that explore how bodily processes influence behavioural stances and valuations, which is applicable both analytically and for learning (box 1.10).

Box 1.10: Experiencing embodied knowledge: Sensory walks

In Western modernity, disembodiment is often associated with a focus on visual information. However, taking an embodiment perspective requires us to consider the full range of sensory experiences when exploring human attitudes towards other species. One method for doing this is the "sensory walk," where a group of participants walks through a natural area and mindfully explores the sensory spectrum. Despite the emphasis on visual aspects, people are also keenly aware of the auditory landscape in their relationship with nature. For example, bird-watching is often more about bird-listening, as many birds may not be visible. Following auditory cues can lead to finding places where birds are visible. Sensory walks encourage participants to focus on specific segments of the sensory spectrum, such as lying down and concentrating on the soundscape or exploring the sense of touch with their hands and feet (fig. 14).

Figure 14: Sensory walk at Tartu LL

The concept of sensory walks serves as both a research method and a learning opportunity. It allows researchers to study how people connect with nature through their senses, while providing participants with potentially transformative experiences. In participatory mapping, participants often place significant emphasis on the sounds they hear in a particular location. By using audio recordings, these experiences can be shared through digital maps. Advancements in technology also allow sensory walks to incorporate auditory experiences that are not usually accessible to humans, such as the communication of insects through plants (Yong, 2022). Auditory methods can serve a metaphorical function, freeing cognitive processes from linguistic constraints and fostering creative connections with nature. For instance, devices can enable people to listen to the sounds of plant life, inspiring musical activities. These auditory experiences, though not directly related to the acoustic functions of plants, can bring about metaphorical cognitive transformations that alter the relationship between humans and plants. One practical application is the therapeutic effects of listening to "plant music."

Figure 15: Plant music in Healing Gardent Living Lab

1.3.4. Meaning

The concepts of habit, practice and embodiment are unified through the concept of meaning, as demonstrated in the example of dog-walking: Both partners mutually perceive and interpret actions as meaning “Let’s go out!” Meaning is embodied in the action. We take a non-speciesist approach to meaning based on general semiotics and biosemiotics specifically (Hoffmeyer, 2009). In this approach, meaning is not referred to as linguistically mediated intentionality. Even in the context of language, meaning is not located in the mind of the speaker but in the response of the receiver, considered generally as a form of action, a view early developed by the pragmatists (Mead, 2015) and today a minority view in the philosophy of language (Millikan, 2005). We will delve into this in more detail in Chapter 2. It is important to notice here that meaning and function are, therefore, seen as two sides of the same coin. This does not dismiss the fact that different species have distinct ways of generating meaning: Humans have unique capacities of creating meanings and enacting them through a wide range of symbolic media. However, even in these cases, meaning emerges in the interaction with others. For example, the meaning of the word “table” is defined by

its functions. If I invite someone to “Sit down on the table”, this invitation may create confusion unless there is no chair in the room. If there are chairs, the receiver may ask back, “You mean, the chair?”, and if I insist on the table, she may feel curious about the reason. As we see, meaning is also related to habit, in the sense of habitual meaning. As Wittgenstein (Wittgenstein, 2009) has forcefully argued, language is embedded in forms of life and, hence, is a form of practice.

The semiotic approach to meaning defines the meaning of any kind of sign in terms of the action that generates a recurrent pattern of reproducing the sign-action link. In this sense, general evolution is a meaning-producing process (Macdonald and Papineau, 2006). For example, the colours of flowers may have the function of attracting pollinators, thus contributing to the survival and reproduction of both flowers and pollinators. In other words, the colours as signs generate the action as their meaning. One step further, the action also has a meaning for the flowers in the sense of generating a function. Rethinking the previous discussion of language, we can, therefore, approach language as a form of action and approach all action as meaningful.

As we will develop in section 2.2, approaching language as action is a key tenet of the theory of speech acts (Green, 2021). Most everyday uses of human language are actions that elicit actions from others; for example, I may explain the way to the main station to a foreigner by explaining the route or by some gestures, and the foreigner follows the meaning. Meaning is not exclusive to spoken and written language; all kinds of signs are meaningful (Hoffmeyer, 1996) By implication, in multi-species interaction practices can be coordinated via a great variety of signs that are themselves generated by actions, or the actions are the signs: The woman approaches the door, fetches the lead, and the dog immediately understands and joins.

Humans have a strong capacity to create meaningful connections that can involve other species in a spiritual world. This is particularly evident in Indigenous spirituality, which is often seen as a paradigm for establishing relationships between people and nature (Maller, 2021; Trospen, 2022). These relationships are expressed through meaningful interactions between humans and other species, often depicted as spirits.

However, similar forms of relationality can also be found outside of Indigenous contexts (see box 1.11).

Box 1.11: Speaking to trees

Trees are widely admired in almost all human societies, especially old and strong ones. However, trees are often sacrificed for economic projects. Protecting and nurturing trees is crucial in addressing the current climate crisis. This includes efforts to stop the logging of tropical forests and to green cities to combat rising temperatures (see box 1.5). The destruction of old trees is often a key factor in deteriorating habitats of many species (Holland and Roudavski, 2024). Respect for trees can be fostered through animistic beliefs, such as those found in Japanese Shinto, even in modern society (Rots, 2015). However, it is challenging to generalize such practices across different cultural contexts. There are numerous observations indicating that, even in postmodern societies, people tend to attribute meaning to trees beyond their natural functions. For instance, eco-burials are increasingly accepted in many societies, often driven by the belief that the deceased will eventually become a tree (Becher, 2021). Cemeteries can serve important functions as green spaces that foster biodiversity (Löki et al., 2019). An illustrative example of the spontaneous generation of meaning, even in the form of people talking to trees, is the case in Melbourne, where the municipality assigned email addresses to individual trees and invited citizens to report on the status of the trees (Gulsrud et al., 2018). Surprisingly, many people started to address the trees as individuals. Generally, naming individual animals and trees strongly activates human empathy and the willingness to recognize these beings as sentient and capable of forming meaningful relationships (see box 3.5). Artwork is a medium that can imbue NBS with meanings that inspire people to engage with other beings, including trees (Conte et al., 2024).

Figure 16: Artistic co-creation of tree ecosystem services

<https://www.climateartproject.com/aula-verde/>

1.3.5. Affordance

Practices are connected to specific sets of signals that are unique to different species and even individuals. We differentiate between the physical environment and the semiotic setting, which we refer to as Umwelt (Uexküll and Kriszat, 1934) (for more detail, see chapter 2). On one hand, every living being exists within its specific Umwelt. On the other hand, this Umwelt includes the actions of other living beings that are influenced by their Umwelts. The same objects, events, or actions can be seen as signs across many Umwelts, and the corresponding actions connect the different Umwelts into the larger ecosystem Umwelts (Maran, 2020a), or, we can call it the local eco-verse. Practices are not only related to one Umwelt but to this larger eco-verse. In this eco-verse, many signs may have different meanings due to their physical makeup, but they contribute to establishing the practice as a recurring pattern of interactions among multiple species.

In order to understand the relationship between the environment and Umwelt, it is important to consider the concept of affordance (Chong and Proctor, 2020). Affordance is a property of the physical environment that can only be identified in relation to an action that it enables. This creates a dialectic between inward and outward embodiment. For example, consider a tree: its branches serve various biological functions for the tree's survival, but they also afford actions such as climbing. Although the branches are not designed for climbing, they physically enable this action. However, if too many children climb the tree, the branches may break and the tree could be damaged. Therefore, an important aspect of affordances is that they co-evolve with actions. For instance, berries have evolved as affordances for foraging by birds, and in turn, birds carry the seeds to other places through their droppings.

Affordances are not inherent in physical objects and are instead relative to the actions that can be taken with them. This means that affordances can also be created by the individuals interacting with the objects. For example, an animal might find a new use for a part of a building, such as using a cavity for nesting, even though this was not the original purpose of the structure. Therefore, an important consideration in designing NBS is whether the physical structures can offer benefits to other species

beyond their intended human use, ultimately promoting biodiversity (Weisser and Hauck, 2024).

Box 1.12: Designing affordances for the multi-species city

The way we think about cities and nature is deeply ingrained in our culture, juxtaposing the two spatially. However, in recent years, ecologists have come to realize that urban areas can actually be important hubs for biodiversity (Alberti, 2015; Collins et al., 2021). The common belief that cities are devoid of nature is not just a product of popular opinion and cultural myths, but also influenced by the way cities are represented in planning processes, as depicted in figure 17 (Derby Lewis et al., 2019). Depending on the level of detail provided by different technologies, cities may appear to be uniformly developed built areas, but higher resolution images reveal a diverse network of green spaces that are large enough to serve as habitats for insects.

Figure 17 Two maps of Chicago area, with different satellite mapping technologies and resolutions

A significant challenge to maintaining and improving biodiversity in cities is that people have limited awareness of the environments of small creatures like insects. Insects play a crucial role in connecting green spaces in a city; they support biodiversity by serving as prey for other animals, acting as pollinators, and more. While building birdhouses is a popular and stylish practice, the needs of insects are often overlooked. Additionally, insects can sometimes be a nuisance or even cause human illness. There are numerous ways in which architects and even small everyday objects like balcony decorations can be designed to accommodate insects (Ávila, 2022). By doing so, balconies can play a significant role in enhancing ecological connectivity in a city, even when direct connections between larger green spaces are limited: The balcony becomes a site of affordances for other species.

1.3.6. Finality

Let us consider a last key concept that we have previously introduced: finality and final causation. In modern science, which primarily focuses on efficient causality, final causality is often viewed with suspicion. However, final causality is crucial for a unified approach to meaning and function in an evolutionary context (Deacon, 2013; Short, 2007). Berries did not evolve with the purpose of feeding the birds that help the bush to reproduce. Nevertheless, in an evolutionary context, finality is evident in the emerging directedness of evolutionary change that becomes apparent once the first variants of berries emerged, which then became affordances for birds' actions. This evolving finality culminates in the connected functions of the practices. Finality is a key feature of co-evolution and the generation of meaning.

Beyond these ontological fundamentals, finality is related to affordances in the sense that affordances relate to functions that are realized given certain capabilities of an actor. Finality and function are closely related notions. This observation connects the concept of finality with the capability approach that has become prominent in the context of ecology and justice (Robeyns and Byskov, 2023; Sunstein and Nussbaum, 2006). The capabilities of individuals enable functionings relative to environmental conditions or may be hampered by them. For example, a bird in a cage has the ability to fly but cannot realize this functioning. Accordingly, we can conceptualize flourishing as a state where the capabilities of living beings are fully realized in functioning. Capabilities and affordances stand in a multi-valued relationship, so a set of capabilities can correspond to an open and variable set of functionings.

Therefore, the capability approach renders the notion of the normativity of CEA-NBS operational by tying affordances, capabilities, and functionings together and allowing the identification of vulnerabilities and deficiencies that are of normative relevance (Parker et al., 2022c), along the lines of what has been dubbed "critical anthropomorphism" (Burghardt, 2004). Moreover, identifying capabilities and conditions for functionings that make flourishing possible is the basis for cross-species cognitive empathy. Capabilities are often generic, in the sense that humans can

recognize a capability and imagine its relevance in relation to functioning, as they can compare this with similar sets of capabilities and functionings in the human case. Being caged hampers the realization of mobility for dogs and humans alike, so humans can cognitively empathize with dogs. Consequently, it is possible to transfer human notions of dignity and injustice to other species' lifeworlds.

These observations lead back to a notion of finality that Kant famously claimed for humans only: being a purpose for itself. In CEA-NBS, all living beings embody finality in this sense, which lays the ground for multi-species justice.

1.4. Three methodological pivots

The concepts outlined have implications for the methods detailed in this report. In this section, we present general observations. We have noted that the concept of practice makes it difficult to apply statistical methods based on large numbers. While practice involves random phenomena, these cannot be statistically quantified because the factors generating them co-evolve. There is no fixed categorization of both phenomena and generating environments from the perspective of an independent observer.

Randomness is created by the internal creativity of the interaction between the world and habit (Peirce regarded this as an ontological universal, dubbed by the special term “tychism”, from the Greek for “luck”). Creativity is, by definition, not directly determined by the physical world. An animal may experiment with new ways of accessing human food resources, such as inventing a tool or a new way of moving its body, such as the beak. If this action is successful, a new practice emerges, and the properties of the human-made object containing the food change into affordances. The human-designed world becomes the animal's environment, and humans may need to adapt to this behavioural innovation.

1.4.1. Individualization

The methodological consequence of recognizing randomness as an ontological fundamental is radical individualization of observational practices, both in terms of

habits and creativity. This means that for both humans and non-humans, the species perspective is not a priority, and habits are not primarily defined as species features but as individual features (see also D 2.1.). We do not approach the behaviour, say, of geese in terms of the geese species' behavioural ecology but in terms of the individual animals and their behaviour at a particular point in time and space. This perspective aims to identify the interplay between habit, creativity and emergent finality.

Individualization of observation is a practical challenge for research, since time and staff is limited, even though the research practice is common in behavioural research (for the example of owls, see (Ackerman, 2023)). Therefore, CEA-NBS puts much emphasis on engaging citizens in research in two senses. One is that observations by citizens assume an independent status as observational data from the data collected directly by the scientist. These data can take a form that is different from the format of the latter and mobilize distinct observational capacities of local people; often, they require distinct methods to elicit the information, such as story-telling (box 1.13), which inevitably activates the subjective stance of the individual observer. However, since the focus of CEA-NBS is co-creation of knowledge, this subjectivity can be an important source of information about the interaction between humans and non-humans in the NBS context. The other way is citizen science, which differs from the previous in setting certain standards to train non-experts in certain methods of data collection, such as counting butterflies in the neighbourhood. However, as this example shows, the two approaches converge when individualization is in focus: The citizen observer will inevitably employ subjective judgment in identifying what appears to be novel and creative behaviour in the ecosystem community.

We introduce the distinction between “trained experts” and “local knowers” which reflects the distinction between general knowledge and local knowledge. In sustainability research, the latter is often associated with Indigeneity, or in general the knowledge that is embodied in sense of place. However, the distinction is also relevant in different disciplinary contexts, especially in the economic theory of entrepreneurship. We come back to this important point in section 1.5.1.

Box 1.13: Story-telling and sense of place coevolvers

A method that combines individual perspectives and local knowers' viewpoints is storytelling (see section 2.2). Storytelling comes in various forms today, including digital media, and can be both individual and collective. For example, a group of citizens involved in gardening can tell the story of their projects. Stories can also be in the form of myths passed down through generations by local people. Stories are subjective and capture individual values and emotions. These subjective perspectives are important in understanding the social context of an NBS. Additionally, stories can provide valuable observational data about the environment of the NBS. They also help in understanding the connection between people and nature, whether positive or negative.

One important use of these methods is in studying place lore. In this case, individualization applies to the community level, referring to the uniqueness of the human community and its local ecosystem. The place is described through a collection of diverse stories that can provide ecological information. The stories can also offer other information, such as those gathered from sensory walks. This leads to another application of the mapping method, which can be digitized to make the place lore accessible via locations on a digital map (figure 18).

Figure 18 Mapping place-lore at Tartu Living Lab

1.4.2. Relationality

When trying to understand both humans and non-humans on an equal level, a significant challenge arises because we are unable to directly access the inner thoughts and feelings of non-humans. This has led to some theories dismissing the importance of such inner states in non-humans, such as their ability to feel or be conscious. However, the semiotic approach proposes that we can gain insight into non-humans' inner states by observing their observable behaviours in response to

their surroundings, known as the Umwelt, that is, the set of affordances that tie their actions and the environment together. The Umwelt serves as a link between inner states and the physical world. In a broad sense, we can view this as an application of the fundamental principle of relationality (Barad, 2007; Eyster et al., 2023)

One important implication is that when it comes to epistemic justice we can use the same approach to study human behaviour (see box 1.8). We have already briefly discussed that the practice perspective suggests that methods which directly inquire about inner states through language might be misleading, as people often provide false information about their own states, both intentionally and unintentionally. This means that CEA-NBS primarily relies on data resulting from observation; standardized survey methods, such as environmental values, are of secondary relevance. However, there is a difference between collecting data on subjective opinions and values as a supposed explanatory scheme and considering these data as part of practice. The latter approach is familiar from critical discourse analysis (Gee, 2011): for example, the researcher collects data on how people appreciate nature but does not take these at face value. In critical discourse analysis, the expressed opinions will be further scrutinized in terms of context, the social position of the respondent, or the larger meaning as part of a local conversation about NBS. This means expressed values may be deconstructed to the extent that the respondent herself would learn about her positionality, which was taken for granted in the survey response. Positionality is a form of relationality (Darwin Holmes, 2020).

Moreover, the subjective data on inner states are of secondary importance for CEA-NBS because we aim to understand the interconnected practices of both humans and non-humans. This requires a unified approach to defining and collecting data. We identify shared types of action for humans and non-humans, such as foraging for berries in the forest or using trees for rest. Although the methods may differ, the underlying actions are similar. Therefore, we analyze humans and non-humans by investigating the activity patterns that express their relationships. This approach is especially significant for studying shared vulnerabilities, such as when considering vulnerable groups in urban redevelopment projects that affect green spaces (box 1.14).

Box 1.14: Relationality, health, and ecocompensation

The concept of ecocompensation is often linked to NBS where, for instance, a city redevelopment project that reduces green spaces would be offset by positive ecological actions elsewhere (Hiedanpää et al., 2023b). This compensation could involve simply purchasing carbon offsets. However, such practices overlook the relationality between people and nature at the original location, particularly affecting vulnerable groups like children and the elderly who may not have easy access to alternative green spaces. Interconnectedness refers to acknowledging the close relationship between people and a place, which can be understood in terms of opportunities influenced by meanings, that is, affordances (sense of place) (Raymond et al., 2017b). One crucial aspect of relationality is that the human body is not separate from the natural environment: Human health is directly impacted in various ways by engaging with nature through all sensory channels, even when individuals are not consciously aware of it, especially in relation to biodiversity (Marselle et al., 2021). As a result, NBS research has emphasized the public health aspect of NBS beyond its specific functionality (Kabisch et al., 2017; van den Bosch and Ode Sang, 2017). This aligns with Indigenous perspectives that view humans as connected beings, rather than isolated individuals as often seen in modern economics (Trospen, 2022).

The methodological implication is that ecocompensation schemes should be designed with a limited spatial scope. A crucial factor to consider is the mobility range of vulnerable groups, including both humans and non-humans. For instance, the mobility ranges of certain birds, like sparrows, and young children may be similar, both falling below 50-100 meters (Weisser and Hauck, 2024). These mobility limitations affect the relationships of both children and birds in terms of their environments in a comparable manner, despite the qualitative differences in their environments. For example, if a car park is planned at the cost of a green space, the ecocompensation would not be to create a substitute at another location but to design the car park and its vicinity in a way that important ecosystem services for humans and non-humans can be preserved (Evans and Hardman, 2023).

Figure 19 Ecocompensation, without (top) and with relationality(bottom) (Herrmann-Pillath, 2024)

1.4.3. Holism

It is important to note that focusing on activity patterns does not necessarily mean that activity is the fundamental unit of analysis. Sometimes, what is most important is the absence of certain actions, like when a dog doesn't bark. Understanding the full context of the situation is crucial for interpreting these absences. Therefore, holism is a key methodological principle of CEA-NBS.

This means that the focus is not on the specific material properties of an NBS, such as the intended functions of street trees, but on the interconnected systems that determine the NBS performance. It refers to the ecological and socio-political contexts in the broadest sense. A unifying concept is connectivity (LaPoint et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2019). Whether street trees contribute to city biodiversity depends on their connectivity with other forms of greenery and green infrastructure. Furthermore, whether they are a sustainable part of the infrastructure depends on many factors originating from the socio-political dynamics of the city, such as urban redevelopment planning. Therefore, connectivity in terms of socio-political network structures of power is crucial.

Holism is a critical perspective when considering the expansion and spread of successful NBS. While NBS as an eco-technological solution can be easily replicated, whether the influencing factors can be reproduced elsewhere is uncertain. Even scaling up in the same location may be hindered by various sociopolitical factors that are not directly related to NBS in the narrow sense. This is important when considering NBS as part of a learning community. The concept of Living Lab is crucial in CEA-NBS, as discussed in the next section, but a Living Lab does not encompass the entire learning community. For instance, a Living Lab is linked to networks of scholars who may not be residents of the area. Therefore, the holistic perspective encompasses multiple layers and webs of learning activities in co-creating a continuously evolving NBS (Van Der Jagt et al., 2019).

1.5. Learning as coevolutionary co-creation of knowledge

1.5.1. Living labs

The key conclusion drawn from the previous discussion is that methodology cannot be broken down into a set of individual methods that can be selected like tools to address specific research issues. The principle of holism applies to the selection of methods on a broader level: methods need to be integrated into a comprehensive framework that is not only conceptual but also practical. In the context of NBS, this framework is the Living Lab ((Bulkeley et al., 2016; Hossain et al., 2019; Soini et al., 2023). The principles of individualization and holism apply to Living Labs reflexively: each Living Lab is a unique case where various knowledge production activities interact, with the researcher serving as an instigator and moderator, but not necessarily the primary producer of new knowledge. The Living Lab is a community of collaborators who work together in the experimental co-production of knowledge. Therefore, the Living Lab represents the institutional form of transdisciplinary co-production of knowledge on an equal footing, similar to a laboratory in the sciences or a multidisciplinary research center in the social sciences.

The difference between standard institutional forms of knowledge production and the Living Lab (LL) is that the former create institutional boundaries between the expert domain and the “non-expert” domain. While experts can work across disciplines by "going to the field," in a genuine LL, the experts become part of the local community, serving as moderators and providers of services, and they interact with what we have now dubbed the local knowers. Knowledge production in a LL is a collective process, with researchers acting as "secretaries" who record the process and participate in reflecting on the resulting documents. This approach is similar to the contemporary ethnographic approach, especially when the ethnographer also acts as an activist concerned with the long-term well-being of the community (Chao, 2022; Povinelli, 2016).

The concept of LL has mostly been used to integrate different human perspectives and ways of knowing to collectively produce knowledge. This approach highlights that methodology is also an ethical issue, related to the normative sciences. The co-

production of knowledge requires equal recognition of different ways of knowing and learning, especially when evaluating outcomes. If new knowledge were only assessed by experts, it could result in epistemic dominance or even violence. However, classical pragmatism suggests that truth is determined by practical application. Ultimately, the people who use new knowledge in LL are the ones who truly matter.

At this point, it is important to emphasize that the duality of expert knowledge and local knowledge extends beyond the current context of sustainability science. When we consider NBS)as co-evolutionary technologies, we must also acknowledge that these solutions increasingly involve private sector actors and businesses. In this context, NBS become entrepreneurial projects (Gültekin, 2024). This aligns with the idea of the Living Lab as an arena for social innovation, where there is a broad spectrum of entrepreneurial opportunities ranging from traditional profit-oriented ventures to those that are socially engaged. We come back on this point in chapter 5.

In entrepreneurship theory, the distinction between general knowledge and local knowledge—specific to time and place—is crucial (the classic is Hayek, 1945; Kiessling 2015). The key aspect of entrepreneurship is the ability to combine general knowledge with local knowledge, which is particularly vital for identifying entrepreneurial opportunities. Consequently, the concept of "local knowers" includes a diverse group of individuals, and the connection to private sector entrepreneurship is becoming increasingly important for ensuring that NBS are sustainable not only environmentally but also economically.

In summary, epistemic justice is a fundamental methodological principle in the LL, meaning to treat all sources of knowledge and their holders as havin equal rights to voice and recognition. In CEA-NBS, this principle is expanded to include the non-human domain, in line with the principles of co-evolutionary epistemology. This means that all members of the ecosystem in which the LL is established are considered part of the community that produces knowledge. This highlights the importance of ensuring epistemic justice. The institutional mechanism through which epistemic justice is achieved is the multi-species democracy (Meijer, 2019).

1.5.2. Multi-species democracy

Classical pragmatism suggests that democracy is a way for communities to generate knowledge through experimentation (Festenstein, 2023). This knowledge production process is similar to the general case: Communities have shared practices, encounter problems with these practices, and then work together to find new solutions. It is important for everyone to participate in this discovery process for two main reasons: First, equal participation ensures a wide range of new ideas, and second, it ensures a fair assessment of the results. In this broad sense, local democracies must be communities where everyone has a voice. We explore this in more detail in chapter 4. However, there is a challenge here, as deliberation in experimental democracy mostly happens through language. Even within language, there are unequal symbolic power and cultural capital: The voices of the educated may carry more weight than those of individuals who lack certain cognitive and rhetorical abilities for various reasons. For example, children are often excluded from deliberative discussions. This exclusion is even more pronounced for non-human beings who lack the ability to communicate in human language. Hence, a key principle in developing research methodologies in LLs is based on the broader discussion in the multi-species democracy debate, emphasizing the need to find ways to communicate and discuss knowledge without depending solely on human language. This is both challenging and straightforward. It is straightforward because language plays a reduced role in the fundamental concept of practice. However, it is challenging because we currently lack practical methods for translating non-linguistic forms of knowledge into human language, which is crucial in the socio-political context of LL, especially when converting insights into public policies.

If we begin by considering language as such, we can solve these problems when considering that language includes both processes of speaking and listening. Listening and understanding are as essential as speaking and intending a meaning in a discourse. As we have already argued, we can approach the utterance as an action, and hence language as another form of practice. From this follows that we can also approach other actions as a form of communication that involves listening and feed

back circuits between the sender and the receiver of a meaningful action. Indeed, human language is also embedded in meaningful actions such as body movements and facial expressions, and often the primordial form of communication is gesturing: I may express dissatisfaction with my face, and only turn to language when the other cannot immediately understand this expression.

The shift from language to action is also significant in the theory of democracy. Democracy is mainly seen as an institutional form of collective decision-making, such as voting, following a deliberative discourse (Christiano and Bajaj, 2024). This view sidelines the role of other actions, such as demonstrations or general strikes. Indeed, there is a view that formal democracy even silences the genuine democratic process, which is mainly via action, not speech (Rancière, 2004). Accordingly, we can develop principles of multi-species democracy by focusing on action as a key medium. This is grounded in ethical principles of equal recognition. Further details will be developed in section 4. Reconstructing a Living Lab as a multi-species community is a radical ecosocial transformation that cannot be easily achieved (box 1.15).

Box 1.15: Sheepville, Act I

Sheep can be involved in wildfire protection, as a classical Nature-Based Solution (NBS). This often involves an agreement between herders and municipalities, where the municipality pays herders to maintain and care for the flocks. In these arrangements, the sheep are not recognized as members of the local community, even though herders, dogs, and sheep may interact on a limited scale. The sheep are considered as "workers", similar to the case of beavers in box 1.6. Citizens may only see the sheep as having a function, or may not be aware of their role and see them as a nuisance (for example, noise from bells, barking dogs, etc.). Alternatively, the neighbourhood where the sheep roam at the edges between the settlement and the forest may choose to recognize the sheep as members of the community (Donaldson and Kymlicka, 2013, p. 135ff). This would mean that the community directly takes responsibility for the sheep along with the herders, who may assume the role of political representatives (eco-stewards). One implication of this is recognizing the civil rights of sheep, such as freedom of movement, and limiting other forms of commercial exploitation of sheep. For example, the sheep would not be slaughtered for meat production, and the wool may only be sold for the benefit of the sheep as their own. Obviously, establishing Sheepville would be a major cultural transformation that requires a thorough change of habits. One way to do this could be the creative invention of secular rituals related to sheep. We will revisit Sheepville in chapter 4, referring to a COEVOLVERS Living Lab (box 4.11).

Chapter 2: Semiotics, aesthetics, and method

2.0. Chapter summary

1. CEA-NBS adopts an integrative approach to ecosemiotics and ecolinguistics. Ecolinguistics in the narrow sense explores the symbolic intermediation of human Umwelts; ecosemiotics embeds this in the larger multi-species Umwelts. This research maps the eco-verse of an NBS as part of a local community in which the NBS is placed.
2. In terms of NBS as infrastructure, eco semiotics explores the sensory governance of nature-culture assemblages in relation to human and more-than-human practices. This results in the aesthetic approach to NBS co-design as artwork.
3. Ecosystems manifest a rich semiotic surplus which allows for co-cultural creativity in the formation of new habits.
4. The integrative approach of CEA-NBS grounds in the semiotic analysis of signs. Meaning is interpretive action mediated by signs of the object to which the action is directed. The totality of signs constitutes the Umwelt of the organism that is the origin of action. Hence, observers can access the Umwelt by interpreting the actions and relating them to signs as affordances.
5. Ecosemiotic analysis explores the duality of function and meaning, which is reflected in the distinction between physical and cultural ecosystem services. Accordingly, NBS design integrates engineering and artful methods of multi-species co-creation.
6. Ecosemiotics defines "objectivity" as impartiality in recognizing the diversity of Umwelts – epistemic justice. There is no external scientific "view from nowhere".
7. Ecosemiotic modelling creates a conceptual map of a local eco-community centered on a focal notion (for example, seeing a city as a "garden") and recognizing umwelts' diversity.
8. Ecographic methods capture the diversity of Umwelts, such as ecofield analysis or ecological repertoire analysis. These are guided by the principle of individualization.
9. A key ecographic method is multi-species story-telling that focuses on actions and events. Multi-species story-telling uses digital media to integrate multi-sensory experiences and fosters perspective-taking in a diversity of umwelts.
10. Ecolinguistics explores stakeholder narratives in NBS communities and how they impact on the sociopolitics.
11. A focus on co-cultural creativity explores the formation of new habits via activating semiotic surplus and semiotic co-option in artful design of NBS.

2.1. Signs as the keys to exploring multi-species worlds of doing NBS

In this section, we will delve deeper into the semiotic basics of CEA-NBS. This is important for establishing criteria to identify the most effective research methods for

highlighting the coevolutionary dynamics and the interaction between humans and other species in creating and sustaining a NBS. A key focus is on understanding how semiotic processes, also known as semiosis, mediate and create shared sensory experiences and webs of actions across multiple species. To achieve this, we require ecosemiotic methods, which encompass the field of ecolinguistics in a broader sense. Ecolinguistics, in turn, is also interpreted in a wider sense, following leading researchers in the field (Steffensen and Fill, 2014), namely approaching language as a central aspect of constructing human *Umwelts* (Tønnessen, 2015). This dovetails with the Wittgensteinian view of language as mediating life worlds (Wittgenstein, 2009) and seeing language as a form of action in pragmatism (Mead, 2015).

We define the approaches in the following way.

Semiotics is the most general conceptual framework which explores all kinds of signs and signifying relationships in the world which are relevant to generating processes of world-making (Hoffmeyer, 1996). Signs are material entities that mediate between two other entities in an interpretive relationship. Hence, the field divides into many subfields, reaching from literature (Lotman, 2001) to even physical processes (Herrmann-Pillath and Salthe, 2011). For example, in biosemiotics the genetic code is analyzed as semiosis (El-Hani et al., 2006). There is a close relationship to the concept of information processing in all kinds of natural and social structures, however, semiotics differs from the mainstream Shannon line of quantitative information processing in emphasizing semantic information, that is meaning and meaning making (Herrmann-Pillath, 2021a).

Ecosemiotics studies the role of signs and semiosis in the making of ecosystems (Kull and Nöth, 2000). This includes the generation and processing of signs by all kinds of living beings who constitute the ecosystem, treating humans and non-humans on par, and focusing on the meaning-generating powers of patterns in ecosystems, such as dynamic assemblages of humans, trees and animals in a forest (Kohn, 2013). *Ecosemiotics* includes the study of human semiosis in relating to nature (Wheeler, 2006).

Ecolinguistics is conventionally not included systematically in the semiotics canon, however, there is no principled incompatibility. The difference is mainly defined by the

focus on human language as a specific sign system and the relevant analytical methods of linguistics (Stibbe, 2021). In this report, we combine the two strands of research, ecosemiotics and ecolinguistics into one conceptual framework that arranges various methods that bridge them, such as the analysis of stories. This approach matches with the position held by many semioticians that linguistics is a specialization of general semiotics (which, however, is controversial, though systematically justified) (Chandler, 2022, p, 2ff).

2.1.1. Performativity of researchers' idioms and more-than-human ecolinguistics

Through the integration of ecolinguistics and ecosemiotics, we can adapt methods initially designed for humans to be relevant to non-human species. While the final outcomes are communicated in human language, we can first change our perspective within this framework. For example, we can tell a story from the perspective of an animal, reflecting specific field observations. This turns a non-fictional report into an artistic portrayal of the other species life world (Despret, 2021) Furthermore, we can expand the idea of a "story" to include various forms of media, creating a dynamic multimedia collage that stimulates multi-sensory experiences beyond language. For instance, in digital storytelling, we can include audio clips to evoke soundscapes (Flicker and MacEntee, 2020). By these methods, we enable humans to imagine the *Umwelts* of other species, as shown in box 1.10.

In our efforts, the term "ecology" will be used in different ways, such as in ecolinguistics, where the term is not only used for the ecology of nature, but also in the sense that language constitutes distinct ecologies of meaning, hence *Umwelts* as defined by ecosemiotics. One important aspect linking this section with the sociopolitics section is that the success of an NBS in terms of achieving certain ecological outcomes is influenced by the interaction between various linguistic expressions and uses by different human groups, such as narratives, texts, or public discourses. We can connect the NBS to different sociolects, such as children's language, the technical language of urban planners, or the language used in business communities. These differences play a multifaceted analytical role, as they can be

utilized, for instance, as a research tool in citizen science approaches or as a means of implementing the NBS in community workshops. Therefore, we can talk about the language ecology of the NBS, which is defined by the social languages and even individual languages of different stakeholders and their interactions. Most importantly, this makes the CEA-NBS reflexive, indicating its status as a normative science: The language used by researchers is part of the language ecology of the NBS (Box 2.1). This means that the way researchers speak and write can directly influence the perceptions and behavior of other participants in an NBS community, and thus have performative effects, both positive and negative.

Box 2.1: Is a Living Lab a “Living Lab”? coevolvers

It can be problematic to refer to initiatives involving local communities as "Living Labs," as the term is commonly used in the context of experimental innovation that involves local users in co-creating new ideas. While this is generally accepted in the realm of technological innovation, it can pose challenges in social innovation processes. When researchers propose experimental changes to local customs, some community members may feel like they are being treated as subjects in a project initiated and designed by the researchers. The term "lab" can imply that people are being treated like lab animals. The metaphorical interpretation can imply criticism of current practices and may lead to unintended consequences, apparently also staying in tension with the claims of transdisciplinarity. The use of language that differs from interactions with donor organizations ("LL talk") and the local community (avoiding LL talk) raises ethical concerns about providing adequate information to local partners and can lead to a loss of trust when discrepancies are recognized by non-expert LL members. Similar issues arise with other key concepts used by researchers, such as the term "vulnerabilities." Identifying a vulnerable group within a Living Lab design can lead to various responses, including objections from the target group or bias from other groups.

The term "ecolinguistics" is used to explore how language shapes our relationship with nature, including how it influences our perception of different elements of the natural world. For instance, the term "weed" carries a negative connotation, which can hinder a positive view of these elements in the local ecosystem (Irons, 2024). Ecolinguistics involves methods such as critical discourse analysis, which help to reveal these interconnections (Gee, 2011). However, many of these methods do not fully encompass the broader scope of ecolinguistics, as they tend to separate language from the values and beliefs embedded within it. This is particularly evident when

examining the concept of value, where there is often an assumption that values exist independently of their linguistic expression. In a broader sense, ecolinguistics views human values as emerging from language-mediated action, or in other words, language as a form of action. Transdisciplinarity plays a role in mitigating the negative impacts of scientific language, which "objectifies" the natural world and thereby fails to recognize the autonomous status and dignity of other beings. For example, scientific language often describes natural phenomena in terms of patterns and trends, which can diminish the agency of non-human entities, particularly on an individual level. An example of this is how researchers, through the use of animal tagging technology, have come to recognize the individuality of roaming behaviour over distances previously unknown to scientists, but observed by non-experts in a casual manner (for example, in the case of owls, Ackerman, 2023).

Ecolinguistics, in the more general sense of a naturalistic approach to language, even rejects treating language as an independent domain of research. Instead, language is an aspect of practice, so language, action, and sensory experiences are not analytically separate. Simply said, language is deeply embodied (Lakoff, 2018). This embodied view grounds the integration of ecosemiotics and ecolinguistics and leads to expanding eco-linguistics into the more-than-human dimension. At first sight, this seems like the standard research on the question of whether animals have a "language". However, in the past, much of this research took human language as the benchmark and simply looked for traces and similarities in other species (Pepperberg, 2017). In integrating ecosemiotics and ecolinguistics, we reverse this analytical stance and treat human language as one semiotic system of many (Chandler, 2022). This follows from the embodied approach to language: Language engages distributed signs in arranging actions and sensory experiences in a species-specific way, as "life worlds" (Box 2.2).

Box 2.2: Place-shaping and world-making in language

The research on NBS involves reinventing language. For example, the concept of "place" is different from the physical space marked on a map where the NBS is situated. This distinction, as discussed in influential works like Tuan (Tuan, 2011), allows researchers to delve into how humans connect with specific geographical locations. This can be observed

in narratives and various forms of linguistic expressions that evoke memory and recollection, emphasizing cognitive processes of understanding. Recent research has focused on the embodied aspects, viewing place as a multi-sensory and multi-dimensional phenomenon (Raymond et al., 2017b). This perspective aligns closely with Indigenous views on the connection between people and land, often characterized as embodied relationality (Trosper, 2022). In this context, legal language is crucial in approaching land as an alienable property and disembodying relationships (Lieber and Rynkiewich, 2007). Considering the diversity of human languages, Indigenous languages have grammatical features that differentiate between the ontological conceptualization of possessive relations. A significant aspect is alienability (Aikhenvald, 2012). Many non-Western languages use distinct possessive grammatical structures for alienable objects, such as body parts compared to secreted body fluids. Non-alienable grammatical structures are used for certain external objects, often including land. This linguistic distinction reflects a way of shaping the world, as it means that the concept of treating land as alienable cannot even be expressed in words. NBS located in countries with diverse languages can benefit from this linguistic diversity, for example, in naming the location of the NBS (Bush et al., 2023; Country et al., 2016). Diverse linguistic environments can cultivate alternative perspectives on the embodied relationships between humans and the ecosystem to which the NBS belongs.

In summary, ecosemiotics and ecolinguistics view NBS not only as engineering projects based on various natural sciences but also as semiotic assemblages that contribute to shaping the world. This perspective raises the question of how signs and language can be used as elements and tools in designing NBS. This applies to both the physical structures, such as the arrangement of trees in urban green spaces, and the principles that govern NBS.

2.2.2. Semiotic surplus and artful design of NBS as natureculture

As discussed in D 2.1, a NBS can be analyzed in two dimensions: infrastructure and landscape in niche construction. These dimensions can also be referred to as the functional and semiotic assemblage modes. For example, an urban watershed that combines both traditional (grey) and natural (green) elements can be described in terms of its physical functions in managing water flows and supporting biodiversity, such as food webs. Additionally, it can be viewed from different perspectives, such as those of humans or birds, and hence conceived as an assemblage of signs which are only meaningful in relation to the diversity of living beings.

The functional perspective takes the viewpoint of an external scientific observer, while the Umwelt perspective is not only species-specific but even specific to individual organisms. This plurality of Umwelts creates a "semiotic surplus" beyond the deterministic structure of functions (Maran, 2021a). In terms of functions, we can imagine alternative potential functions. The Umwelt perspective emphasizes that various patterns in the world, like the movements of a fly or the swirling currents in a river, can become signs or semiotically mediated affordances for action. These actions involve creative interpretation of the signs and are often uniquely individual. The semiotic surplus is evident in the multiplicity of Umwelts and can be further enhanced through mutually "translating" Umwelts (Lotman, 2009) This duality of meaning and function contributes to the finality in the co-evolving NBS. This most general abstract duality is manifest in the duality of infrastructure and landscape.

As elaborated in D 2.1, the notion of infrastructure refers to the concept of ecosystem services that are activated by the NBS. The functional dimension is ultimately grounded in the ecosystem in which the NBS is embedded. For example, a healing garden as NBS is embedded in the larger ecosystem defined by neighbouring areas, for example, a forest, epitomized by the wider ranges of birds and pollinator mobility beyond the garden. Considering these embedding structures is the key to understanding how the NBS affects biodiversity and reflects the general principle of holism. Any kind of physical infrastructure can be approached from this perspective, unless it is completely insulated and artificial without any other living beings. For example, a large photovoltaic farm can be seen as functional infrastructure without any mobilization of ecosystem services, or we recognize the manifolds of plants, insects and other animals exploiting the specific conditions created by it and attracting immigration into that area (Uldrijan et al., 2022). This view raises the question of how far the artificial instalment can contribute to biodiversity, which might invite specific design modification. Hence, different from the functional perspective on the solar park, new ecological functions can emerge via the creativity of other species relating to the park in terms of their Umwelts. This applies both for operating infrastructure and for defunct ruins (Jasper, 2020).

This perspective becomes important when considering NBS in terms of the landscape, which is often a topic of public debate in cases such as solar farms, which are sometimes seen as disrupting the "natural" landscape as perceived and experienced by humans. In our approach, the landscape is defined by the multiple ways of experiencing and interacting with it at the NBS site: There are as many different landscapes as there are observers: The solar farm can become "nature" via its affordances for non-human species. It is important to note that these experiences and interactions cannot be solely reduced to functionality; they also have a semiotic meaning beyond their functions (Kohn, 2013). Recognizing this meaning distinguishes the biosemiotics view from the traditional evolutionary approach, which mainly focuses on adaptation and genetically determined behaviors at the species level (see D 2.1). Real-world ecosystems exhibit a complex and rich pattern of potential and unpredictable interactions, so individual living beings must learn about specific conditions and develop appropriate responses that are within the scope of species-level capabilities, yet are novel behavioural expressions of these. These individual responses are creative adaptations to the unique experiences of the living being and they result in practical outcomes over time. This perspective reflects the principle of individualization. As a consequence, infrastructure, as built by humans, becomes landscape as reflected in the Umwelts of diverse species, humans and non-humans, and thus is being transformed into nature: "Nature" appropriates human-built artefacts which thereby become part of it, or "naturecultures" (Malone and Ovenden, 2016). The upshot of this discussion is that the planning of NBS as infrastructure radically eschews the conventional stance of rendering the infrastructure invisible (see D 2.1) (Star, 1999). In this view, there is a neat differentiation between the visible service the infrastructure provides (such as the clean water) and the provisioning devices (such as a sewage plant). This arrangement also reflects the social differentiation between the users of the service and the expert producers. In an NBS, these relationships must be radically overturned to mobilize co-evolutionary and co-creative processes. Even if we only focus on the human beneficiary, the "users" of an ecosystem service must be aware of the generating assemblages to get involved with its co-creation. Further,

many NBS presuppose citizen participation in sustaining and upscaling the NBS, and finally, the NBS is also expected to change habits and cultural stances towards nature. That means, the design of an NBS as infrastructure is ecosemiotic design making the assemblages visible, which means, more generally, “actionable” in the sense that affordances are co-created that invite and sustain certain patterns of action, that is, practices, that contribute to the shared flourishing of the local multi-species community. In chapter 4 we discuss one important consequence of this approach, namely conceptualizing governance of NBS as “nature based governance”.

In practice, this leads to approaching the design of an NBS as aesthetic act: Making the NBS visible takes the form of artwork (Conte et al., 2024; Herrmann-Pillath et al., 2023). Artwork leverages and creates semiotic surplus. This can be primarily understood as addressing humans, in many senses, such as overcoming aesthetic barriers to NBS acceptance or leveraging awareness of nature and motivating psychological transformations (Lydon 2024) (Box 2.3). In our approach, this creation of semiotic surplus also addresses other species. We will further explore whether this mainly means creating affordances for functional innovations, or also involves non-functional non-human aesthetics (Prum, 2017).

Box 2.3: The science and art of NBS

In urban infrastructure, there is a growing trend towards replacing traditional grey water management systems with green infrastructure. Typically, traditional drainage systems are hidden from view, but NBS for drainage directly alter the urban landscape (Levy Yeyati, 2019). For example, transforming impervious surfaces like parking lots by using permeable materials that allow rainwater to infiltrate the ground, and incorporating underground pipes to collect the water for rewilded areas like ponds, can attract local plant and animal life. There are various design options, from carefully tended green spaces to more natural rewilded areas. The “gardening” option emphasizes the artistic and aesthetic aspects of the design, involving ecologists and artists to create visually appealing and community-engaging NBS. In these NBS, the drainage function is not only visible but also serves as a form of sensory governance, influencing habits beyond its specific purpose.

Fig. 4. Rain Yard
 a. Rain Yard overall
 b. Diagram of 'bunk bed' concept for people utilizing the surface, and rain and plants inhabiting the soil underneath
 c. Using the rain pump.

Figure 20 Aesthetic design of a rainyard (Levy Yeyati 2019)

2.2.3. Co-cultures, co-creation and more-than-human feelings

We can think of an ecosystem in two ways: as a set of connected functional relationships, such as predator-prey interactions, or as a collection of individual Umwelts that communicate with each other, like when predators and prey signal to each other. First, we should recognize the diversity of Umwelts, and then consider how these diverse environments come together to form a local “ecosemiosphere” (Maran, 2021b) (the term “semiosphere” has been coined by Lotman to refer to the world of signs). We see these two perspectives – functional and Umwelt perspective – as integrated. This means that Umwelts are influenced by and limited by the ecological web, while at the same time, animal Umwelts, through selective perception and action, regulate the ecological webs in every interaction. In this broader view, the observable ecological functions are created by all species and individuals living together, and they originate in a shared semiosis of habit evolution that cannot be reduced to genetic evolution. As we can see, the previous argument about naturalizing language is expanded to include a non-anthropocentric idea of culture (Hünefeldt, 2022).

This points to the idea of phenotypic flexibility in relation to genetic endowments, which is often emphasized in reference to humans. The emerging picture shows that the creativity of Umwelts and related behaviours allows for significant flexibility in interactions between humans and other species, facilitated by the various potentials

of semiotic surplus in the ecosystem, of which both humans and other species are members. In CEA-NBS, a key concept is co-culture or interspecies culture (Parker et al., 2022c; Sueur and Huffman, 2024), referring to the emergence of new patterns in cross-species interactions sustained by the semiotic structures embodied in the material assemblage of the NBS and its embedding ecosystem. These structures, known as affordances, mediate function and meaning.

Affordances that embody co-cultures are seen in actions and emerging habits shared across species. A prime example is the relationship between dogs and humans. Domestication is no longer viewed as a result of one-way breeding by humans, but rather as a result of reciprocal processes and mutual adaptation of habits (Gibson, 2021). This led to genetic evolution in domesticated dogs, while also creating co-cultures that are not genetically fixed. The surplus of co-cultures invokes the analytical dimension of aesthetics, which is the valuation of sensory flows in actions beyond their immediate function. This perspective suggests that the design of NBS should not only be based on engineering criteria of function, but also on aesthetic criteria. NBS design can be considered as an artwork. In CEA-NBS, art is seen as an aspect of action that applies universally across species, rather than just a human cultural achievement (Prum, 2013). We differentiate between functional design and semiotic design, which come together in the emergence of functionally sustainable habits. Over the long term of co-evolution, such habits may also become genetically endowed and may drive local dynamics of speciation (a semiotic version of the Baldwin effect).

Our approach is based on the semiotics of cultural creativity as explained by Lotman (Lotman, 2009). Juri Lotman emphasized the non-identity and difference between participants as an essential aspect of communication, which serves as a source of cultural dynamics and creativity. Recognizing the diversity of Umwelts is a significant driver of human cultural creativity and can be utilized in designing NBS as artwork. These observations help us refine the concept of biodiversity and the notion of loss of biodiversity (Maran, 2023). Biodiversity is commonly measured in terms of species diversity from the perspective of an external scientific observer, and loss is defined in relation to past biodiversity. We can also view biodiversity as the diversity of Umwelts and approach loss as the destruction of semiotic diversity and potential, hence as

ecosemiotic diversity. This prompts an intriguing shift in thinking about biodiversity: Is it possible to increase ecosemiotic diversity without directly introducing manifest biodiversity?

These ideas ground the approach to co-cultural creativity in abstract terms. In order to apply this general view in research methods, we need to make two methodological adjustments:

1. When studying humans, we must reduce the emphasis on cognitive and linguistic biases in understanding human behavior in the NBS context. This implies adopting a multi-sensory approach that aligns with aesthetics in NBS design.
2. When studying other species, we must acknowledge their creative agency and the semiotic surplus of individualized environments.

These two perspectives come together in unified methodologies, which we will delve into in this contribution. At this stage, we emphasize a key idea that allows us to take the first step – developing the concepts and practices of sharing feelings across species. Co-cultures are based on mutual understanding and empathy for feelings, which we will further explore in chapter 3. In the process of NBS, this relational aspect can be activated through co-creative mapping, as one method among others (Box 2.4). We have already encountered mapping in different contexts (Boxes 1.3, 1.8, 1.13). Now, we will examine in detail a practical exercise which is itself a form of artwork, while inviting humans to step into the shoes, or rather paws, hooves, fins, and more, of other species.

Box 2.4: Mapping feelings to ground co-culture

Among the various methods of co-creation in Living Lab practices, the exercise of mapping feelings can initiate the co-creation of co-cultures on the human side. The main idea is that the human participants project their own feelings onto a non-human entity in the NBS and the embedding ecosystem. This works in the following way:

1. The facilitator or an artist prepares a poster/flipchart drawing the landscape in which the NBS project takes place. This can also be abstract and should depict as diverse elements as possible (different natural features such as streams, forests, animals (attacking/sleeping/playing), wind, rainbow, flowers, stones, etc.) and non-natural features (bridge, houses, rubbish, fence with gate, bench, playground, etc.).
2. The poster is placed on a magnetic board. The facilitator asks the participants to choose a magnet and position it on the poster where they see themselves with their emotional state at the current stage of NBS development and in their respective roles. Examples:

River: "I feel like I'm about to go down," or "I'm drifting." Flowers: "I am happy how my ideas are flourishing." Fence: "I feel left out."

3. The facilitator asks the participants to share the reason for their positioning with the group. No one is forced to do this.

4. If negative feelings are mentioned, it is essential to follow this up.

5. The magnet can always be moved at the end of a project day or at regular intervals to check the new feelings/needs of the participants.

This exercise pursues various aims. The first is to enhance cooperation in the group of humans engaged with the NBS. This happens on a non-cognitive basis by projecting feelings onto objects that are not the individual. This means the feelings are actively embodied, and the human considers the potential of the non-human in sharing the feelings with the human. In doing so, the sharing of feelings within the human group is mediated via the non-humans. This opens the possibility of co-creating co-cultures. The latter becomes especially strong if the sessions are repeated throughout the project (see point 5).

2.2. Semiotic fundamentals: Semiosis, semiotic causation, semiotic creativity

In this section, we will explore the fundamentals of semiotic analysis based on the ideas of Charles S. Peirce. However, we will avoid using his specific terminology, as it might be overwhelming for readers and not necessarily provide additional insights in the context of NBS (Burch, 2024). We also point out that semiotics is a rich field with various traditions that do not always concur with the Peircean line (Chandler, 2022). A full exposition would explode the limitations of this report.

Our focus is primarily conceptual, and we will begin by introducing basic theoretical concepts, which might be challenging for readers unfamiliar with semiotics. To illustrate our arguments, we will use the example of the Powerful Owl (*Ninox strenua*) in Australia, which has been studied in a thought-provoking discussion of interspecies art by an Australian research team ((Parker et al., 2022a); <https://pursuit.unimelb.edu.au/articles/new-design-tech-offers-hope-for-urban-wildlife>). For a detailed description of this case, see box 1.7. While this example may not directly relate to NBS, it can be considered highly instructive in understanding the general principles of building multi-species communities using ecosemiotic methods. Additionally, we can also view owls, similar to the famous case of New York falcons in the early 20th century, as a form of NBS for controlling urban rodents, especially in the Global South (Barua, 2020). As mentioned earlier, owls that migrate to cities

creatively redefine the city as part of their natural environment. By appropriating urban spaces, these spaces become "natural" as they are no longer exclusively defined in relation to human needs, desires, and preferences.

2.2.1. The sign and evolutionary semiosis

We base our reasoning on figure 21, which is inspired by Robinson and Southgate (2010) and builds on the work of Herrmann-Pillath and Salthe (2011). It is important to note that this diagram only represents a conceptual structure and at most, the basic structure of the core element of semiotic analysis, the sign (understood as the elementary unit of semantic information, Herrmann-Pillath, 2021). As we will explain, semiosis is a process, particularly in the evolutionary sense, involving sequences of emergent signs that change over time (Nöth, 2012). The outcomes of semiosis themselves are signs of various qualities and types (we ignore the semantic ambiguity here to avoid jargon, namely that strictly speaking, the sign is the triad, and the sign as indicated in the diagram the "sign vehicle" or "representamen", see Chandler 2022, p. 30ff). According to Peirce's original thinking, semiosis is a process of habit generation in a world initially shaped by randomness. In our study of bird behaviour, owls and humans engage in multidimensional interactive semiosis. Humans interpret owls in certain ways, influenced by myths and past experiences. Owls, on the other hand, explore unfamiliar urban environments, interpreting them based on their past experiences. Both parties face the challenge of forming new habits of cohabitation.

Figure 21 Basic structure of semiosis

Figure 21 provides an overview of the key conceptual elements of semiosis. In this context, we differentiate between objects (O), signs (S), and interpretants (I). Interpretants are actions of organisms and are embedded in interpreters or "agents." For example, when a human sees pellets below a street tree, looks up, discovers an owl, and chases the owl away, this action signifies that the owl is scary, dangerous, and unwanted: Notice that it is not the owl that has these properties *ab ovo*. The owl may respond with calls indicating defensive aggression. Evolutionary semiosis is initiated when a child observes these actions, which are signs in turn, and may later draw an image of a scary owl. It is essential for the ecosemiotic method to recognize that intentionality is not a necessary condition for meaning as action. However, this understanding does not reduce to crude behaviourism, as the action can only be understood as being mediated by the sign. The sign is defined as properties of the owl that incite the action as interpretant: We notice that this relationship directly corresponds to the notion of affordance as introduced in the first chapter. Objects, such as the pellets, stand in a mechanistic causal relationship (M) with organisms (inner triangle) (if only via the physical mechanisms of perception). At the same time, the object relates semiotically with the interpreter in eliciting the action (the

pellet is also sign for the interpretant). Whereas mechanistic causation is unidirectional (efficient causal sequences of cause and effect), semiotic causality is bidirectional, meaning that the object is represented by the sign, but also the sign is interpretively assigned to the object: A pellet is not only the physical object but also what is perceived by the human. In a very similar manner, Jakob von Uexküll (Uexküll, 2012) describes in his '*functional cycle*' the connection between an organism and environmental object as taking place through two complementary arches – perception and action – while both being mediated by signs.

The relationship between an object and its representation through a sign can take different forms. This can include direct causation (referred to as "index" in Peircean terminology), metaphorical representation ("icon"), or arbitrary symbolism ("symbol"). The interaction between a human and an owl is semiotically complex. For humans, an owl's pellet is an index pointing to the owl, as it is directly caused by the owl's metabolic processes. However, the pellet also has iconic qualities, representing various disgusting things for humans due to its similarities with them. Simultaneously, the owl, as perceived by humans, is a sign of its living being, such as its plumage colors and distinctive features like its eyes. As an icon, the owl brings to mind various images of owls in humans, including symbolic meanings such as wisdom or forewarning of misfortune. Different from the icon, the symbol is arbitrary in the sense that, for example, "wisdom" does not relate to any perceptual features of the owl. Consequently, owls have many different and sometimes conflicting symbolic meanings across human cultures (Ackerman, 2023). The iconic qualities of the pellet and owl can combine, resulting in humans associating owls with negative feelings in specific contexts, which can influence their symbolic meanings. Looking at this evolutionary semiosis from a co-evolutionary theory perspective, the original function of the pellet as an index is not only related to the owl, but is likely also related to a genetically ingrained human instinct that triggers a feeling of danger when encountering disgusting things.

The process of semiosis demonstrates purposeful behaviour, whether through evolutionary selection processes or the intentional actions of interpreters (Short, 2007). Evolutionary processes occur in various ways, including genetic, economic,

and sociocultural modes (Jablonka et al., 2014). Humans may instinctively respond to certain stimuli, such as pellets, to avoid infections without directly connecting them to owls. The symbolic significance of owls evolves through cultural myths and may be influenced by intentional actions, such as conservation efforts aimed at changing public perception of owls. Overall, evolutionary semiosis is co-evolutionary, as no single agent determines its direction due to the purposeful steps in the semiotic process (box 2.5).

Box 2.5. Co-evolutionary multi-species semiosis

The co-evolutionary relationship between flowers and their pollinators is an instructive case for evolutionary semiosis when considering the colors and shapes of flowers. There is no direct connection between these visual cues and the process of pollination, unlike the physical shape of a flower and how it is accessed by pollinators. One hypothesis suggests that the visual cues of flowers evolved in response to a random mutation in the vision of insects, which occurred long before flowers themselves emerged in evolution (Yong, 2022, p. 114f). As a result, flowers adapted their visual cues to match the visual capacities of these insects. This means that the way the interpreter, in this case the insect, perceives the flowers ultimately influenced the evolution of the flowers themselves. This dual process, involving both mechanistic and semiotic causation, drove the co-evolution of the interpreter and the objects being interpreted. The original mutation is considered a type of exaptation that cannot be solely explained by natural selection (Gould, 2002, p. 1270ff). This concept also applies to human interaction with flowers, as humans appreciate flowers aesthetically, thereby influencing their evolution in various ways (Raguso, 2021). This influence can be negative, for instance when certain plant properties are attractive to humans but lead to actions that are harmful to plant reproduction. An example of this is how Agave growers prevent the plants from blossoming in order to prolong the lifetime of the plant for extracting raw materials for Tequila production.

An interesting perspective suggests that the domestication of animals and plants can be viewed as the reverse domestication of humans by those species. This means that plants, for example, rely on human labor to reproduce, indicating a mutual relationship where plants adapt to human needs and humans become essential for the reproduction of plants. While these ideas are debated (Abbo and Gopher, 2020; Purugganan, 2022), they reveal a concept that may also be relevant for CEA-NBS: The design of a NBS must serve a purpose for humans by incentivizing them to sustain the NBS ecosystem. This mutual influence works both ways: Humans design an NBS, and the NBS, in turn, shapes human behavior beyond their original intentions. The NBS serves a purpose for humans, and humans, in turn, serve a purpose for the NBS. This symbiotic relationship resembles gardening, where humans tend to the garden and, in doing so, work in the interest of other species within the garden (box 1.9).

The primary framework for all these co-evolutionary processes is not natural selection, but rather sexual selection. Sexual selection is often viewed as the most important type of what is also known as signal selection (Zahavi and Zahavi, 1997). Building on this idea, we propose the term “semiotic selection” (Maran and Kleisner, 2010). While natural selection focuses solely on mechanistic causation, semiotic selection involves co-evolutionary processes. Many biological adaptations, typically attributed to natural selection, are actually utilized in immediate interactions and behaviours within specific environmental conditions. Therefore, most adaptations are in some way dependent on the semiotic qualities of animals – their perception, recognition, and interpretation – which may also include aesthetic aspects. This suggests an evolutionary rationale for the development of subjectivity and independent creative agency.

In a complex ecosystem, it is unlikely that the coordination among all its components is directly determined by genetically fixed behaviours. The complexity and unpredictability of continuous change require the ability for flexible behavioural coordination among agents, which necessitates forms of semiotically mediated reflexivity, even in the simplest ways. This enables forward-looking exploratory behaviour, memory, and innovation. As a result, animals, and perhaps all living systems, exhibit forms of "self" that are certainly different from, but also phylogenetically related to humans (Damasio, 2019). Furthermore, there is the potential for convergent evolution on various levels. For instance, while most researchers consider Great Apes to be closely related to humans in terms of self-awareness and consciousness, there are compelling reasons to believe that elephants are qualitatively closer due to convergent evolution in similar habitats (Ross, 2022). On a different level of phylogenetic depth, forms of self may have emerged several times, such as in the now much-debated case of octopuses with a rich semiotic behavioural repertoire (Godfrey-Smith, 2017). These different forms of self-awareness enable creative behaviors within complex ecosystems, resulting in the development of consistent patterns in behavioral coordination, or habits.

2.2.2. Umwelt and semiosis

Accordingly, we can introduce another important distinction for our argument: the difference between Umwelt and ecological niche. When approaching an ecosystem, we can take two different approaches. One is focusing on the mechanical causality of food webs and other forms of physical interaction. The other is to conceptualize the ecosystem as an assembly of Umwelts based on the general Peircean model of semiosis. Von Uexküll's concept of Umwelt can be directly translated into the Peircean framework, with Umgebung referring to the environment as an object and the Umwelt as the assembly of signs that elicit actions from the organism. Von Uexküll also recognizes the creative agency of the animal, so subjectivity is both how the environment appears to the organism and how the organism acts on that environment. However, since von Uexküll mostly considers the species level, the Umwelt can be seen as being determined by ultimate causes P* in the longer run.

Figure 22 Semiosis of Umwelt

The translation between Peirce and Uexküll is straightforward, so we concentrate on one key point. This starts out from the often-heard critique of Umwelt as Uexküll's "bubble" since it seems to conceptualize Umwelt as monadic subjectivity. But that

overlooks the fact that we can conceptualize an ecosystem both as connected via mechanistic linkages such as predator-prey relations, or as multitudes of *Umwelts* which are connected via communication, such as the signaling between predator and prey. We can first recognize *Umwelt* diversity, and then ask how from this diversity the ecosystem is constituted as a local *ecosemiosphere* (Maran, 2021b). We can also see these two perspectives – mechanical and *Umwelt* perspective – as integrated. That is, *Umwelts* are rooted in and constrained by the ecological web, while at the same time, animal *Umwelts*, through selective perception and action, regulate ecological webs in every interaction.

At first glance, it may seem difficult to access these various perspectives, but the Peircean approach offers a simple solution by treating the action as an interpretant. For instance, in the previously mentioned Australian experiment, owlhouses that have not yet been visited by owls have been explored by other species. By observing these actions, we can make hypotheses about the different subjective perceptions of the object. This method is commonly used in biological research on animal sensation, such as pain. Although we may not know if animals feel pain, we can infer from certain actions, which go beyond simple nociception, that they likely experience a feeling functionally similar to human pain (Tye, 2017). The general point here is to observe actions that deviate from established habits. While the owlhouse was designed to be metaphorically accessible to owls, similar to a termite mound, it may also hold meaning for other species, possibly for different reasons.

Semiotic causality is a complex form of causation, which Karen Barad refers to as “intra-action” (Barad, 2007). This concept also applies to the relationship between an object and a sign. The duality of perception and assignment translates into different types of relationships that we already met previously (Atkin, 2023). One type of relationship is mechanistic, known as the index in Peircean terms. Indexes are signs that are physically related to the object, such as being caused by it, and they also have causal powers. For example, heat is a sign of fire, both as a property of fire and as a cause of the surrounding environment heating up. Another type of sign is the icon, which is physically distinct but similar to the object. The recognition of an icon as referring to an object requires identifying similarities, like comparing various holes in

past nesting sites with the hole in an owlhouse. There is a connection between indexical signs and icons, as the perception of an icon as adequately referring to an object relies on anchoring the assignment in a physical property of the object that triggers the assignment, which amounts to indexical evocation of the icon (Kohn, 2013, chap. One). At the same time, the recognition of an indexical sign is grounded in the perception of similarities that are themselves iconic. In this sense, cognition is based on iconic signs, as it is rooted in similarities. In the domain of action, similarities are habits. These distinctions are theoretical in the first place but allow us to conceptualize how Uexküllian Umwelts “intra-act”, including human Umwelts as reflected in language.

These theoretical considerations are important for CEA-NBS when it comes to understanding the relationship between different ecosystem services, biodiversity, and culture. Since the term was first used, ecosystem services have been primarily focused on human needs and include cultural ecosystem services (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). In the general understanding, cultural ecosystem services are clearly anthropocentric, while the other ecosystem services can also be seen as interconnected with the needs and functions of all other beings in an ecosystem. The ecosemiotic approach enables the development of operational methods to integrate these different perspectives (box 2.6).

Box 2.6 Iconic species and ecology

The ecosemiotic approach allows us to consider ecological issues at the intersection of nature and culture, such as in an urban community and its surrounding area. When looking at urban ecology and conservation issues, the typical approach focuses on functional relationships without acknowledging any additional dimensions of meaning. This overlooks the perspective of the community and non-experts, and what they value in their local ecosystem. This is similar to the differences between scientific language and the everyday language of the community, such as the scientific knowledge about owls versus the stories and myths of the community. This is becoming more recognized in scientific approaches. An important example is the difference between the indicator species approach in conservation, the iconic species approach, and the flagship species approach (Davies and Tippler, 2024). There are differences in terminologies across various contributions in the literature (Albert et al., 2018; McGinlay et al., 2017), where “charismatic species” is often used to refer to what is considered an iconic species here, following Davies and Tippler.

An indicator species reflects a specific aspect of ecosystem functioning and health, while a flagship species may have no functional value and may not even be present in the local ecosystem. The indicator species approach is based on causal relationships between certain ecosystem properties and species abundance. The flagship species is a symbol that lacks this causal connection and is only highlighted in societal discussions about nature conservation. In contrast, the iconic species has significant value in the local human community and is explicitly considered as representing the local ecosystem. Both types of species can be counted as charismatic, but the flagship species has no direct embodied significance for people. This is different for the iconic species. A standard example is certain types of fish, like salmon, in places with a tradition of fishing. In this case, the symbolic (cultural) and the indexical (ecological) merge, which defines the iconic species as bridging the perspectives of other species and humans. The iconic species emerges in a unique process of communication in which the human and non-human domains are connected through shared signs, and this is eventually examined through scientific reflection. The scientific approach is transdisciplinary because the identification of the iconic species incorporates the contributions of the local community; this is then used to embed local valuation in ecological analysis. For the local people, the iconic species is known in embodied experiences. In contrast, people may only have remote experiences with flagship species, such as in the zoo. When creating a NBS, this means that by focusing on the needs and functions of the iconic species rooted in the local ecosystem community, a wide range of connected structures in the habitat is involved, contributing to ecosystem flourishing while focusing on a species valued by the local community. Conversely, conserving the iconic species produces a cultural ecosystem service in terms of place-shaping (Raymond et al., 2018).

2.2.3. Semiosis of technology and aesthetic design of NBS

In this section on semiotic fundamentals, we introduce the semiotic analysis of technology (figure 23), which is important because NBS are conceived as co-evolutionary technology (Herrmann-Pillath et al., 2022). We present a “constructivist” view here, which we distinguish from an evolutionary view that we support. The constructivist view assumes that there is an agent who is fully knowledgeable about the technology; the engineer is an expert. First, the engineer creates the artifact as an object and includes its design in this creative act; second, she defines the ultimate

to the previous analysis, we acknowledge the role of semiotic creativity, which is reflected in the ambiguous nature of design. On one hand, design functions in a mechanical way, for example in terms of ergonomic practicality. On the other hand, design is interpreted through other, mostly aesthetic, subjective criteria of the user. This involves assigning meaning to design and indirectly influencing the evolution of design. Metaphorical cognitive processes are significant, for instance, considering a knife not only as a tool but imbuing it with other interpretations, such as viewing the knife as a symbol of violence, which might influence certain knife designs, like decorating it with particular symbols. A sword is not just a weapon, but a symbol in itself.

In modern cognitive science, the theory of metaphor as the elementary cognitive operation implies treating something as something else, for example, treating heat as a metaphor for fire (Fauconnier and Turner, 2003). Metaphorical operations are also crucial in artistic creativity, such as using "fire" in a poem as a metaphor for the "heat" of emotions. Literary theory emphasizes metonymy and metaphor as key dimensions of the artful use of language, which corresponds to index and icon, thus revealing the cognitive roots of creativity (Wheeler, 2016, p. 163). There is an important connection here to play, which is a behavior shared by humans and many non-humans: Owls "hunt" other objects than their prey, apparently without functional significance, such as towels or plastic bags.

In this perspective, meaning is initially seen as functional, but in Peirce's classification of signs, there is also a surplus of meaning through creative interpretation and active creation of signs. Within this framework, we consider Umwelt analysis as guiding the technological design of NBS as art. This involves a two-fold approach. Firstly, ecosemiotics aims to help us understand the aesthetic value of non-human entities and hence recognize it in human design of signs within multi-species Umwelts (Kull, 2022; Wheeler, 2016). Secondly, we seek to establish methods for involving non-humans in co-creating NBS, thereby inviting and facilitating their independent creative agency (Box 2.7). Both of these steps integrate aesthetic and ethical considerations, as design implementation may at times lead to conflicts and outright contradictions among diverse aesthetic values.

Box 2.7: Falconry as a traditional NBS in hunting

Traditional falconry exemplifies close human-animal interactions, where both parties influence each other's perceptions, communicate, and coordinate their actions (Schroer, 2021). It is a cultural tradition that has turned the human activity of hunting into an art, while also being a technology in which the bird is used as a tool. Falconry is seen as an aesthetic form that engages both birds and humans, and has also been the object of other artistic work, such as paintings or poetry.

Figure 24: Medieval falconry

<https://www.medievalists.net/2016/03/falconry-birds-and-lovebirds/>

A falconer learns to perceive the world from a falcon's perspective by emotionally connecting with the birds and interpreting their actions. The falcon does the same, leading to a mutual trust and understanding between the two. This interaction reflects Uexküll's theory that the animal and their surroundings are connected through emotions, which he refers to as "mood" and "tone". However, Uexküll believed that researchers could only access the animal's surroundings through cognitive processes, contradicting the embodied interaction seen in falconry. This case aligns with Uexküll's musical metaphor, where nature is compared to a piece of music with different melodies resonating with each other. The example of falconry illustrates the emerging harmony between the human and the animal, enabling joint action. However, the falconer does not have direct cognitive access to the falcon's surroundings, such as being able to "see" the world as the falcon does, as it is physiologically impossible. This creates a conceptual tension between Uexküll's idea of subjectivity and the resonant interaction between surroundings (Feiten, 2020). We can resolve this tension by considering the falcon and the falconer as an emergent entity with connected interpretations, involving a flow of actions embodied in feelings. This means that the surroundings change, making the process creative. Importantly, the relationship between the falconer and the falcon is individualized beyond the generic aspects of the species' behavior.

Figure 25: Falconer and falcon

<https://www.npr.org/2023/02/26/1158798396/falcon-hunting-training-falconer-bird-kansas>

In semiotic creativity, the organism does not passively perceive signs, but its world is a world of signs created by intra-action with the objects in the world. Accordingly, and essential for our argument, the line between “art” and “objective representation” is blurred (Daston and Galison, 2010). This is the fundamental reason why biotic phenomena such as the coloring of bird feathers can be conceived as art (Prum, 2017).

This is not the place for speculating about whether this can be reconciled with the general theory of evolution. In fact, this has been well elaborated in general theories of co-evolution that explain the evolutionary rationale for the emergence of non-genetic channels of transmission of traits, most importantly, cultural evolution (for a now classical exposition, see (Jablonka et al., 2014). Accordingly, the question of subjectivity relates to the theory of cultural evolution and, therefore, refers the question of non-human subjectivity to the question of non-human culture. Once we move to this framing of our discussion, the troubles with non-human subjectivity lose bite, as animal culture is today widely recognized for many species (Ramsey, 2017). Many birds are one of the important examples, since for many semiotic repertoires of birds cultural transmission is the regular case. That means, similar to human language, there is a genetic disposition to generate certain sound patterns, but how this evolves in specific manifestation is not genetically determined but a result of cultural learning. That

means, we diagnose a co-evolutionary process of creating birdsongs. We do not know the original creators of birdsongs ('artists'), but the local community of birds is a community of creative actors, presumably even less elitist than the human "artworld". Indeed, there is an illuminating analogy between excluding aesthetic activities from the notion of "art" that are conducted by marginalized groups in certain societies and the disregard of artistic creativity by non-humans.

2.3. Ecosemiotic methods

2.3.1. General principle of objectivity: Impartiality in recognizing the diversity of Umwelts

Grounded in the general theory of signs, ecosemiotic methods focus on actions as the primary unit of analysis and data collection. This category of action includes both humans and other species. Actions are viewed not from the perspective of an external scientific observer but instead from the diverse viewpoints of Umwelts that coexist and interact within the local ecosemiosphere. There is no concept of "action" from a "view from nowhere." Acknowledging the multiplicity of Umwelts means that no specific standpoint is privileged; thus, ecosemiotic methods maintain an impartial stance (Sen, 2009). Impartiality, in this context, is an ethical position that avoids referencing external standards of justice when evaluating the preferability of various arrangements for cohabitation between humans and other species.

Impartiality is widely recognized in advanced methods of transdisciplinary research that aim to include diverse human perspectives when evaluating a situation. A contemporary concept known as "two-eyed seeing" integrates both scientific and Indigenous viewpoints regarding an object of inquiry (Bartlett et al., 2012). However, in the human realm, this approach extends to the perspectives of various groups that engage with the object. For instance, these groups may include farmers, administrators, children, and others. In subsection 4.2, we will explore methods to identify these groups, primarily through stakeholder analysis.

It is important to emphasize that stakeholders are not merely predefined entities; rather, they are integral to the ecosemiotic process. Some groups may not express

any concern or may even display ignorance regarding the object. Nevertheless, from an expert's standpoint, these individuals may still be affected by the object without realizing it. For an effective ecosemiotic analysis, it is crucial to understand why and how the sharing of knowledge is obstructed among these groups. A fundamental principle of a Living Lab is that stakeholders are not assumed to be fixed; instead, they are shaped through the experimental practices of the Living Lab. This means that individuals who were not initially considered stakeholders can become involved as the process unfolds.

Impartiality is the ecosemiotic criterion for objectivity. This means that objectivity cannot be achieved solely through science; rather, it requires a transdisciplinary process. A key aspect of ecosemiotic methods is the organization of this process. A fundamental principle is that both data collection and analysis must be conducted inclusively, emphasizing participatory research. This does not imply that standard data collection methods should be abandoned. However, at a minimum, the interpretation of data must include input from the respondents. For example, this can be achieved through transdisciplinary workshops focused on data analysis. The gold standard is to involve local knowledge holders in the original design of specific research activities. This approach aligns well with the modern social science standards of qualitative research. However, it is challenging for all parties since it means that even the basic processes of data collection, data definition and data extraction must be shared among trained experts and local knowledge holders. A case in point is the necessary adaptations of ecosemiotic methods (box 2.8.).

Box 2.8: Co-creating ecosemiotic coding **coevolvers**

Ecolinguistic methods emphasize text-like structures, such as stories. In qualitative research, coding is the first step in analyzing text bodies that result from field research, like interview transcripts. This process becomes particularly challenging in transdisciplinary research because we cannot start from an expert's perspective when defining codes, which leads to categorizations based on a specific theory (deductive coding) (Hennink et al., 2019) p. 220ff). Knowledge co-production necessitates close collaboration with members of the NBS community to generate first-order codes (inductive coding). Furthermore, ecosemiotics adds a layer of complexity, as we avoid the goal of arriving at a single theory as an outcome; instead, we view the researcher's theory as just one linguistically mediated Umwelt among many others. We present an

overview of the ecosemiotic approach to coding in Figure 25.

Figure 25: Ecosemiotic approach to coding

We treat ecosemiotics as a metatheory that acknowledges the multiplicity of Umwelts in the context of epistemic justice. In this framework, various Umwelts serve as a basis for "theory" within standard coding practices. For example, a specific observational datum can be interpreted through the lens of ecological theory, from the perspective of a child's Umwelt, or from that of a sheep's Umwelt. Ecosemiotics achieves this by focusing on specific data types that possess more-than-human qualities (refer to section 1.3, figure 9). These data types include experiences and actions. In the initial phase, transdisciplinary researchers identify actions and experiences within textual materials. This process involves collaboration with the producers of those texts, using formats such as focus groups or rehearsals of original interviews. Non-human perspectives are systematically integrated to build a comprehensive body of texts that includes both human and non-human participants. For instance, this can involve combining human narratives with vicarious non-human letter writing that pertains to the same environment, such as a forest.

The first-order codes represent "concrete abstractions" of the original data type, meaning they are generalizations. For example, various references to a fence can relate to actions and experiences, such as access being blocked or feeling protected by the fence. These references can be coded as "meeting a fence" (a concrete abstraction). However, a significant challenge arises due to the diverse Umwelts; the fence may signify very different experiences and actions. For instance, the fence with a gate might not constitute a mobility constraint for adults, but it could be a barrier for young children and sheep. For birds, the fence provides a perching spot, while for certain plants, it offers an opportunity to grow upwards. Therefore, when applying codes, it is crucial to consider the relationships to multiple categories, such as "mobility constraints" or "resting places" (see figure 26). Relating codes to various categories is essential for capturing the diversity of Umwelts in ecosemiotic analysis.

Figure 26; Multiple categorization of codes

Second-order categories emerge through a two-step process of abstraction over coded data. For example, we can relate the concept of “meeting a fence” to the category of “mobility constraints.” Mobility constraints can encompass various first-order codes and connect to Umwelts as theoretical constructs, as outlined by ecosemiotic metatheory in the second step. For instance, a “no trespass” sign represents a mobility constraint only within the human Umwelt.

By employing ecosemiotic coding on a sample of texts, we can reconstruct what is initially perceived as “nature,” such as forests or lakes, from the ground up. This process reveals a multiplicity of Umwelts grounded in the basic experiences and actions of both humans and non-humans. Instead of starting with beliefs and attitudes about nature, we begin by examining experiences and interactions with objects that are instinctively associated with nature. This means we start our analysis with trees rather than considering the forest as a whole. It is also worth noting that while a fence may represent non-nature to humans, it can be considered part of nature for a bird that enjoys perching on it.

Ecosemiotics plays a crucial role in bridging the two fundamental epistemic movements that separate the sciences from the humanities (Snow, 2018): explanation and interpretation. Interpretation is essential for understanding data in relation to various Umwelts. Therefore, data cannot be considered "objective" in the traditional sense. However, this interpretative step is vital for enabling researchers to explain their observations, including the manifest actions of different actors in NBS.

The challenge lies in incorporating the Umwelts and perspectives of other species into a transdisciplinary process. There are essentially two approaches to achieve this.

First, researchers can translate their findings into actionable steps and engage with the responsive behaviours of other species. This experimental approach to data generation and analysis is characteristic of Living Labs. Second, through a transdisciplinary method, humans from diverse backgrounds can adopt representative roles pertaining to other species and communicate their actions using human forms of expression. In this collaborative engagement, the arts serve as an essential method (box 2.9).

Box 2.9: Co-creating a NBS avatar

This art-based method originates from a surrealist parlor game and is now available in various formats. We can use it to disrupt participants' usual way of thinking about what constitutes a human agent and encourage creative connections with non-human entities. In this activity, we collaboratively draw a humanoid that symbolizes the NBS in question, such as an urban natural watershed, represented by a steward embodying its key features, which are then transformed into an avatar. The humanoid is divided into four segments: head, torso, waist, and legs. For each segment, participants think of non-human creatures that possess the qualities needed to support the flourishing of the NBS, metaphorically speaking. For instance, one participant might draw the head of a salamander to represent its ability to thrive in both land and water environments. In four groups, each participant draws one segment on separate pieces of paper. These papers are folded so that participants can only see the specific segment they are meant to draw. The procedure is as follows

1. Participants start in groups of 3-4 people and are provided with several pieces of white rectangular paper and colored pens. Each paper is folded into 4 parts so that it creates 4 parallel sections - the top will be for the head, the second section for the torso, the third for the waist, and the fourth for the feet.
2. The facilitator explains the background and concept of the exercise and the expected time each person will have to draw each part of the body.
3. When the timer starts, each person begins to draw a head on the top of their folded paper with some phrases or keywords that represent what this being might say or how their mind works.
4. After 3 minutes, each person extends the outline of the neck approximately 1 cm into the section of the paper below the head, so that the next person knows where to start their drawing. Each person then folds the paper in such a way that the next person cannot see the head (only the neck marks).
5. Everyone then draws the torso and arms, using the neck lines as the beginning point, including words or phrases that represent how this being might feel emotionally, or what they care about.
6. Once again, the outline or edges of the torso are marked approximately one cm into the next section. The paper is folded again so that the next person cannot see either the head or the torso and it is passed on.
7. This process is repeated with the waist to knees (what is motivating the being, what their deeper drives might be) and the knees to feet (what kind of actions they might take and how).

8. Finally, all of the characters are unfolded and participants have the chance to see them as a whole.
9. Groups are invited to discuss differences and commonalities and to consolidate themes and ideas that emerge (including paradoxes).

As a result, the group creates four images that combine features from four existing non-human beings into a new fictional creature. This creature symbolizes the presumed abilities needed to effectively address the NBS challenge. Participants engage in discussions about how to interpret these different embodied perspectives and capacities in relation to the NBS.

The core idea of this method involves bridging both indexical and symbolic signs to co-create an icon, without achieving a comprehensive design or engineering solution. By envisioning the capabilities of other species within the context of ecosystem functioning, participants draw upon their knowledge to identify and select specific body parts. While the process appears primarily symbolic, it also reflects the evolutionary flexibility of the composition or avatar. Ultimately, the outcome is an icon representing the NBS.

Adapted and method paraphrased from:
<https://www.reimaginary.com/methods/exquisite-corpse>

Figure 27: Exquisite corpses

<https://www.tes.com/teaching-resource/ks3-art-exquisite-corpse-12841509>

2.3.2. More-than human empathy as a necessary condition of impartiality

The theory of impartiality traces its roots to Adam Smith's (1982) work on moral sentiments, which can be effectively expanded to include other species. In the 19th century, this theory played a crucial role in inspiring early animal rights movements, advocating that sentiments are universally shared among both humans and other

species (Pearson, 2021). Smith posited that impartiality can be represented by the concept of the "spectator," an internal cognitive state that supports the process of impartial judgment. This state arises not from reasoning based on language, but from a struggle of conflicting feelings within a framework created by a general capacity for "sympathy" among humans. This perspective aligns with modern views on moral intuitionism (Haidt, 2001).

Smith's concept of sympathy aligns with modern understandings of empathy (Decety, 2015). The underlying mechanism is that a particular action invokes feelings, such as joyful approval or resentment. These feelings are experienced either as one's own emotions or as the imagined emotions of others, rooted in empathy. As a result, individuals can intuitively compare contrasting feelings, such as their own resentment towards someone else's actions against that person's resentment towards a retaliatory response. For example, if someone slaps me and I hit back, I can evaluate the feelings of both sides in this situation. Smith argues that empathy enables individuals to form judgments from a third-party perspective, ultimately leading to a sense of impartiality. The entire argument is based on the capacity to empathize. Empathy is not innate; rather, it is shaped by the semiotic structuring of ingroup and outgroup boundaries (Cikara et al., 2011; Herrmann-Pillath, 2021b) (for more on that, see chapter 3). For instance, during the era of Nazism, many Germans suppressed all empathy toward Jews through various ideological constructs. This situation parallels the relationships between humans and other species today. While we may empathize with our pets, we often fail to do so with chickens raised on industrial farms. This illustrates that fostering empathy is crucial in co-cultures that recognize other species as having feelings (Young et al., 2018).

Now, this argument is often seen as anthropomorphic. However, there are two principled reasons why empathy is possible that can foster a Smithian process of non-cognitive weighing of feelings across species (Simon and Gutsell, 2021; Urquiza-Haas and Kotrschal, 2022). The first has been presented in section 2.1 where we introduced the capability approach as a general framework for ethical judgments. If we semiotically construct the Umwelt of other species as related to their capabilities, these capabilities can be translated into categories that match with similar capabilities of

humans, on an appropriate level of abstraction. For example, mobility can take different forms, such as walking, swimming or flying, but caging results in the same incapacitation across all those modes. Hence, we empathize with an Octopus in a narrow aquarium even though morphologically, the species is very different from humans. The second reason is that we can argue that feelings are phylogenetically grounded in the deep evolutionary past and eventually reflect the common origin of life on Earth (Damasio, 2019).

Therefore, a key aspect of ecosemiotic methods is creating conditions for empathizing with other species that cohabit in the ecosystem where the NBS is located. This prepares the ground for a transdisciplinary process in the Living Lab (box 2.10).

Box 2.10 Personifying more-than human feelings

In the design of sustainability workshops, there is a method for personifying emotions among humans (Pearson et al., 2018, p. 30ff). This method can be adapted to include non-human species. The procedure is straightforward. Participants from a LL community gather to envision several non-human species that are relevant stakeholders in the NBS. The group discusses the main issues and creates a list of typical situations where interactions between humans and non-humans affect the performance of the NBS, as well as how various stakeholders may be positively or negatively impacted. For instance, when considering an eco-compensation scheme, participants may identify issues such as relocating animals. This process results in two lists: one of the identified issues and another of the non-human stakeholders. The facilitator may then add a list of potential feelings associated with these issues.

Next, participants form pairs. Each pair selects an issue and chooses one non-human species to represent. One participant acts as the non-human and announces an emotion related to the issue (such as fear), while the other participant expresses that feeling using gestures, facial expressions, or other non-verbal cues. The first participant then responds by mimicking the non-human they represent, emphasizing the physical traits of that species, although it does not need to be an accurate biological representation.

After completing this round, participants discuss their experiences. The rounds can continue by rotating the members of the pairs. The session concludes with a group discussion. The aim of this method is to enhance the empathetic capacities of LL members and help them relate to various non-human stakeholders in the NBS through embodied expressions.

2.3.3. Ecosemiotic modelling of NBS and community composition

A key ecosemiotic method is the ecosemiotic modelling of an NBS (Maran, 2020a). This method connects to the psychological mechanism of framing that we explore in

chapter 3: An ecosemiotic model creates a frame in which actors perceive the NBS. The modeling serves two main functions: first, from the researcher perspective it establishes the analytical framework within which various aspects of the NBS are explored; second, for the community it guides the development of the NBS by co-creative actions. This further illustrates the principle of normativity. For example, ecosemiotic modelling may define whether an NBS is viewed as a commons or not, which requires, most importantly, the identification of a common resource. This could be treated as functionally given. However, the ecosemiotic modelling can assume performative powers in guiding a process of commoning by which the community both recognizes and cocreates that common resource (Leitheiser et al., 2022; Ragavan and Srivastava, 2020).

Ecosemiotic modelling does not start from a privileged perspective. Instead, it focuses on defining alternative frameworks that promote collaborative conceptualization and implementation of NBS. A key epistemological condition is the recognition that the human cultural and scientific realm exists within the broader ecosemiosphere, where humans coexist with other species. The human sphere creates an "Umwelt" that influences human actions, which in turn interact functionally with the ecosystem. For example, our cultural perspective shapes how we perceive wolves, guiding our interpretations of their behaviour and subsequently affecting our actions towards them (Hiedanpää, 2023). The human sphere is marked by a diversity of groups, such as conservationists and farmers, along with individual differences. Similarly, wolves exhibit variations in behaviour, including age-related differences. Ecosemiotic modeling starts by establishing a viewpoint that is as inclusive as possible.

Considering the example of wolves, we can explore a broader issue regarding how we interact with liminal species that exist at the boundary between the human domain and the non-human world (Donaldson and Kymlicka, 2013). This boundary typically lies between human settlements and other areas, which are largely under human control. A significant step in ecosemiotic modelling is to establish a framework that dissolves the semiotic distinctions between the human environment and the outer territories: What is the "landscape" that we see in the NBS (Farina, 2021)? One potential approach is to reframe urban areas as forests, a concept reflected in

metaphors such as "urban jungle." This perspective enables us to view the human domain and surrounding areas as part of a larger ecosemiotics unit, which partially eliminates the boundary: The forest becomes the model for both the urban and the surrounding areas (on the forest as a model, see (Maran, 2021a). As a result, liminal species, like wolves, entering urban spaces are perceived not as crossing a line but as engaging in a normal movement through space. The perception of wolves as "wild" or "liminal" largely depends on how we frame urban settlements in relation to their surroundings. If we see the area as an artificial city, the wolf is viewed as "wild"; however, if we frame it as a "forest," the wolf may even be regarded as part of the community that encompasses both the city and its surroundings.

Grounding the ecosemiotic model within the forest framework has many implications, particularly when we consider what type of forest is envisioned—whether it's a capitalist monoculture or a dense jungle, for example. In practice, this grounding can take various forms. For instance, a workshop could be organized with diverse human groups to engage in a creative process aimed at envisioning the human/non-human domain as a forest and determining which specific image of a forest is most relevant. This process should not be restricted by scientific criteria. The transdisciplinary creation of a grounded framework is a creative and artistic endeavour that can take many forms of expression.

Box 2.11: Inviting non-humans in composing the NBS coevolvers

This exercise has two main functions. First, human participants select a specific non-human entity and adopt its role within the NBS as Living Lab members. This process helps them develop their capacity for empathy. Second, by doing this, participants co-create the Living Lab from the perspectives of various non-humans, thereby building an ecosemiotic model.

The session begins with an outdoor walk at the NBS location. The facilitator distributes Umwelt cards (fig. 28) to the participants, each of whom selects one card. During the walk, participants focus on the environment through the lens of the information provided on these cards, which describe essential characteristics of the species, their habitats, and behaviors.

Figure 28: Umwelt cards used by Tartu Living Lab

Back to the meeting room, the procedure is as follows:

1. Ask everyone to take a few moments to imagine being “in the skin” of individual on their Umwelt card: how does it feel, what do they notice, how do they move through the landscape?
2. In pairs, participants introduce themselves to each other in character, either reading from their card and/or sharing spontaneous reflections.
3. Give participants some time (3-5 minutes) to reflect individually on their ‘character’. Invite them to write down some notes, words, or drawings, inspired by some guiding questions (sample script):
 - What does this place mean to you?
 - What is your best memory of this place?
 - If you think about the past, is there something you are grateful for?
 - How are the changes taking place affecting you and your life?
 - What do you wish for the future of the place, what are the needs you wish could be fulfilled for your species?
 - How would you like to contribute to making this ideal future come true?
4. Participants share insights or thoughts in pairs, and in the group.
5. Once everyone has settled into their role, the role can be retained for the rest of the workshop / thematic discussion in the project. Everyone now represents the interests of their role.

The ecosemiotic model can now be developed in the form of a story that tells the experience of this exercise.

Adapted and method paraphrased from: <https://www.reimaginary.com/methods/inviting-non-human-stakeholders>

2.3.4. Multi-species ecography

Ecosemiotic modeling embodies the principle of holism, while ecofield analysis reflects the principle of individualization. Ecofield analysis is a method used in ecosemiotics to describe and analyze NBS as landscapes viewed from various perspectives, taking into account the actions of different agents who hold these perspectives (Farina and Belgrano, 2006). Ecofields can be reconstructed analytically at the species level; however, since this concept is based on actions, it ultimately pertains to individual instances. Additionally, the concept applies to both humans and non-humans, as it is independent of linguistic representation and focuses on actions instead.

To understand the relationship between individuals and their environment, we start by examining their capabilities and functions, which helps us reconstruct their respective *Umwelts*. For example, consider a rabbit: it has various relationships, such as foraging for food and avoiding predators like birds. These two activities represent different ecofields centered around the rabbit, each with its own spatial structure and related actions.

We can define an eco-field as a set of affordances tied to a specific type of capabilities and functions. Foraging, for instance, is a generic concept applicable to humans as well. People who gather wild berries or mushrooms also engage in foraging. This understanding allows us to create a series of eco-fields for various agents in relation to the NBS. By doing so, we can construct the multi-dimensional *Umwelts* of different agents. The ecofield analysis relates closely to the ecological repertoire approach (Maran, 2020b). The difference is that the ecofield focuses on actions, whereas the latter takes events as a unit of observation. Events are defined as interactions and encounters. This has the advantage of avoiding the Uexküllian bubble fallacy and making the connections across *Umwelts* explicit: The ecofields include other agents, as in predator-prey interactions.

Both methods are based on observation and hence are analogues to the ethnographic method, which suggests the term “ecographic”. As with ethnography, ecography substantial input of researchers’ time. Therefore, ecography invites the inclusion of

citizens as local knowledge holders in documenting events and actions. An established method is behavioural mapping (box 2.12).

Box 2.12: Behavioural mapping

Behavioural mapping (see box 1.8) is a method for documenting the uses of a certain terrain by its inhabitants and visitors, both humans and non-humans, and employs methods of ecological repertoire analysis. It is participatory regarding humans who document both human and non-human actions and events. It can be done via both offline and online maps. For the offline case, the procedure is as follows. A group of LL members gathers and launches the project.

1. Behavioural maps are produced manually on site. Obtain an accurate map of the area under observation and print it out. Attach the map to a piece of thick and stiff paperboard/ wooden board for convenient drawing and writing.
2. Define together with the participants activities and details to be observed, such as the type and duration of the activity, direction of the movement, users' gender and age, time of the day, time of the week and weather conditions.
3. Schedule specific times and their repetitions for observation. Include different times of the week (weekdays and weekends) and different times of the day (morning, afternoon, evening). It is useful to make observations in varying weather conditions (dry, warm and sunny versus rainy, cold and windy).
4. Develop a system of symbols for coding and counting. The symbols should be clear and simple to minimise the effort required for recording observations. Attach the list of anticipated activities, their assigned symbols and additional details (e.g. duration, age group) to the map for guidance. Include some additional symbols to record unexpected or infrequent activities.
5. Conduct the surveys with the participants.
6. Analyse the results. How did the actual observed activities and their locations differ from your expectations?

The map can be seen as depicting the various ecofields of individuals which are not only reflected in actions and events, but also habits, if the project is conducted over longer time spans,

Source: <https://participatory.tools/tools/observation-behavioral-mapping/>

2.3.5. Semiotic acts and story-telling

In the semiotic approach, meaning is seen as action, and action is influenced by various perspectives. The division between humans and non-humans often opposes language to other forms of behavior. However, with the emergence of speech act theory and ordinary language theory in the 1950s and 1960s, the idea has gained traction that language is a form of action that can be analyzed through the lens of speech acts (Green, 2021).

Speech acts serve different functions, such as making threats, transferring information, or making promises. We can expand this concept to include semiotic acts, which help bridge the gap between humans and non-humans, while also freeing human speech acts from the limitations of spoken and written language. A human speech act is always accompanied by other semiotic acts, such as facial gestures, which are often crucial for conveying the intended meaning of spoken words. For instance, expressing a threat is only credible when supported by the appropriate facial expressions and hand movements. This combination establishes a continuity between humans and non-humans through the convergence of certain gestures and actions that serve signalling and expressive functions (Bar-On, 2018). This connection also suggests a potential basis for empathy. While there are risks of anthropomorphism that could lead to misinterpretation, this connection also supports interspecies learning.

Documenting and analyzing semiotic acts is a central concern in ecosemiotics. However, it is important to recognize that semiotic acts are never isolated; they occur within a continuous flow of events. For instance, a threat arises in an encounter between two agents, and this interaction is part of a larger structure involving a series of actions. Consequently, one key method in ecolinguistics as part of ecosemiotics is the analysis of narratives. Narratives take various forms and illustrate broader patterns, which we will discuss in the next section. In the previous example involving wolves, societal narratives about wolves shape behavioral attitudes during specific encounters that themselves have narrative structures. We refer to the description of such encounters as a “story.”

We use this term in two ways. First, it refers to the story that people construct about an event. Second, it highlights that the event itself has a structure similar to a story, meaning the story told by individuals is just one perspective. This implies that many different stories could emerge from the various viewpoints of those involved in the event. We can merge these stories into a narrative that showcases these diverse perspectives, a technique commonly found in artistic writing or filmmaking, where events are portrayed as experienced by different characters (Goldie, 2014).

In ecosemiotics, this unique blend of fiction and real-world ecological knowledge is termed “nature-text” (Maran, 2007; Tüür, 2009). Thus, in ecosemiotics, stories serve as an art form with analytical scientific value, as they capture the flow of semiotic actions within a particular event or series of events. How does a threat occur? What is the response of the receiver to the semiotic act? Similar to fiction, this flow of events is never predetermined but remains open-ended. The storytelling method makes this exploration possible (box 2.13).

Box 2.13: Multi-species digital story-telling coevolvers

Digital storytelling is a powerful method for giving voice to individuals who may lack mainstream skills in verbal expression, who experience emotional distress that is difficult to articulate, or who wish to convey sensitive meanings that language may not fully capture (De Jager et al., 2017; Flicker and MacEntee, 2020). This approach allows for the expression of feelings, the interpretation of contexts, and the narration of events, making it a fitting medium for sharing nature-related narratives. However, there remains a challenge in inviting other species to participate in digital storytelling, even when the primary focus of the story is to communicate issues such as the threat of extinction and the suffering that accompanies it.

In the context of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), a potential initiative is to launch a project focused on multi-species digital storytelling within the local community. Participants would form various groups, with each group choosing to write a story that features a specific species as a character, rather than simply writing about the species itself. This approach is similar to letter-writing, where participants craft letters from the perspective of an animal or other living being.

These stories will follow the principles of nature writing, blending fiction with ecological knowledge. The advantage of digital storytelling is that participants can incorporate various media to capture a wide range of sensory experiences. For instance, they might include audio recordings of specific animal vocalizations relevant to the story, such as alarm calls. Additionally, video technology can provide unique perspectives, allowing us to see the world through the eyes of animals, for example, by using drones to capture images or videos from a bird's viewpoint (see box 1.8). The result of such a project is a collection of digital stories of diverse species that make up the NBS, such as when considering a green roof, writing stories about birds, bees, butterflies or worms relating to the green roof. As in this case, the stories can be motivated by a preliminary stage of observing a green roof over a certain time span.

Storytelling is essential for integrating the principles of holism and individualization. This perspective aligns with the duality present in von Uexküll's work, where he alternates between viewing Umwelts from a reductionist standpoint—as products of natural selection and evolution—and as “melodies” that highlight a semiotic surplus,

serving as a creative principle (Feiten, 2020). This distinction is reminiscent of the Ancient Greek concepts of *bios* and *zoe* (Cazaban-Mazerolles, 2018). Consequently, storytelling is also an effective method for reporting and reflecting on the scientific processes and outcomes of a Living Laboratory (LL). The report illustrates the evolutionary dynamics of habit formation. For example, in Australia, the concept of “country” becomes the focal point of storytelling, describing the transdisciplinary process as being co-authored by the land (Country et al., 2016).

2.3.6. Narratives

In ecolinguistics, media studies, and related fields, narratives are distinct from stories. While stories focus on single chains of events, narratives encompass broader structures of recurring themes that describe specific patterns in the flow of events (Stibbe, 2021). For instance, climate change is often associated with narratives about rising sea levels and the necessary actions to address this issue. There are various narratives surrounding NBS, each relating to specific ecosystem services and their role in addressing societal challenges. However, these narratives can vary significantly in the patterns of action they promote. For example, the green transformation narrative upheld by the EU often emphasizes job creation and business perspectives, while the expert community tends to highlight the importance of biodiversity.

Narratives closely relate to the concept of discourses (Gee, 2011). The definitions of the terms diverge in the literature, so we fix our own usage in distinguishing discourse from narratives in explicitly relating to the communities in which discourses unfold. As in the previous example, there is the NBS discourse at the EU and the NBS discourse in the scientific community, which can be further dissected in discourses, say, in the community of hydraulic engineers or the community of urban ecologists. There are many tools in discourse analysis that allow to decode texts and messages linked to NBS, often revealing tensions and contradictions over NBS (Han and Luo, 2024; Melanidis and Hagerman, 2022).

Ecosemiotics approaches these categories as Umwelts that are shaped by human language, that is, internal to the human domain (Tønnessen, 2015). An important question is how the NBS evolves in the interaction between those various human Umwelts via the interaction between the different communities of discourse, how this is moved by narratives, and how the NBS community can create new narratives that bridge the various discourses (Box 2.14).

Box 2.14: Future more-than-human newspaper

The "future newspaper" is a tool that allows participants to explore various sequences of events leading to specific future outcomes. This activity can be framed in different ways, such as aligning with the different scenarios and pathways outlined by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. We propose a new approach that connects the newspaper concept to various communities, both human and non-human. In the human context, this reflects the increasing partisanship in journalism, particularly in the United States. We can create different newspaper issues tailored to specific scenarios for diverse audiences—for instance, developing a newspaper issue that addresses the worst-case scenario for a neo-liberal audience.

Moreover, we can extend this idea to non-human audiences that pertain to specific NBS. For example, if the NBS focuses on forests, we can envision a "forest newspaper" aimed at the members of the forest ecosystem. Participants can take on various roles, such as "tree reporters," "deer reporters," and so forth. The process is as follows:

1. Divide participants into groups of three to five. Give each group a Future Newspaper Canvas and Post-it notes for brainstorming.
2. Write a headline which reflects the chosen scenario. It is often easier to start from the landmark change they want to see in their particular context. This can be as realistic or outlandish as you want: however, this choice will have a direct impact on the ideas generated after.
3. How do we get to that future? Using the canvas, participants will consider, discuss, and strategize what resources, conditions, people, and events must come together to achieve the future they have envisioned.
4. Lay out all the Future Newspapers. After a brief presentation and discussion on the merits of each, different methods can be used to reach a consensus on which route to take.

As a result, the future newspaper constructs various sets of narrative of the NBS in a multi-species perspective. These narratives are discussed in the human NBS community to explore future pathways on transformative change.

Sources: <https://unalab.enoll.org/future-newspaper/>; <http://gonano-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/citizen-sensing-a-toolkit.pdf> p. 124-128

2.3.6. Co-culture

The concept of co-culture focuses on the connections between species-specific cultures through semiotic linkages (see section 2.2.3). A key term here is "semiotic co-option," which refers to phenomena that hold meaning across different species, even though they are embedded within specific behavioural contexts (Kleisner, 2022).

To illustrate this, consider our workbird of owls. Owls carry diverse cultural meanings in human societies, ranging from negative associations, such as those with witches and death, to positive ones, such as wisdom (Ackerman, 2023). We cannot treat these meanings as mere reflections of nature, since they are symbolic and disconnected from ecological knowledge about owls. However, when we view the construction of owl houses as a co-cultural co-creation, we see a different relationship.

An owl house is a complex symbol that bridges owl and human cultures (see Box 1.7 for more details). Importantly, the design of the owl house must be intentionally crafted to encourage owls to adopt this new nesting site. The connection to ecological knowledge arises from adhering to specific engineering criteria when creating the owl houses (Parker et al., 2022b). The relationship between owl and owlhouse grounds in iconic signs, evoking similarities with natural nesting sites. At the same time, the owl house serves as a symbol in the human realm. The designer aims to establish a scenario where humans react positively to the presence of owls. The very notion of a "house" suggests "home," which fosters empathy and relationality. However, challenges can arise, such as the size of these structures being placed in urban neighbourhoods. Thus, the owl house may also be perceived as a piece of art, featuring a design that appeals to human aesthetics. As a result, the owl house is semiotically co-opted, bridging the divide between human and non-human worlds.

Co-cultures have long been recognized in zoosemiotics research (Mäekivi and Magnus, 2020) and are commonly observed in various contexts where animals interact systematically with humans, even as "workers". The NBS can resemble these co-cultures, especially in situations where two distinct groups of humans engage with animals: the caretakers or "employers" and the tourists or "clients." For instance, during vacations at horse farms, caretakers develop a co-culture with horses while

tourists experience the caretakers' culture alongside the horses (Hoarau-Heemstra and Kline, 2022).

Another instance in tourism is the interactions between tourists and monkeys at temple sites. These interactions were not originally intended by tourism designers; rather, they emerged from the active agency of the monkeys themselves (Malone and Ovenden, 2016). Co-cultures accompany CEA-NBS since in the long run, humans and other species need to develop shared and interlocking habits that sustain the NBS. On the human side, an essential aspect of co-culture is ritual and ritualization of habits (Herrmann-Pillath, 2024a). We come back to this in section 4.3. In general, humans can foster co-cultures via creative activities that enable them to access the Umwelts of other species and explore new forms of interacting with them (Box 2.15).

Box 2.15: Cross-species shadowing

A straightforward method for understanding other people's Umwelts in the human domain is through a technique called "People Shadowing." In this approach, two participants form a dyad where one person shadows the other. The activity occurs in the natural context of the person being shadowed. For example, the shadow of a teacher would follow that teacher throughout the entire day and during all activities, aiming to see the world through her eyes. This differs from participant observation, where an observer takes an external stance and simply enters the scene.

This method can potentially be extended to non-human animals, although there may be technical challenges depending on the species involved. However, many forms of shadowing can be easily realized, especially when animals serve as "workers" in NBS. For instance, when sheep are used for natural wildfire prevention, the shadowing can take on two different roles: one person could follow a shepherd, while another could follow a specific sheep. After the activity, the participants discuss their experiences, reflecting on how they viewed the same NBS from different perspectives.

Source: <https://unalab.enoll.org/shadowing-stakeholders/>

Chapter 3: Embodied drivers of action in coevolving NBS

3.0. Chapter summary

1. In studying human drivers of action in NBS, CEA-NBS integrates psychology, sociology, economics, and related disciplines in a general semiotic framework that applies Umwelt analysis on humans. Coevolutionary dynamics shape the emergence of habits via interactions between individuals and context/environment.
2. Drivers are seen as embodied (contra rational choice and cognitivist approaches). Terminological references to drivers are via thick concepts that relate cognition and feelings in evaluation (such as judging something as “ugly”). This view sees aesthetics as fundamental in the general sense of evaluative multi-sensory experiences that become embodied and drive actions.
3. Drivers are manifest in habits as embodied practices. Cognitive judgments are contextualized (“framing”). This contextualization is embodied in turn (for example, via cues). Values are constructs by the scientific observer and have no direct causal powers.
4. The human/non-human divide is shaped by the general human proclivity of constructing ingroup/outgroup boundaries. These boundaries affect the reach of inter-species empathy.
5. “Making kin” means transforming other species into in-groups of the human community (classical example: pets). This is essential for creating a multi-species community of NBS. There are various mechanisms, in which individualization is essential (recognizing the individuality of members of other species).
6. Framing is a fundamental cognitive mechanism that shapes drivers for action. Research methods should pay attention to framing effects, such as of money. Ecolinguistic methods identify framing effects. Frames are mostly triggered via embodied mechanisms.
7. Values are approached from two angles: First, they are reasons given for actions and, hence, are central to reflexive deliberation. Second, they are embodied in different forms, including as routines in organizations or institutions. Both dimensions do not need to concur: The value/action gap.
8. Therefore, in CEA-NBS, practice analysis is the key to understanding the drivers of action. Research methods, such as using vignettes in surveys, take practices as units of reference.
9. Practice analysis allows for the inclusion of non-human values via the reporting of practices in encounters between humans and other species. Here, multi-sensory experiences are critical. Preferred interviewing approaches are on-the-ground methods, such as walking interviews at the location of an NBS.

3.1. Coevolutionary theory, ecological psychology and semiotics: Umwelt analysis of individual human behaviour

3.1.1. Cross-disciplinary coevolutionary theory of evaluative individual-Umwelt links: Generalized aesthetics

The topic of why and how people perceive and respond to environmental issues is complex, drawing from various disciplines, particularly environmental psychology, sociology, and economics. In this section, we continue the approach established in previous sections, focusing on how people relate to non-human species and what a coevolutionary approach can contribute to cross- and transdisciplinary integration. Our emphasis is primarily on the human aspect, which is crucial for the subsequent chapter that will explore the more-than-human socio-politics of NBS. A key contribution of this chapter is linking human behaviour analysis to Umwelt analysis and ecosemiotics, as discussed earlier.

Focusing on the human side does not mean we overlook non-human concerns; rather, a central theme here is understanding how humans can incorporate non-human perspectives into the mechanisms that shape their behaviour towards the environment and NBS specifically. The main message is that this inclusion primarily occurs through embodied relationships rather than through reflexive concerns. This has methodological implications: methods that capture these embodied mechanisms are essential for CEA-NBS, while conventional approaches, such as surveys and interviews that focus on reflexive concerns, are less relevant. This methodological perspective is rooted in Bourdieu's research on habitus and practice (Bourdieu, 2019). The concept of co-evolution has two interpretations in this context. The first pertains to the human domain. Different disciplines focus on various aspects and use distinct reasoning styles, which is evident in their methodological approaches to understanding the role of context in individual behaviour. For instance, economists emphasize individual rationality and often downplay how much individual preferences—those that drive choices—are influenced by the choice environment. In contrast, behavioural economists highlight deviations from rational standards and advocate for environmental manipulation, termed “nudges,” to encourage rational

behaviour (Thaler and Sunstein, 2021). Psychology is generally more open to considering contextual factors, such as the influence of group conformity on individual behaviour. However, most approaches still regard individuals as the primary source of behaviour, focusing on personal values while viewing the environment merely as a modulating or enabling factor. In contrast, sociology places a stronger emphasis on contextual influences, often viewing individuals as reflections of group-level and societal processes.

The co-evolutionary approach seeks to integrate various perspectives into a single theoretical framework, where individuals and their contexts co-evolve to form shared habits that are reflected in practices. As outlined in the first chapter, the concepts of practice and habit are central to our research. One significant implication of this approach is that it prevents any form of individualistic reductionism in explaining behaviour. We connect individualistic perspectives with collective approaches by applying the concept of Umwelt to human sociality: other individuals constitute the social Umwelt for each person, and interactions with this social Umwelt depend on individual capabilities. These Umwelts are influenced by semiotic structures, with language being a crucial component (Tønnessen, 2015). The social Umwelt of a vulnerable and disadvantaged group, such as elderly single men with low education and pensions, is vastly different from that of local administrators who are adept in urban planning. When these two groups interact, the inner psychological states of the individuals co-evolve along with their actions, creating a semiotic pattern of practice. For instance, when communication fails between these groups, it can negatively impact the environmental values upheld by the vulnerable group. This scenario reflects recent experiences of populism and pushback against green policies across Europe (Bocquillon, 2024). Such developments inevitably affect how narratives regarding NBS are disseminated and accepted in society, as discussed in the previous chapter. They also have significant framing effects, a concept we will explore in this chapter. Methodologically, it's essential to note that these analytical concepts increasingly connect different disciplines; for example, economists have started examining how narratives shape collective economic states (Shiller, 2019).

Co-evolution can refer to the way human behaviors and their underlying drivers evolve alongside non-human behaviours. This concept expands the traditional view by acknowledging that non-humans act as autonomous agents in developing shared habits, leading to a situation where human drivers become integrated into this process. This perspective is revolutionary and aligns with recent developments in the evolutionary theory of domestication, which suggest that humans did not merely domesticate certain animals; rather, these animals also played a role in shaping human behaviour. A well-known example is the dog, which may have influenced cultural practices and behavioural patterns in humans (Gibson, 2021). While the issue of genetic co-evolution remains a subject of debate (Serpell, 2021), there are contemporary examples of dog-human co-cultural evolution that serve as key illustrations for CEA-NBS: in various nature-based settings, there is potential for the mutual adaptation of habits that are passed down culturally (see box 3.1).

Box 3.1. Street dogs in India

Recent developments in infrastructure theory, highlighted in D2.1, emphasize the importance of human/non-human relationships in providing certain infrastructural services, such as waste disposal in cities of the Global South (Barua, 2021). A particularly interesting case is that of street dogs in India, which have held a “liminal” status between feral and domesticated for centuries. These dogs have adapted to urban life in various cultural forms, exhibiting different behaviours in crowded places or shantytown environments (Barua and Sinha, 2022). Street dogs primarily scavenge for food and may hunt in groups. Their interactions with humans often involve reciprocal food exchange, where humans provide food, and in return, dogs offer emotional companionship and even services, such as acting as watchdogs. This dynamic reveals a multiplicity of *Umwelts* within human society. For the Indian middle class, dogs are often perceived as a nuisance, especially when they bark at night. As a result, these dogs are marginalized and not viewed as beings with whom emotional bonds can be formed. Conversely, marginalized human citizens, such as the homeless, tend to develop strong, reciprocal bonds with these dogs, often sharing food that is precious to them.

This example illustrates that human/non-human relationships, along with the associated values and beliefs, can only be understood through ecographic methods that reveal distinct *Umwelts*. For feral dogs, the city provides a rich array of ecofields, such as those for foraging and denning. Depending on the human group, dogs may be marginalized or even regarded as companions. This diversity is also evident in more formal NBS, where animals are intentionally engaged to provide distinct ecosystem services, such as the aforementioned examples of beavers and sheep.

The case of street dogs has significant historical implications as well. In the 19th century, dogs were a major policy issue in metropolitan areas like Paris and London, where the eradication of street dogs was considered a civilizational achievement—often contrasted with cities like Constantinople (Pearson, 2021). Domesticated dogs were “civilized” in

various ways, including special dietary provisions. Additionally, the way humans treated dogs was often viewed as a reflection of human civility and morality, suggesting that the evolution of habits around this relationship encompassed both dogs and the humans who considered themselves in charge.

Figure 29: Street dogs in India

<https://helpanimalsindia.org/news/library/saving-indias-street-dogs-from-abc-to-arv>

The example of domestication involves genetic coevolution, which is mostly not relevant in the context of NBS. However, a notable instance where coevolutionary dynamics is significant, even in the short term, is the relationship between human aesthetic tastes and the spread of wild plant species in urban areas. This relationship interacts with practices related to maintaining greenery. For instance, leaving dead wood from fallen trees in public parks can attract various wild plants and animal species, but this practice may conflict with human aesthetic preferences. Recognizing the natural beauty of such environments might require alternative aesthetic approaches, akin to the way fractures in classical Japanese porcelain are celebrated within the wabi-sabi aesthetic (Parkes and Loughnane, 2018). Overall, a key concept that connects valuation and behaviour is aesthetics, which also applies to human-animal relationships—such as viewing street dogs as dirty or unattractive compared to pets.

When approaching aesthetics in research methodology, it is crucial to refer to "thick concepts" and avoid abstract evaluative terms. The distinction between "thick" and "thin" concepts is particularly significant in ethics, where it differentiates abstract terms referring to the "good" from terms that evaluate specific behaviours, such as "cruel" or "caring" (Väyrynen, 2021). Thick concepts are vital in normative sciences because they inherently carry an evaluative component. This component primarily manifests in feelings rather than solely in cognitive judgments. For example, when we describe a behaviour as "fishy," it implies a cognitive judgment of distrust towards someone, even in the absence of direct evidence. Thick concepts directly relate to emotions which differ from visceral impulses in combining feelings with judgments. Emotions are critical in CEA-NBS as they build the bridge between environment and psychological states and are deeply contextualized by semiotic intermediation (Trip Glazer, 2017). In aesthetics, we observe a similar distinction between abstract terms like "sublime" and more everyday language terms such as "messy" or "elegant." Thick aesthetic concepts carry evaluations that are grounded in experience; for instance, muddy water evokes feelings of dirt and disgust. Therefore, when conducting surveys or interviews, it is essential to use such terms to identify embodied valuations. Abstract notions, like describing nature as beautiful, do not capture the specific experiences tied to phenomena in nature. What is important is to relate to those specific instances and the thick concepts that arise from them. This understanding should also inform the design and public communication of NBS measures. It is not sufficient to merely inform people about the necessity of keeping certain areas "messy." Even if individuals comprehend why an area should remain untidy, this information may not influence their embodied evaluations (see box 3.2).

Box 3.2. Everyday aesthetics and NBS design

As we have argued in previous sections, the principle of holism in NBS design and research suggests approaching NBS as elements in a landscape. Humans have distinct aesthetic stances towards landscapes, even those considered "wilderness", with many implications for policies (Saito, 2007). For example, controlled fires have been used over many centuries by North American native tribes to contain more catastrophic wildfires. These practices have been suppressed or forbidden by governments even in national parks because the results would no longer appear to be "scenic". With the spread of wildfires in recent times, authorities have recognized that native practices are a very effective means of protecting

forests and communities against the rampant wildfires caused by climate change (The Economist, n.d.).

The principle of holism also applies in the urban context, where the landscape needs to be designed for enhancing connectivities across places and buildings (LaPoint et al., 2015). Traditionally, green spaces were seen as confined to certain places in the city. To enhance biodiversity, connectivity requires arranging such green spaces as elements in the larger landscape which includes all kinds of green elements such as street trees or private gardens. In this case, property arrangements often become a hindrance because privately owned land is used according to the aesthetic preferences of the owners. Owners often have tastes that are not supportive of biodiversity and of creating potential for connectivities, such as preferring exotic plants over native plants or orderly lawns in their gardens. It is important to consider the diversity of Umwelts: For example, a lawn that is allowed to rewild may become a threatening “wilderness” for young children who play barefoot and may get hurt when stepping on a bee.

This analysis demonstrates that treating NBS solely as individual technical tools—such as considering trees only for their ability to lower temperatures in cities—can lead to policy failures. This issue begins with the technical challenge that planting trees only achieves the desired effects if the canopy is dense enough, which requires viewing urban greenery as part of a broader landscape design (Vuckovic et al., 2023). Additionally, when we factor in biodiversity, human aesthetics can create tensions among various goals (Liu and Slik, 2022). Landscape design can become a contentious issue, potentially leading to a backlash against NBS (Raymond et al., 2023a).

In summary, the coevolutionary approach to behaviour examines how individual patterns evolve alongside both the social and natural environments. For instance, when considering an NBS that creates an urban wetland, we would investigate how this NBS influences co-evolutionary dynamics in human communities. This includes exploring the emergence of new environmental values among groups, such as school children, and how these values impact their parents. Additionally, we would analyze the role of non-human species in fostering new shared habits, such as grassroots conservation activism, and how these developments may lead to the emergence of co-cultures.

3.1.2. Externalism and coevolutionary theory

Psychology and economics agree that an individual's inner states drive behavior, a concept known as "internalism" in the philosophy of science (Wilson, 2004). For instance, psychologists often view values as central to explaining various behavioral phenomena, believing that these values remain stable for individuals over longer periods. Economists use the term "preference" in a similar context. This understanding

is crucial for developing research strategies; the first step is to explore these individual states using standard methods like questionnaire surveys or qualitative interviews. However, research has consistently shown that there is no clear causal relationship between values as presumed inner states and observable behavior. For example:

- Manifest behaviour can differ from expressed values because of forces of conformity with peer group standards (Jans and Fielding, 2018).
- Framing effects determine how the situation is perceived in which the behaviour is expressed (Böhm and Tanner, 2018).
- Low- and high-cost settings have distinct effects on the expression of values (Bolderdijk et al., 2018).

Observations such as these strengthen the argument for externalism, which suggests that the behavioral drivers of individuals are primarily influenced by their environment—both past and present. Even if these drivers are currently internal, they often reflect past external factors, like socialization. The debate between externalism and internalism is significant for practical matters and policy decisions. For instance, when discussing addiction, an internalist perspective focuses on factors like brain dysfunctions or psychological aspects of self-control, while an externalist perspective emphasizes the importance of social context, peer influences, and historical socialization.

These discussions are also crucial for our topic of NBS. In essence, since NBS is part of the environment that influences human actions, it raises pertinent questions: How much does NBS itself contribute to altering behavioural drivers? Furthermore, do these changes in behaviour affect broader behavioural drivers in other contexts, thereby fostering forces of eco-social transformation across the board?

The co-evolutionary perspective addresses the divide between externalism and internalism by incorporating the principle of embodiment (Johnson, 2017) (section 1.3.3). Inner states both reflect and influence external states in the see-saw of inward and outward embodiment. In psychology, this perspective is aligned with ecological psychology, which intersects with enactivist approaches in cognitive sciences, albeit in different ways (Read and Szokolszky, 2020). Additionally, it closely aligns with the Umwelt concept introduced by von Uexküll. These ideas can be traced back further to

classical pragmatism, particularly to G. H. Mead, the founder of social psychology (Mead, 2015), and even to Hegel (Basso and Herrmann-Pillath, 2024). We do not confine the co-evolutionary approach to any single tradition. Instead, we emphasize that a co-evolutionary perspective on human behaviour begins by analyzing circuits of inner states, actions, and further inner states. Here, "action" encompasses the interactions that emerge, particularly in relation to other humans, thus forming the social Umwelt. This implies that we cannot identify any specific internal factors, such as values or beliefs, as the primary drivers of behaviour. Rather, we begin from these circuits, similar to the way ecological psychology examines circuits of sensation and action.

As discussed in the first chapter, our analytical framework focuses on habits, which are regular patterns of individual behaviour influenced by the environment (Klößner and Verplanken, 2018; Robbins and Costa, 2017). Researching habits can be challenging because it requires observing behaviour in context. Habits are often linked to environmental cues that can trigger a relapse, even when individuals intend to change their behaviour. These cues can be difficult to measure or identify (Lindenberg, 2018). Conversely, similar to the concept of nudging in behavioural economics, experimental tests of different cues can reveal effective strategies for changing habits. For instance, reducing the size of glasses and bottles has been shown to decrease the amount of liquid, such as soft drinks, that people consume habitually. Focusing on habits means that understanding motivation and behavioural change involves not only examining individuals' stated values and goals but also considering the external environment as a significant factor in decision-making and preferences. For research on NBS, this provides a theoretical basis for viewing the NBS itself as a locus of distributed agency (see box 3.3).

Box 3.3. Rainwater management and habits in cities of the Global South

An example of holistic NBS that involve a multi-dimensional change of habits is green water management in cities of the Global South (Diep et al., 2022). If NBS can cope with heavy rainfall and flooding, a network of small measures is necessary, such as rain gardens, permeable pavements, or rainwater harvesting. Given limited administrative and public resources, such measures require sustainable community engagement, hence habit formation that governs the use and maintenance of the various elements of the NBS.

One general issue is trust, since often the measures affect established claims on land plots, for example, inhabitants of informal dwelling fearing that some measures taken at spaces contiguous to their homes would signal future dispossession. There are many habits that need to adapt and influence the public acceptance of the NBS. For example, changing the landscape of the settlement in adding more gardens for public use would also open opportunities for children to play, which might also produce additional health ecosystem services. However, parents may be concerned about safety, for example, threats from animals such as snakes. In general, the aesthetics of the greenery plays a significant role in motivating people to take part in the NBS maintenance. That means that non-functional features may be crucial for habit formation, such as regular visits to places and engaging in maintenance activities.

The central role of habits highlights a significant connection between coevolution and semiotics. Behavioural patterns are fundamentally based on semiotic causality, as seen with habits, where environmental cues trigger specific habitual behaviours. In the following sections, we will emphasize how semiosis influences human behaviour in the context of NBS, with particular attention to interactions with non-human entities.

3.2. Ingroup / outgroup and the non-human “other”

3.2.1. Non-humans as outgroup

We begin by addressing a crucial issue regarding our relationship with non-human entities, which is extremely important for NBS. The distinction between ingroup and outgroup is one of the most significant aspects of human behaviour and has deep evolutionary roots (Bowles and Gintis, 2011). The divide between human and non-human species represents a profound ingroup/outgroup distinction that is deeply embedded in the Western tradition of Christianity and, more broadly, in the Abrahamic religions, combined with Cartesian thought stemming from the rise of modern science (Descola, 2011). This tradition forms the foundation of Western anthropocentrism and human exceptionalism. For instance, when comparing creation myths from Western civilization and those of Indigenous peoples, a key difference lies in the role of animals in the creation of the world and humanity (Kimmerer, 2020). In the Indigenous worldview, animals—and all living beings—are interconnected with humans through a unique form of spirituality and cosmology, which blurs the boundaries between humans and non-human species. In this perspective, following Haraway’s (Haraway,

2016) call to "make kin" with other species is a natural extension, while in the Western scientific view, it may sound like a metaphor without deeper ontological significance. These general observations matter because environmental psychology has shown that group processes and ingroup/outgroup borders deeply affect the expression of all other psychological factors that may drive pro-environmental behaviour (Jans and Fielding, 2018). The classic example is the entirely different treatment of pets and animals in meat factories. Pets are ingroup, and pigs in meat production are outgroup, even though pigs, in many respects, are similar to dogs as far as sentience and sociality are concerned. The same applies to the distinction between dogs as pets and stray dogs (box 3.2).

In general, the ingroup/outgroup distinction affects the following psychological factors in relating to other species.

First, empathy is strongly influenced by psychological mechanisms that determine how we include or exclude others, particularly in how we relate to non-human beings (Cikara et al., 2011; Young et al., 2018) (see chapter 2). This limitation can have devastating consequences, as evidenced by countless atrocities committed against those deemed "the other" throughout history. For instance, during the Rwandan genocide, viewing certain individuals as non-humans—such as comparing them to cockroaches—was a crucial factor in the dehumanization process. Thus, the way we empathize with others is deeply shaped by our perceptions of group inclusion and exclusion.

Secondly, empathy also influences the level of altruism we extend toward other beings. This is particularly relevant in the context of care, which is often regarded as a fundamental expression of bio- and ecocentric value shifts (Moriggi et al., 2020). It's essential to differentiate between general ecocentric beliefs—like broad attitudes toward nature—and our specific relationships with individual beings. While "nature" itself cannot be categorized as an ingroup, certain animals can be perceived as part of our group or as outsiders. Animals often viewed as dangerous or aesthetically displeasing are typically classified as outgroup members (see box 3.4).

Lastly, empathy affects our willingness to gather and assess information about other species. Typically, the information we receive about outgroups is filtered through a biased lens, often displaying negative perceptions.

Box 3.4. Slugs: The enemy number 1 in gardening

Proponents of deep eco-social transformation often highlight the importance of relationality and forming connections with all living beings. However, in practice, significant boundaries exist between humans and other species. One intriguing example relevant to urban gardening as a NBS is the issue of slugs (Ginn, 2014). In certain regions of Europe, particularly England, slugs are considered one of the most damaging pests in gardens. They consume large amounts of plant material in a short period, especially during the early growing season when plants are still young.

Figure 30: Slugs devouring salad

<https://www.gardensall.com/how-to-get-rid-of-garden-slugs/>

Fighting slugs is a common topic in gardening literature and even in local news, with many tips being repeated over the years. Gardeners often have a tense emotional relationship with slugs, which can include feelings of anger and even hatred. These emotions are heightened by the slugs' morphology; they lack limbs and cannot withdraw their heads, making them seem almost non-human. As a result, many gardeners refer to them as “monsters.”

The relationship with slugs is influenced not only by a calculation of costs and benefits but also by viewing them as an outgroup. This perception allows people to justify various forms of violence against them, even though many would prefer to use eco-friendly chemical substances that kill slugs without leaving traces, thereby making the act invisible. Caring tactics, such as collecting and relocating them, can be very time-

consuming, particularly in allotment gardens, where the only option may be to toss them into a neighbour's yard.

However, the 'slug drama' has a positive side. Research has shown that some gardeners do not feel comfortable with lethal methods of dealing with slugs. They may experience guilt or moral tension regarding their actions. Reflecting on these practices can lead to a more positive perspective on nature. This example illustrates how our embodied behaviors can become subjects of reflection and contribute to value formation. This topic is significant in chapter 4 when we consider criteria of multi-species justice and how the role of killing non-humans is seen in this context.

It is important to understand that the boundary between ingroups and outgroups does not align with the distinction between domesticated species and wild ones. This boundary is shaped by non-functional semiotic processes. For instance, individuals often personalize animals by naming them or tagging them. In the London Pollinator Project, participants learned to recognize specific bees that frequently visited their gardens, expressing concern when those bees did not return (Chittka, 2024, p. 278). As a result, they began to view these bees as friendly visitors, thus considering them part of the ingroup associated with their garden.

Box 3.5: The power of naming coevolvers

The naming of animals often evokes human affection and garners attention in the media. This effect is especially pronounced when the name highlights atypical animal behaviour. A notable example is Silvio, the pelican, from the Cagliari LL. Silvio attracts attention because, unlike other pelicans, he does not migrate with his flock. Instead, he stays at the Parco Molentargius Saline, the site of the Cagliari LL. His unusual behaviour sparks empathy, leading to concerns about his loneliness and lack of mating opportunities. Furthermore, this situation allows the public to learn about the ecological conditions in the park, such as the abundance of fish available.

Silvio nella garzaia. Foto: Filippo Melis

Figure 31: Silvio, the pelican

<https://www.vistanet.it/cagliari/2020/08/14/solitario-e-unico-come-silvio-storia-del-pellicano-che-ha-scelto-cagliari-come-casa>

Public attention is crucial for the work at the LL, as it helps engage stakeholders and fosters a sense of connection with the local ecosystem community. Animals like Silvio can become iconic figures, even if they are not original inhabitants of the area (see box 2.6). While this may be seen as anthropomorphizing, it is a nuanced perspective: Silvio demonstrates autonomous agency and creatively interacts with the opportunities presented by the park.

3.2.2. Making kin aka ingroup

What determines the boundary between ingroups and outgroups? A key finding in social psychology is that this boundary is arbitrary among humans (Brown, 2020). It is a purely semiotic construct and cannot be solely attributed to material interests, although this introduces an element of cultural opportunism. Importantly, this implies that the boundary can be defined in various ways, including the involvement of non-humans. The primary issue is how much humans identify with non-humans as part of an ingroup, particularly in the context of a multi-species community as conceptualized in an NBS framework.

The medium through which shifting boundaries can be organized is the arts in the broadest sense. This highlights the important role of artistic expression and creativity in CEA-NBS. Existing models, such as Haraway's science fiction that explores kinship through genetic merging between humans and non-humans, or Despret's work in

Therolinguistics (Despret, 2021) provide foundational ideas. However, these models are currently individualistic and do not focus on creating new more-than-human groups in practice. In the context of NBS, the primary challenge is to establish a more-than-human community.

Such an effort is a matter of both research and design. Since the border is arbitrary, it must be discovered and created at the same time via community actions. That means, the identification of an NBS community is a project of citizen art and science (box 3.6). The group boundaries cannot and should not be defined by the scientists, although scientists can positively contribute to raising awareness of the richness of the local NBS ecosystem. For example, scientists can show species that are invisible or even unknown to non-experts. The goal of art-based group-making is to trigger a long-term identification of humans with the local ecosystem so that all other mechanisms of fostering pro-environmental behaviour are now taking place in the in-group frame.

Box 3.6. Non-human Letter writing as co-creating community

Letter writing has been introduced in D 3.1 as a method to raise human awareness of non-human affordances. This approach can be expanded as a means of community formation. Various formats may be used, such as a writing competition for students. One variant might involve the local NBS community nominating a spiritual leader, similar to the role of hunting chiefs among North American native tribes. However, this leader initially lacks a community. To address this, individuals can write letters volunteering to become members of the community. In their letters, they introduce themselves, explain their needs and expectations for being part of the community, and outline what they can contribute. The unique aspect of this activity is that they adopt the perspective of non-humans. If framed as a writing competition, the call for submissions can encourage original and creative approaches that aim to identify unexpected and less familiar species. The more challenging the identification, the greater the recognition for the achievement. This activity explores the local ecosystem from a human perspective, which can provide valuable insights for engaging actively with the NBS. Simultaneously, it fosters community formation, as individuals demonstrate their ability to identify with non-humans and introduce them as community members. Researchers can learn from the outcomes, revealing blank spots in human perception of the NBS.

In conjunction with other methods and taking into account the diverse information gathered, the NBS community can engage in artistic projects that visualize “affordance mosaics.” These projects can depict the Umwelt of other species from their perspective. For example, they might collect and exhibit paintings (see Figure 32).

Figure 32: Affordance mosaic from Tartu LL: Umwelts of beavers, pendular tits and recreational fishermen

3.3. Framing

The ingroup/outgroup boundary is an example of how strong framing effects influence human cognition. Framing effects are widespread and can even impact fundamental differences between altruistic and self-interested values (Bowles and Polanía-Reyes, 2012).

In classical value theories, dualisms such as other-orientation versus self-orientation and collectivism versus individualism hold a foundational status. However, the link between these dualisms and behaviour is always mediated by how a situation is framed, such as whether it falls within the ingroup or outgroup context. In behavioural economics, a common framing effect involves whether a choice is presented in market versus non-market settings, accompanied by the distinction between pecuniary and non-pecuniary motivations. These effects have been empirically validated in many instances, beginning with the well-known Titmuss experiments on blood donations (Farrell, 2023). The general finding is that monetary incentives and intrinsic motivation do not always reinforce each other, even if they appear to support the same outcome. For instance, when intrinsic motivation is present, and a pecuniary incentive is added,

the desired behaviour may actually decrease. The Titmuss case illustrates this: offering payment for blood donations resulted in a reduction in donations.

Similar patterns have been observed in pro-environmental behaviour, particularly when examining the interconnectedness of various actions. For instance, a specific individual behaviour may be encouraged by financial incentives, but related civic engagement may decline as a result (Cinner et al., 2021; Ling and Xu, 2021). Framing effects demonstrate that values cannot be considered in isolation from their context. If individuals are intrinsically motivated to take a certain action based on their values, altering the framing may diminish the influence of those values or even render them irrelevant. Generally, shifting the focus to economic concerns can weaken an initial willingness to act based on intrinsic motives, instead reinforcing self-interest, even when the behaviour itself is not directly tied to financial aspects (Frey and Gallus, 2017). This is particularly relevant in the case of NBS, as arguments often emphasize their economic benefits, such as cost-effectiveness. While this claim may hold true and does not negate the other advantages of NBS, it shifts the frame, leading individuals to evaluate their actions primarily through an economic lens rather than considering other perspectives, such as biophilic values. These interdependencies are complex. Although the straightforward crowding out of intrinsic values is not always supported by empirical research (e.g., (Esteves-Sorenson and Broce, 2022)), there is substantial evidence suggesting that a combination of extrinsic and intrinsic motivations is most effective in fostering long-term pro-environmental behaviour (Silvi and Padilla, 2021). The intricacies of these issues are also acknowledged in literature on intrinsic motivation in management (Fishbach and Woolley, 2022) and neuropsychology (Morris et al., 2022).

For most researchers on NBS, fostering and sustaining intrinsic motivation, often dubbed “pro-environmental values”, is a key concern. Sociologists and philosophers have emphasized the crucial role of framing in order to foster cooperative and other-oriented actions in society (Sandel, 2013). This discussion connects with the topic of narratives, as narratives convey frames. However, while narratives operate on a cognitive level, frameshifts can be triggered by cues that often function subconsciously. In experimental psychology, this relates to the priming method, where

cues can significantly influence behaviour. For instance, studies show that exposure to money can shift motivational structures toward stronger individualism (Yang et al., 2013).

This analysis has important implications for NBS. A notable example is ecocompensation (Wang et al., 2022) (see box 1.13). Ecocompensation embodies the principle of reciprocity between people and nature; this means that if humans use a service provided by nature, they must give back. However, there are various ways to conceptualize reciprocity, with two prominent frames being the gift and the market. The market frame is prevalent in standard ecocompensation systems, such as carbon offsets, where individuals and organizations can purchase certificates to compensate for environmentally harmful actions. This form of reciprocity is disembodied and fails to create a closer relationship between people and nature (and even results in shifting ecological damage elsewhere, as in ecological load displacement, Jorgenson 2016). In fact, similar to medieval indulgences, it can be interpreted as paying for the right to engage in harmful actions, which can inadvertently legitimize those actions. This framing effect is well-known in other instances where sanctioning fees are perceived as prices for permission to engage in certain behaviours, ultimately lessening intrinsic moral constraints (Vohs, 2015). Conversely, when reciprocity is framed as a gift, the relationship is perceived as embodied, as the gift represents a shared identity (Hénaff, 2002). Consequently, the act of giving can only occur locally, within the community. This distinction has significant practical consequences, as ecocompensation should ideally be confined within the same spatial scope of the ecosystem.

This discussion mainly centers on the design of ecocompensation but also draws important conclusions about methods. Different disciplines employ monetary incentives and measurements in various approaches, such as experiments (Tyler and Amodio, 2015). If money has significant framing effects, it suggests that the methods themselves become performative, creating psychological impacts on the participants (see Box 3.7).

Box 3.7. Willingness to pay: disembodied and embodied modes

The distinction between two types of reciprocity has important methodological implications. One example is the widely used approach of asking individuals about their willingness to pay (WTP) for a specific ecosystem service provided by Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) (Viti et al., 2024). WTP can cause a frame shift, as people start to consider the ecosystem service within the context of their other spending behaviours in the marketplace. As discussed, environmental psychologists have documented that monetary incentives can significantly impact environmental behaviour, as the monetary frame diminishes the moral aspect and reduces intrinsic motivation (Bolderdijk et al., 2018). Thus, WTP can be problematic from the perspective of CEA-NBS. Additionally, WTP often correlates with income levels; typically, individuals with higher incomes exhibit a greater WTP. However, this may reflect a shift to a low-cost scenario: for those with higher incomes, a specific amount of money represents lower opportunity costs compared to lower-income individuals.

Despite these concerns, this method does not fully invalidate its use in CEA-NBS research. The standard application of WTP refers to money, which is a medium of disembodiment. We can consider embodied alternatives— for instance, asking how many hours or workdays people would be willing to contribute to an NBS project. In this case, the focus shifts to a gift mode of reciprocity, as voluntary work is more associated with non-market settings.

These insights are also relevant for policy design, particularly in supporting the implementation of NBS through various narratives. Different “NBS narratives” may emphasize distinct aspects, such as biodiversity or cost efficiency. These narratives create frames that can influence group behaviour. Several methods, such as role-playing board games (see boxes 1.1, 4.10), can help raise awareness of the effects of framing.

One significant effect of monetary framing is that it can cause people to change their attitudes across the entire value spectrum. At one end, there are sacred values that are non-negotiable and inalienable. At the other end, there are monetary values that suggest transactional considerations and imply substitutability. In between these extremes, there are other forms, such as lexicographic preference, which prioritize certain actions and choices (Basso and Herrmann-Pillath, 2024). Coevolutionary thinking indicates that this spectrum is influenced by the way values are represented, particularly in monetary terms. This representation has contributed to the many moral dilemmas associated with money throughout history (Walsh and Lynch, 2008). This observation is another demonstration of the normative nature of NBS research methods.

3.4. Co-evolutionary performativity of values

Values stay at the centre of a very comprehensive and detailed IPBES publication (Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, IPBES, 2022). This section will emphasize what distinguishes the coevolutionary approach from the findings in this report. First, we include non-human entities. Second, we adopt an embodied perspective. Third, we contextualize the issue within NBS. These differences have significant implications for our research methodology.

3.4.1. Values as reasons

The IPBES report emphasizes that the term "value" has multiple meanings. For our discussion, we can identify two primary interpretations that are common across many languages.

Firstly, a value can refer to an abstract principle that we consider fundamental in our lives, such as justice or human dignity.

Secondly, a value can signify what is important or beneficial to someone, depending on their purpose. This interpretation allows for numerous possibilities, and a critical question arises: what is the basis for this valuation?

For instance, I might value a forest for its importance to biodiversity, its positive impact on human health, or its potential as an economic resource. This distinction is crucial for working on NBS, as all these different valuations play a significant role in the sociopolitical processes that guide the design and implementation of NBS in public discussions.

This observation highlights a significant issue regarding values. Typically, values are examined through surveys about attitudes and behaviours, where the results are processed statistically to generate a list of values. This approach results in an abstract value construct created by the scientific observer, who projects these values onto a specific group. Simultaneously, group members may express certain values when asked to identify what is important to them. Both methods reflect conceptual

operations regarding values. For instance, individuals may claim to value nature and express a willingness to sacrifice personal benefits to protect it. Researchers might validate this through a construct of biocentrism derived from a questionnaire survey. However, there exists a "value-action gap," where people's behaviours do not align with their stated values.

Embodiment theory views this type of value research mainly as an exploration of the reflective operations that shape valuation processes, which are embodied and influenced by specific groups. Notably, research on moral behaviour indicates that most people respond intuitively to moral issues, offering value statements mainly as post-hoc rationalizations (Haidt, 2001). Therefore, when we discuss this issue through language, we focus more on the realm of providing and defending reasons rather than the actual mechanisms by which valuation and behaviour are formed (Mercier and Sperber, 2018).

This does not mean that values are unimportant; on the contrary, they play a significant role. However, the coevolutionary perspective does not view values as primary factors in explaining behaviour. Instead, values influence behaviour indirectly in several ways. One key way is through self-categorization and the expression of identity, which applies both at the individual and group levels (Ariccio and Mosca, 2023). This is particularly evident in political debates, such as those seen in the American culture wars. Additionally, values are relevant in local contexts, especially regarding NBS. Various stakeholders involved in an NBS may reference their values to position themselves within public discourse, whether as environmental advocates or as responsible businesspeople who prioritize both sustainability and job creation.

Another significant way values impact individuals is by filtering and shaping the information they receive; in some cases, values can even prevent certain information from being acknowledged. Furthermore, values contribute to the dynamics of ingroup and outgroup boundaries. In this context, values become intertwined with group identity, making them more entrenched and potentially hindering understanding and cooperation between different groups.

Since values are reasons, this perspective can be extended to non-humans. As we will discuss in the next chapter, non-humans cannot articulate their values in language

but in actions. So, they cannot give reasons. Yet, the capability approach and the affordance concept introduced previously imply that non-humans have values in the methodological sense championed here, namely as constructs of the scientific observer who extracts values from diverse data sources such as surveys. This also allows for extending the perspective to citizen science when it comes to non-humans (box 3.8).

Box 3.8.: Performing non-human values in NBS

More-than-human intervision is a reasoning method that includes non-human perspectives in problem-solving discussions. The process involves a structured discussion with a strict time schedule, where each participant's contribution is limited to a fixed time slot, such as three minutes.

In this approach, participants take on different roles. Some may represent their actual positions, like an administrator, while others assume the roles of non-human entities. This procedure builds on previous activities that familiarize participants with NBS, the environment, and the non-human species present in it. The discussion begins with one participant acting as the “problem owner,” identifying a specific issue in the design and implementation of the NBS. Following this, there is a round for clarification questions from other participants to gather background information.

Next, participants reflect on the identified problem and explore potential solutions. After this reflection, the problem owner responds to the ideas presented. The session then concludes with a brainstorming session on lessons learned, focusing on key questions such as the importance of the problem for different participants, their evaluations of alternative solutions, and how these solutions may enhance well-being.

The procedure continues with each participant taking a turn as the problem owner. At the end of the session, participants reflect on their various roles and the impact these roles had on their perspectives regarding the problem and the valuation of solutions. They also discuss the hierarchy of values, particularly which aspects are non-negotiable when considering trade-offs among different solutions.

Source: <https://www.reimaginary.com/methods/more-than-human-intervision>

3.4.2. Embodied values

When we think about values primarily in terms of reflection and discussion, what does embodiment mean? We do not claim that values, formed through reflection, are embodied, but rather the processes that underlie valuation are. In the context of NBS, there are three particularly significant types of dynamic embodiment.

To build on the themes discussed in the previous section, language serves as a medium of embodiment (see box 2.2). For example, consider the term “nature” in a

value survey. Many people associate “nature” with positive feelings, which can influence their responses. However, researchers may not know the specific values that shape these responses. Just like in the previous example with slugs—while they are also part of nature, they are often viewed negatively, evoking feelings of disgust. Words carry connotations that reflect these embodied valuations. For instance, “nature” and “wilderness” can evoke different emotions in different people. While “wilderness” may remind some of joyful outdoor activities, others might associate it with danger and death (Van Den Berg and Konijnendijk, 2018). These different interpretations reflect framing effects, which relates to embodied valuations. To account for this, surveys and interviews should implement linguistic triangulation. This means covering similar topics with sets of questions that use varied wording, such as “nature” and “wilderness.” An ecolinguistic analysis can uncover deeper meanings in respondents' answers.

The second mode of embodied valuation focuses on the interaction between the material environment and behaviour, connecting valuation to the concept of affordance. The entire construction of Umwelt can be understood as a reflection of embodied valuation, where what is considered an affordance is what is valued. One of the most significant aspects of embodied valuation is habit, which we introduced as a basic concept of CEA-NBS in Chapter 1. Habits are often seen as a major barrier to pro-environmental behaviour. People may rationally support certain measures and values but fail to act on them, which helps explain the value-action gap. However, this view tends to overlook the crucial role of embodiment in the valuation process and tends to frame habits negatively, portraying them as obstacles to realizing values. In reality, habits are a fundamental form of embodied valuation. They are shaped by past experiences and are usually rooted in positive valuations, even though negative habits, such as addiction, also exist. Thus, habits serve as a critical instrumental category in CEA-NBS (Linder et al., 2022).

Changing habits requires a transformation of both the physical environment and individual behaviors. Therefore, the design of a NBS is essential for encouraging behaviours that contribute to its sustainability and scalability. The ecosemiotic approach, as previously discussed, highlights the importance of semiotic co-option.

This refers to the connections between signs and two different interpretants, whose actions create interconnected habits that embody distinct yet complementary values. This relates to a debate in the theory of the arts whether aesthetic criteria are purely arbitrary and determined by social and cultural contexts, or whether there are “natural” criteria in the sense that humans may even share certain aesthetic predilections with non-humans because of a shared phylogeny (Davies, 2016). The latter possibility, as in the case of flowers, pollinators, birds and humans, suggests a possible convergence on biophilic design (box 3.9).

Box 3.9. Biophilic design and embodied valuation

An important finding in environmental psychology is that humans have an embodied appreciation for natural patterns. Empirical evidence supports this, showing both the positive health effects of biodiversity and the benefits of connecting with nature. However, there can also be negative effects, such as allergic reactions for some individuals (Marselle et al., 2021). Interestingly, these preferences extend to architectural design. Research on restorative environments reveals that people value statistical fractal patterns, such as the view of a tree canopy in a forest. This insight encourages the incorporation of urban greenery, such as green walls, and suggests the potential for using biomimicry in architecture (Joye, 2007). For example, gothic architecture often features intricate patterns that create opportunities for hybrid designs, enhancing human well-being while providing spaces for non-human inhabitants. Buildings adorned with rich ornaments, turrets, and cavities can offer resting and nesting spots, especially when combined with vertical greenery. However, research indicates that vertical greenery does not necessarily promote greater biodiversity compared to structures with more varied designs (Belcher et al., 2018). This observation highlights the concept of semiotic co-option in valuation: it is the living beings that incorporate human-built structures into their environment, thereby transforming it into "nature."

[https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Ornament_with_Thistle_\(Gothic_Thistle\).jpg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Ornament_with_Thistle_(Gothic_Thistle).jpg)

Figure 33: Gothic ornament with thistle

The third form of embodiment occurs within institutions, including social norms. Institutions have been shaped over time through societal conflicts, negotiations, and powerful interventions. They encompass various incentives and sanctions, as well as cues that guide behavioral expressions. In Chapter 1, we assigned the concept of institutions to the human domain. Most theories related to institutions are disembodied, with economics particularly emphasizing abstraction (Hayek, 1989; North, 1990). However, pragmatist economists have always stressed the internalization of institutions, linking them closely to habits (the classic example being Veblen, 2009/1899; see also Hodgson, 2004).

There are disembodied interpretations of this internalization perspective that connect institutions to “mental models” and cognitive states (North, 2005). Embodied views, on the other hand, begin by considering the role of material representations as a form of informational compression, suggesting a semiotic interpretation (Aoki, 2011; Herrmann-Pillath, 2013). In these views, institutions are embodied in signs that correspond with inner emotional states, such as the signs of police authority that evoke feelings of respect or even fear. We cannot explore this complex theme in detail here, but we will pursue it further in the next chapter when discussing embodied forms of governance.

Embodiment has significant implications, indicating that both material and institutional embodiment can include non-human values, potentially fostering the embodiment of these values in humans, regardless of whether humans consciously endorse them. An important example of this is the institutional rights granted for accessing and using certain animals, a practice commonly seen in conservation and restoration efforts, which is legally similar to easements (Box 3.10).

Box 3.10. Contested spaces and more-than-human institutions bottom-up

All nature-based solutions (NBS) require space, which can lead to conflicts over that space. Human territoriality, as reflected in property institutions, asserts absolute control over land (Vanuxem, 2022). This means that humans have the right to manage and manipulate all living beings within their territory. However, in practice, people typically only exercise these rights when they feel threatened, such as when dealing with invasive “weeds” on their sidewalks.

This raises complex issues with NBS, which aim to enhance biodiversity. The question arises: is this biodiversity only permitted if it aligns with human interests, or must we also accept uncontrolled developments that might conflict with those interests? These dilemmas frequently occur. For example, nature protection laws often create easements for the benefit of non-human species, particularly endangered ones. Protected birds might build nests in locations that are inconvenient for humans, leading to situations where human interests are at odds with those of the birds (Meijer, 2019). Such conflicts can even delay construction projects, generating significant backlash against green policies. Protected birds might build nests in locations that are inconvenient for humans, leading to situations where human interests are at odds with those of the birds (Meijer, 2019). Such conflicts can even delay construction projects, generating significant backlash against green policies. To mitigate these negative outcomes, it is crucial for institutions to develop from the ground up, rooted in cooperative habits among both humans and non-humans. In the bird nesting example, local communities can work together to provide suitable nesting opportunities in locations that reduce potential conflicts. They can also take preventive measures to deter birds from choosing problematic sites. Making these efforts visible, such as through signs indicating nesting locations, can help.

This principle also applies to larger-scale issues, such as when migratory geese unexpectedly choose agricultural fields as temporary resting spots and cause damage to crops (Hiedanpää et al., 2023a). In response, humans often react aggressively towards these intruding animals. A more constructive approach would involve scaring geese away from human-used areas while providing alternative spaces, such as designated fields for geese. Ideally, such initiatives should stem from grassroots efforts, with administrative measures playing a supportive role.

Through these activities, humans can express their value conflicts, as many people feel empathy for birds in need of rest after long migrations. Institutions developed at the grassroots level can embody both human and non-human values effectively.

Figure 33: Institutionalizing easements for geese (foto: Jukka T. Forsman)

3.5. Practices as methodological pivots

In the introduction, we argue that adopting a coevolutionary approach helps avoid individualistic reductionism. This perspective has significant implications for research strategies. To understand the behavioural drives, valuations, and beliefs that people hold, we should focus on practices rather than individuals. Practices involve multiple elements; even when centering on one individual, aspects of the environment—such as affordances—and often other people are engaged.

There are various ways to study practices. Typically, this requires qualitative, in-depth research with a strong interpretive approach. However, even in quantitative surveys, there are multiple ways to operationalize practices. A key example of this is the use of vignettes, which connect to storytelling methods (Aarons, 2021, p. 159f). In qualitative research, vignettes have become a powerful tool for understanding interactions between humans and non-humans.

In quantitative research, a vignette is a simple narrative followed by a set of statements or questions that respondents can easily answer, facilitating straightforward quantitative analysis. In NBS research, vignettes can draw on highly personalized storytelling. For instance, a person might recount an encounter with an unfamiliar animal attracted by an NBS, detailing their feelings and reactions. This story can be

transformed into a vignette, followed by questions about what respondents might feel or do in a similar situation, or how local authorities should respond to the presence of unfamiliar animals, such as predators. The key point is that even within a survey context, the vignette not only encourages reflective thinking but also evokes memories, associations, and emotions in respondents, which in turn shape their answers.

Box 3.11. Vignettes as diffractive method in Umwelt analysis

In quantitative research, vignettes are primarily used to gather data reflecting certain feelings and beliefs of respondents. In qualitative research, however, vignettes can be utilized in a more nuanced manner, following Haraway's and Barad's (Barad, 2018) concept of "diffraction", which is particularly effective in analyzing diverse Umwelts (Jenkins et al., 2021). The physical phenomenon of wave diffraction is a metaphor for projecting a phenomenon in different worlds. In a study examining dog-human relationships in dementia treatment, Jenkins et al. suggest that vignettes can reveal the various ways dementia dogs interact with their owners, highlighting how these interactions lead to the co-creation of unique co-cultures between the two partners. These co-cultures are influenced by the individual characteristics of both humans and dogs. While traditional views often position dementia dogs merely as helpers or "prosthetics" (Callon, 2008), the diffractive perspective recognizes dogs as having their own agency. This agency allows for a greater variety of outcomes in dog-human interactions.

This intra-action viewpoint aligns with theories of *agencement* in Actor-Network Theory (ANT), particularly as discussed by Callon (Callon, 1986). Vignettes enable researchers to understand the performative multiplicity of relationships (i.e., diffraction). Jenkins et al. categorize these relationships into three alternative patterns: antibiosis, commensalism, and mutualism. The first pattern, antibiosis, is described as "counterperformative," meaning that the dog's presence can produce effects contrary to the original intentions. In contrast, mutualism represents a genuine form of cohabitation grounded in shared feelings.

Vignettes offer significant interpretive freedom, thereby mimicking performative processes in real life. In qualitative research, this approach facilitates a deeper understanding of human/non-human interactions, such as the moral dilemmas illustrated in previous examples. In quantitative research, methods like the Q-method (Zabala et al., 2018) make performative effects visible.

Ethnographic methods are often time-consuming and may not be feasible for a NBS project. However, there are alternative approaches, such as context-based interviews or walking interviews. Walking interviews allow participants to engage with their environment, which influences their responses by introducing subconscious cues. Additionally, interviewers can listen to respondents while observing their body language in an environmentally contextualized setting (see Box 3.12 for details).

Box 3.12. Exploring non-human values: owls and people

Returning to our study of owls, research indicates that formalized training and expert investigations often overlook the diverse valuations, expressions, and behaviors of these birds, particularly at an individual level (Ackerman, 2023). Valuable insights frequently emerge from collaborations between researchers and local citizens, especially those with transdisciplinary expertise, such as bird watchers. A particularly effective method for tapping into this shared knowledge is conducting walking interviews with engaged individuals (Parkwer et al., 2024). This approach is especially fruitful when examining the interactions between humans and owls and the embodied values that arise from these encounters. For instance, informed citizens are often more adept than formal researchers at recognizing and interpreting the emotional expressions of owls, especially in relation to specific events they have witnessed, such as chicken deaths caused by accidents or predators. They may also observe and interpret vocalizations of grief over extended periods. Furthermore, these citizens tend to be more attuned to the distinct and varied vocalizations of owls.

Another area where informed citizens' insights can be particularly valuable is in understanding innovative and playful behaviors. With more time to spend observing and a natural curiosity about owls' unusual antics, they can reveal how these birds respond to changing environments. Citizens can also closely monitor owls' preferences, which can significantly impact mating behaviour and, consequently, reproduction. For example, owls may have specific preferences for the shapes of branches they use, and this knowledge can inform artificial interventions to create suitable habitats elsewhere.

Practices involve patterns of interaction between humans and non-humans, so we need to use methods that move beyond viewing humans solely as agents. This understanding is particularly evident in the context of play between humans and non-humans, where the agency of non-humans is clearly recognized. Therefore, it is important to adopt the metaphor of play as a methodological principle in practice research related to CEA-NBS. This metaphor suggests that we should view all interactions between humans and non-humans as having the potential for novelty and surprise, as well as the sharing of positive emotions. This includes emotions that arise from restraint, even in situations involving potentially dangerous acts, such as in animal play, where perilous behaviors are displayed without participants exploiting these behaviours.

One approach to exploring this is through meta-play, where humans engage in playing as non-humans. Specifically, meta-play can facilitate the creation of rituals that embody and enact shared values among both humans and non-humans (for more detail, see chapter 4, section 4.3.3.). Ritual behaviour is a fundamental pattern that is

common to both groups and serves as a medium for expressing non-negotiable values. We will delve deeper into this in the next section, but here we want to emphasize the role of rituals among humans in establishing understanding and empathy towards non-human perspectives. This connection is especially highlighted in the context of Indigenous rituals, which serve as a way to connect with other beings (Kimmerer, 2020).

Box 3.13. Meta-play and the creation of rituals

The creation of rituals has become an essential tool in eco-social transformation. Rituals can be integrated as a regular component of formal meetings within NBS, such as when stakeholders convene to discuss specific decisions. This practice extends beyond community levels and is even adopted in United Nations meetings (Chamel, 2022). Creating new rituals involves a collaborative exploration stage, where participants agree on a specific schedule for these rituals. Literature on this topic provides valuable guidance (Gordon-Lennox, 2017). Participants will identify a shared motivation for developing the ritual, which should blend cognitive and emotional elements relevant to the occasion. They can then brainstorm various forms of rituals, which can be diverse—for instance, singing a song or performing a short dance.

A contemporary requirement for these rituals is that they must be inclusive of non-human entities. Participants should start by reflecting on the NBS and consider which species are vital for the ecosystem community to engage with ritually. This could be informed by the iconic species approach (see Box 2.6). For example, if choosing to incorporate a song, they might draw inspiration from Indigenous spirituality, which includes non-human vocalizations, as seen in some forms of Sami music (Aubinet, 2020; Ullrich and Trump, 2022). Similarly, they might incorporate non-human-like movements into their ritual dance (see Figure 34).

Figure 34: Being a mushroom: Humans connecting like mycelium

The key point is that when humans adopt behavioral patterns from non-humans, they don't merely express their imagination about these creatures; they actually experience feelings akin to those of a non-human. For instance, in a NBS ritual related to gardening,

individuals might perform a harvesting ceremony that involves mimicking the movements of earthworms. This could require them to lie on the ground, keep their limbs close to their bodies without moving, and crawl according to a set ritual script. Additionally, rituals can serve as a form of storytelling when they connect with a "myth" surrounding the non-human beings.

See <https://hellobrink.co/what-is-the-role-of-ritual-in-building-resilient-communities/>

Chapter 4: More-than-human politics in a multi-species community

4.0. Chapter summary

1. Sociopolitics in a multispecies community requires the inclusion of other species' voices. This means conceptualizing politics as a struggle for recognition in which nature-based governance emerges as a regulating framework that is accepted by a majority of community members and continues to be open to revision: this is multi-species democracy.
2. Recognition presupposes eschewing human language as the prime medium of deliberation and recognizing action as a semiotic medium in which claims are communicated and negotiated. Nature-based governance grounds in embodied deliberation.
3. Embodied deliberation unfolds in the learning multi-species demos. Voting with the feet is a basic mechanism for establishing freedom in a multi-species democracy: A multi-species democracy is without borders (such as including migratory species). The procedures of multi-species democracy are collaborative experimentation (co-creation).
4. Affordancing is a basic form of co-creative action in the multispecies democracy which follows the logic of exaptation. Humans create novel affordances and recognize the free responses of other species. Affordancing is political aesthetics.
5. Stakeholder analysis is a critical method for preparing the ground for multi-species politics. Standard methods, such as ecological sciences, can identify passive stakeholders. Active stakeholders express themselves in actions that are neutral across species. Hence, stakeholder analysis is Umwelt analysis as more-than-human political science.
6. Stake specificity creates vulnerabilities. Typically, vulnerabilities are asymmetrically distributed in favour of humans relative to other ecosystem members. Often, vulnerable humans share similar positions like other species (for example, regarding urban greenery, children and animals both enjoy the benefits of greenery and have less alternatives). Stewardship is a crucial means of stakeholder representation.
7. A key issue is the differentiating between legitimate and illegitimate stakes, which is a central theme in the struggle for recognition. Designing governance mechanisms for recognizing and involving stakeholders is encumbered by the complexity of various goals that representatives pursue (for example, a municipal tourist agency may have a stake in greenery, but only in relation to the goal of attracting tourists).
8. Nature-based governance (NBG) has two aspects. One relates to embodied mechanisms of regulating behaviours, habits on the individual level and routines on the organizational level. The other is governance by nature, in the sense of recognizing deontological powers of natural processes. Hence, NBG is defined as: Nature-based governance grounds governance mechanisms in embodied more-than-human practices with normative force.
9. Multi-species justice involves both human/other species relations specifically and species/species relations in general. In a multi-species NBS community, humans have the ethical responsibility to act as impartial judges in regulating interspecies relations.

4.1. Principles of multi-species democracy

This chapter, like the previous ones, examines the sociopolitics of NBS from a specific perspective: what methods can help us understand and engage in sociopolitics within a multi-species community? Traditionally, sociopolitics has been viewed primarily from a human-centric lens, focusing on various interests, their interactions, and issues of justice. For instance, much research on environmental justice centers on humans, particularly vulnerable groups, both locally and globally (Mohai et al., 2009; Risse, 2012). While there is a wealth of literature on this topic, we cannot cover it all in this chapter. Our primary focus is on the inclusion of non-humans in political and social contexts largely dominated by humans (Celermajer et al., 2021). This topic is also mostly neglected in the literature on environmental justice in NBS, with rare exceptions that introduce a more general notion of inclusive “ecological justice” (Pineda-Pinto et al., 2022).

This discussion also touches on vulnerable human groups, as their marginalization often mirrors the exclusion faced by non-humans in political processes (see the example of street dogs, box 3.1.). In the animal rights literature, it has frequently been noted that young children and animals experience similar forms of exclusion, due to a lack of language proficiency and reasoning capacity (Deckha, 2021). However, as we will argue, the emphasis on capacity hides the fact that often the real issue is recognizing the languages of others in political processes, and not their alleged incapacity. This is often recognized for vulnerable and marginalized groups with different views of the “nature” in the NBS and diverse ways of relating to it (Tozer et al., 2020).

This approach does not mean that we do not consider more conventional topics of sociopolitics. A key example is stakeholder analysis: Investigating non-humans as stakeholders presupposes an overview of all relevant stakeholders in an NBS. Similarly, the inclusion of non-humans is shaped by structural features of human community politics and administration. We cover this aspect in investigating the forms of governance in NBS.

4.1.1. Politics as struggle for recognition

When exploring the relationship between politics and society, we begin by recognizing politics as the primary domain. Politics shapes and stabilizes the power structures inherent in society and its practices (Bourdieu, 2019). For instance, the marginalization of vulnerable groups reflects these power structures, which politics can both reproduce and change. This aligns with the perspective that society should be organized around democratic principles, with the goal of achieving justice through inclusive and participatory mechanisms (Sen, 2009). These mechanisms are essential components of politics.

In considering non-humans, the analysis must start by examining the relationship between humans and non-humans as a power structure. In the context of NBS, this perspective is often implicit in the engineering approach, which assumes that humans are in control of NBS. However, the co-evolutionary approach suggests a more political dimension, allowing non-humans to influence the evolution of an NBS beyond human control. For example, when considering an urban forest, this view prompts questions about the extent to which the area can be rewilded. It challenges humans to accept the presence of other living beings, even those they may not favour, which might encroach on private gardens. The political nature of NBS is highlighted by the prioritization of human interests, which, in cases of conflict, position humans as the ultimate decision-makers in resolving disputes. Hence, engineering the NBS is a form of governing non-humans, and not just a technological fix.

The baseline for politics in the context of the CEA-NBS is rooted in the concept of recognition and the struggle for it. The underlying issue of asymmetric power arises from a lack of recognition (Honneth, 2005). Recognition involves acknowledging the interests, needs, beliefs, or emotional concerns of others and granting them the same legitimacy and authority to be expressed and pursued as one's own. This recognition is essential for all specific forms of implementing NBS (Kortetmäki et al., 2023). Politics fundamentally revolves around the struggle for recognition. This insight leads to a vital distinction between politics within established institutional frameworks, such as conflict

resolution, representation, and interest negotiation, and political activity that occurs outside of these frameworks (Chambers, 2011; Rancière, 2004). Recognition entails that an individual or group is accepted as a participant in the former, while the struggle for recognition unfolds in the broader social domain.

What implications does this have for the concept of a multi-species society? To address this question, we need to differentiate between the classical notions of "society" and "community." In Tönnies' original framework, society refers to a realm of abstract relationships, primarily governed by economic exchanges, whereas community is characterized by concrete, emotionally grounded relationships (Herrmann-Pillath, 2023a). A key question regarding multispecies politics in relation to NBS is how the societal struggle for recognition (such as political conflicts over the selection and design of NBS) contributes to the development of NBS as a community or embeds them within an existing community (Gulsrud et al., 2018; Raymond et al., 2023). "Society" and "community" differ fundamentally in terms of available mechanisms of inclusion, with society being mainly focused on disembodied forms, and community on embodied ones (Basso and Herrmann-Pillath, 2024).

Box 4.1. More-than-human placemaking and the struggle for recognition

A notable example of community building in the context of NBS is the challenge of gaining recognition for these initiatives. Depending on their scope and size, NBS can lead to structural and institutional changes that alter the relationship between people and places (Raymond et al., 2023b). The concept of "place" can also imply a resistance to change, a phenomenon often seen through the NIMBY (Not In My Backyard) effect, which is frequently institutionalized through property rights. For instance, planting trees on a sufficient scale to mitigate heat waves in urban areas may require collaboration with private garden owners or may face opposition from those living near new trees, as their presence can block light from windows. While participatory planning is seen as a potential solution, it may not resolve existing political stalemates (Toxopeus et al., 2020). Challenges abound, starting with a lack of trust in the planning process, which can lead to citizen passivity.

A key principle follows the method of diffraction introduced earlier: viewing an NBS as open to multiple interpretations from various groups, including non-human species, thus fostering an ongoing process of community formation. NBS invoke diverse "Umwelts," or lived environments, not only for non-humans but also for humans. Therefore, analyzing these Umwelts is crucial for understanding how an NBS functions in relation to different community groups, such as vulnerable populations versus high-income earners, and their unique interactions with urban greenery.

A case study from Shenzhen, China, illustrates how distinct features of urban greenery are strongly influenced by community identity politics and demographic composition, resulting in specific forms of green gentrification (Herrmann-Pillath et al., 2024). Although migrant workers make up the majority of the population, they often lack a direct voice in decisions regarding urban greenery. In contrast, local natives, who are the original landowners, have become wealthy through real estate and have relocated to condominiums with picturesque natural views, while in other areas, trees are removed for urban redevelopment. In a recent development, one of the communities which features a dense street greenery with old trees decided to cut 50 percent of the trees because the early morning bird songs were perceived as “noise”. Inclusive community management can backfire if the voices of non-humans remain excluded, since community leaders and municipality have promoted the green image of the community for long.

4.1.2. Beyond human language: Embodied deliberation

The multi-species society is a landscape for the struggle for recognition that takes place within existing power structures, where humans dominate non-humans. This makes the multi-species society inherently political. However, this political dimension is rarely acknowledged, as many people believe that a shared language—a crucial element for politics, especially in a democratic setting—is lacking in this context (Meijer, 2019). Often, the absence of recognition manifests as discrimination against the languages of others, with the assumption that certain beings lack the ability to communicate effectively and, therefore, cannot engage in public debate and decision-making. This argument is particularly relevant for non-humans, who are often defined by their perceived lack of language, with the criteria for linguistic capacity being human-centric. Thus, denying language to non-humans is a clear expression of power dynamics. As we have seen, if we distinguish between the multi-species society and the multi-species community we can possibly change this power dynamics because community implies embodied forms of interaction and communication

An alternative perspective on politics aligns with the ecosemiotic approach discussed in this report: we can view actions as a form of language (see section 2.3.4). In this semiotic framework, meaning arises from interpretation and does not rely solely on human language. In the discourse surrounding animal languages, this perspective could be misconstrued as merely recognizing animal signs as natural indicators, while still denying these beings their linguistic agency (Bar-On and Moore, 2017). For instance, humans may interpret rising temperatures as evidence of human-induced

climate change, thus feeling compelled to act responsibly. Similarly, animal behaviour, such as predators encroaching on human habitats in search of food due to habitat degradation, can also be seen as a natural sign. Recognizing animal behaviour as a natural sign is a crucial first step in acknowledging other beings; as discussed in section 4.2, this implies recognizing non-humans as passive stakeholders in NBS.

However, we can and must extend this idea further. Viewing animal behaviour merely as a natural sign overlooks the agency of these beings in using behaviour as a sign. In chapter 2, we noted that a key assumption in ecosemiotics is that human language is just one kind of semiosis with agency among other kinds. This perspective allows us to consider human language as embodied action, enabling a broader recognition of linguistic agency in other species beyond humans. By approaching human language as an action grounded in embodied meanings, we can begin to see animal signs as a different but structurally similar form of language that serves similar functions (Bar-On, 2018). This philosophical viewpoint can be supported by adopting the "intentional stance" of humans, a concept essential for constructing a social ontology independent of naturalistic viewpoints (Dennett, 1998). This means, we need to distinguish neatly between two analytical approaches:

- One is mostly dominant in discussing animal languages which emphasizes the naturalistic dimension in terms of capacities for language and factual linguistic behaviour of non-humans
- The other is to highlight the constructivist dimension of humans "making others speak" in terms of adopting the intentional stance to them and hence recognizing their signs as language, which is empirically salient in the diverse forms of Indigenous spirituality, among others.

Interestingly, neuroscientific research has cast doubt on the traditional understanding of human agency, such as the idea of free will (Ross et al., 2007). We might consider humans, like non-humans, as neurophysiological entities that generate behaviour without a "ghost in the machine." In this context, agency develops within societies where cooperation necessitates the assignment of agency in social ontology (Searle, 2011; Tuomela, 2013). With this understanding, there are no fundamental distinctions between human and non-human agency as both can be recognized in the human

social construction of agency. This construct resembles the institutional concept of legal personhood: a corporation is recognized as a legal person but, in a naturalistic sense, lacks agency. Nonetheless, legal persons are perceived as political actors, for instance, in lobbying efforts (though not as voters). The recognition of agency does not require the naturalistic capacity of agency. This conclusion also applies for language: Corporations do not have the naturalistic capacity to speak, but nonetheless we listen to their messages often without recognizable human authors.

If we embrace this conceptual shift, we can consider politics in a multi-species society as a form of deliberation through embodied communication that transcends human language in their naturalistic sense but is being recognized and constructed as “language”. Acknowledging non-human signs as a form of communication functionally similar to language is a vital step in the fight for recognition and establishes the foundation for multi-species justice. For humans, this requires a willingness to listen to non-human expressions and to engage in co-operative communication (see box 4.2).

Box 4.2: Deliberating with cows

Recent developments in high-tech agriculture have resulted in mixed outcomes regarding animal welfare. One well-documented example is the use of milking robots (Driessen and Heutinck, 2015). These robots were initially promoted as providing cows with greater individual freedom by allowing them to decide when to be milked. However, the practical results have been varied; many cows require significant encouragement or even coercion to use the robots. For instance, guardrails were often installed, and robots were positioned to block access to feeding areas, forcing cows to cross over the robots to get milked first. Unfortunately, these methods have proven less effective than allowing cows true free choice.

Interestingly, early adopters of this technology were often farmers who viewed cows merely as machines for milk production. These farmers struggled more with implementing the technology than traditional farmers who had a more caring approach and took the time to teach their cows how to use the robots. This suggests that cows engaged in an ongoing communication with the farmers through their behaviour, shaping the process of technology adoption. There was also a notable degree of individual variation in how different cows responded to the robots. One point raised in the discussion was that cows were no longer treated in a species-specific manner. Traditional milking involved regular, communal sessions, while the new system transformed cows into "neoliberal subjects," emphasizing individual choice. Cows responded in creative ways, such as forming smaller groups of peers to approach the robots together. The presence of robots also triggered other social dynamics, such as dominance hierarchies for first access.

Overall, the introduction of milking robots marks a shift towards husbandry practices in which both cows and farmers can explore various approaches, and the cows' actions are seen as a form of expressed opinion in an ongoing process of deliberation about the ways how to deploy the new technology.

In practice, there are two primary approaches to recognizing non-hum communication as “language”. The first approach assumes that all humans have the capacity to understand and respond to non-human signs through the intentional stance. Although this view is often criticized as anthropocentric, as we discussed in Chapter 1, the intentional stance can be grounded in shared understandings of capabilities and functions. A key example of this recognition is found in Indigenous spirituality.

The second approach involves the use of interpreters and translators, similar to their role in facilitating communication between speakers of different human languages. This method follows an institutional model of representation for legal entities or individuals who may lack certain communicative abilities, like young children. However, the role of the interpreter is even more limited in this context, as they are not a legal representative. Instead, the non-humans still speak for themselves, and the interpreter's job is to translate the meaning of the message. The interpreter is required to adhere closely to the intended meaning that emerges from adopting the intentional stance. We will explore this topic in more detail in the next section.

4.1.3. The learning multi-species demos

The recognition of non-human languages allows non-humans to participate in a deliberative process within a multispecies society. This shift transforms the extra-political into the intra-political, necessitating institutionalization. The traditional understanding of politics poses an obstacle to this transformation. However, we have already introduced a solution in section 1.5.2. Instead of viewing democracy solely as public deliberation and formal collective decision-making, we adopt the Deweyian perspective of democracy as experimentation. In this context, communication occurs primarily through actions: humans take actions, and non-humans respond with their own actions, necessitating a translation for political processes.

From the human perspective, explaining our actions to non-humans is familiar in interactions with domesticated animals and pets (Mondémé, 2018). Humans often communicate with non-humans as if they could understand human language. While this is sometimes the case due to mutual learning, it is essential to recognize that non-verbal communication can serve as an effective means of explaining human actions, such as via eye-contact (Savalli et al., 2016). However, the challenge arises from the fact that human non-verbal communication often follows different rules. For example, smiling may convey friendliness among humans, but showing teeth can signify a threat to non-humans. Thus, humans must learn to "speak" the language of non-humans or develop a sort of universal grammar that is, however, limited in scope (depending on the degree of how far the human and non-human Umwelts overlap). In fact, even among humans, smiling is a complex behaviour with diverse meanings and often not directly linked to expressions of intentions, but guided by social conventions (Dixon, 2023, p. 76ff).

To understand non-human actions, humans must build on existing knowledge about the ecology and behaviour of other species. Even scientific knowledge can be misleading; for instance, the misinterpretation of animal territoriality as human-like property has dominated models of foraging and aggression for decades (Despret, 2019). Therefore, to establish a multispecies society characterized by learning and democratic experimentation, it is critical to create a transdisciplinary knowledge base that integrates various forms of information about other species relevant to specific jurisdictions: This connects disembodied science in the domain of society with local and embodied knowledge in the community. For example, in the iconic species approach mentioned earlier (box 2.6), a community develops a knowledge base about a species that includes scientific facts, indigenous knowledge, local stories, and diverse citizen experiences with that species.

A crucial step involves understanding the demos. Traditionally, the demos consists of all human citizens who are recognized as having this status, although their voice is often limited to certain relevant decisions. Even when decisions directly affect all citizens, they may lack a voice, as seen in the case of many central banks. In the context of non-humans, defining the borders of the demos is more complex, as the

territories of many animals and even plants do not align with human jurisdiction. Thus, identifying the demos requires a learning process regarding its own status. This process can be bidirectional and issue-oriented; for example, migratory species may be considered part of the learning demos in some contexts while remaining outside it in others but can opt in by demonstrating issue-relevant actions. Some species may be regarded as “dormant” members whose vital interests are currently unaffected, engaging minimally with humans.

In the learning demos, the policy cycle (Jann and Wegrich, 2007) consists of human actions and non-human responses, followed by adaptive measures. Human actions serve as proposals, and the resulting experiences from these experiments inform evaluations of the proposals and suggest changes. It is unnecessary to assume that non-human actions are intentionally aimed at humans; rather, humans interpret these actions through an intentional lens. In this intentional stance, humans integrate non-human voices into the unfolding human political process, which primarily occurs through human language.

Figure 35: Policy cycle in multi-species community (author Simo Sarkki)

The principle of individualization is important in the policy cycle. Treating non-humans as mere “masses” and focusing solely on ecosystem mechanisms, such as population growth, may provide information but fails to recognize agency. In a democratic process that values experimentation, individual responses play a crucial role in driving learning. This is evident in civil rights movements, where we remember the courageous individuals who initiated change and often faced harsh repression from the majority. A similar dynamic is observed in animal rights literature: while most animals in a zoo may passively accept their situation, a few may attempt to escape or protest by throwing feces at visitors. These individuals, who take political action, should be heard in a learning democracy. Generally, this suggests that behaviors that deviate from the norm in a species can be particularly significant in the learning process.

Species-level majoritarian behavioural science reflects the power structures within multi-species communities. In this context, majoritarian science and local knowledge holders do not only complement each other within a transdisciplinary framework. Instead, local knowledge holders may challenge majoritarian science, which often represents non-humans in a way that upholds a speciesist perspective, in a twofold meaning. This highlights the dual nature of “majoritarian”—both in terms of scientific discourse and the dominant behavioural standards relating to species that stem from it.

The learning eco-demos is guided by a central principle: shared flourishing, often related to the “One Health” concept (Freeman and Merskin, 2023). Experiments in this framework are evaluated based on their contribution to shared flourishing. In formal democratic systems, it is assumed that voters express their opinions indirectly through the ballot box. Real-world democracy also encompasses essential institutions like a free press. However, shared flourishing in the human community is often measured using indicators such as GDP per capita and its distribution. An important alternative that has emerged in recent decades is the use of happiness indicators, which depend on individuals articulating their feelings of happiness (World Happiness Report, 2024). Ecological economics has made significant contributions to this area (Costanza et al., 2014). But what approach corresponds to the multi-species community? How can we

assess whether non-humans are flourishing, especially when considering their own perspectives?

One intriguing approach comes from the theory of federalism, which posits that alternatives to voting and speaking up include "exit" or "voting with their feet" (Somin, 2019). Tellingly, voting with the feet is one motivation for human migration as expressing discontent with political systems that are not responsive to their needs and concerns. This idea can be directly applied to non-humans, as they often respond to human actions by avoiding certain areas or migrating. For example, beavers dissatisfied with how their habitat is managed in a human-designed nature-based solution (NBS) may simply leave for another location (Welden, 2023). A key requirement for this style of embodied democratic deliberation is that non-humans must have the freedom to move. This concept is complex when considering animals like caged tigers in zoos, raising the question of why they are confined in the first place. Nonetheless, it is possible to envision scenarios where non-humans can have a degree of freedom, such as pigs in farming environments who are allowed to roam in adjacent protected areas, offering them a range of lifestyle choices. While we cannot explore this idea in depth here, there are many ways how it can be institutionalized (see box 4.3).

Box 4.3: Engaging wildlife as voluntary animal workers in NBS

Non-human animals often serve as workers for human causes. In the context of NBS, an example is using flocks of sheep to graze in areas designated as firebreaks. This approach is typically more cost-effective than other methods, such as mechanical clearing. There are various ways to employ animals for these tasks. A notable case from Mallorca involves guiding feral goats to perform this role (Pareja et al., 2020). The number of domesticated goat flocks in Mallorca has declined alongside the rural human population, leading to an increase in the feral goat population after releasing the domesticated goats to roam freely. These feral goats have become problematic, as they often damage private gardens and public greenery. A project was initiated to attract feral goats to firebreak areas, effectively assigning them the task of grazing in these regions. This approach does not involve controlling the goats through fencing or similar methods; instead, it utilizes knowledge of goat behaviour to make these areas more appealing as habitats. Simple measures, such as installing water holes and salt licks at certain times of the year, have proven effective. This strategy has been successful in several ways: it reduces wildfire risks, supports biodiversity, and minimizes damage to human property. However, there are also issues such as whether the released goats also competed with other species, similar to an invasive alien species.

In general, there are often opportunities to enhance the freedom of choice for non-human animals, allowing them to decide whether or not to engage with humans for human objectives (Driessen, 2014). The same concept can apply to plants. Designers of urban green spaces have various options regarding how strictly they control the species composition of an area and whether they allow for spontaneous evolution of the landscape (DeI Tredici, 2014)

4.1.4. Co-creation of NBS as “affordancing”

Considering the implications of the analysis conducted thus far for NBS, it is important to note that NBS are typically designed and implemented by humans. Within the human context, co-creation is widely recognized as the preferred approach to developing NBS. The literature on human co-creation is extensive and varied (Hirschnitz-Garbers, 2018; Nunes et al., 2021). Co-creation encompasses different methods of participatory planning and transdisciplinary knowledge production, creating a complex and sometimes confusing semantic landscape. For our purposes, we can simplify these discussions by stating that co-creation is an inclusive and non-hierarchical way of collaborating in the design and implementation of NBS.

Most co-creation processes involve stages that are mediated through language, such as community meetings where project officers explain the NBS to residents and invite them to participate in the project. Various challenges are associated with this process, and these are well-documented in the literature. An important question arises: how can we extend co-creation to non-human entities? Creation occurs through actions that bring something into existence. Co-creation involves interactions where actions combine to produce outcomes. This interaction can also be understood as a communication pattern; one party suggests an action, and the other responds by taking action, and so on. We refer to this dynamic as “affordancing.” Affordancing means that humans create opportunities for other beings through their actions, which these beings can then engage with. Humans, in turn, learn how to modify and enhance these opportunities based on the responses from other beings. At the same time, they may also respond to affordances created by the other species.

The key point is that the initial creation of these opportunities is not deterministic; it is open-ended and invites creativity from all involved parties. This concept lies at the

heart of learning within a multi-species community: humans must be prepared to be surprised by other beings and must be willing to learn from their responses.

Figure 36: Affordancing as a political process (author: Simo Sarkki)

Affordancing can occur both intentionally and unintentionally. Intentional affordancing involves actions such as creating spaces for resting, bathing, or providing shelter for various beings, even without targeting them specifically. This approach begins with generating a range of affordances for unknown users, based on a general understanding of their needs and capabilities. This idea aligns with the concept of exaptation, which can lead to sudden qualitative changes in the evolutionary process, as many beings may be pre-adapted to the affordances—even if their potential was initially dormant.

Unintentional affordancing can also happen. For instance, a construction site might temporarily leave debris or create water holes that are not functional for humans and were not meant to serve as affordances for other beings. However, it's possible that some beings might find these areas beneficial due to specific combinations of temperature, humidity, and resource availability. It is important for humans to be aware of such occurrences and to respond in a productive and cooperative manner. We consider an example in section 4.2, box 4.6). In landscape planning, a classic example of intentional affordancing is the renaturation and rewilding of old industrial sites. As overviewed in figure 35, this case illustrates mutual leveraging of affordancing. Lost

habitats create vulnerabilities for non-humans who search for alternative spaces, humans may recognize that old industrial sites, once decontaminated, offer a rich ecology of unknown affordances for these other species. Once the affordancing succeeds, humans discover new affordances for them, such as recreational uses of the renatured sites.

Box 4.4: Affordancing defunct urban sites in landscape urbanism

As we transitioned into the new millennium, landscape urbanism emerged as a cutting-edge approach in urban design and architecture (Reed and Lister, 2020; Waldheim, 2016). The concept of landscape can be traced back to the 18th-century fascination with dilapidated architecture in cities like Rome, where the ruins were intertwined with vegetation. Today, a similar phenomenon is occurring in urban areas facing decline, such as Detroit, where municipalities often lack the funds to demolish abandoned buildings and industrial sites. Leading architects have created a coevolutionary framework for creatively reconfiguring these spaces (Corner and Hirsch, 2014). A central component of this approach is to allow these areas to rewild through careful observation and management, incorporating architectural interventions that make them accessible for human recreation, such as cycling and hiking. Given the complex ecological histories of human-altered environments, planners cannot predict which plants will thrive in a given area, nor can they anticipate the subsequent arrival of pollinators, herbivores, and eventually predators (Del Tredici, 2014)(Reed et al., 2009). These areas then become experimental fields for coevolution. There is a broad range of possible interventions, including targeted measures similar to gardening and park design. This allows for the integration of ecological restoration goals with cultural heritage initiatives, as seen in the German Ruhr area, where the history of the steel and coal industry is celebrated alongside revitalized natural spaces (Teixeira et al., 2021).

Figure 37: "industrynature" in the Ruhr area, Germany

<https://www.rvr.ruhr/news/startseite-news/news/westpark-bochum-industrienatur/>

4.2. More-than-human stakeholder analysis

4.2.1. Neutrality of methods of stakeholder analysis?

Stakeholder analysis is a well-established tool in NBS research and ecological planning (Albert et al., 2021; Reed et al., 2009). Various methods exist to identify stakeholders and examine their relationships. However, most of these methods primarily focus on human stakeholders. This limitation is not inherent to the methods themselves. For example, social network analysis is adaptable to include any type of entities. It can be used to explore networks of humans—such as citizens, NGOs, and local government departments—and also incorporate non-human elements, like an iconic species, to analyze their interactions and events within the network (see box 4.5). If we consider "meetings" as an event that creates nodes in the network, we can include interactions between humans and iconic species in various formats. This approach requires documenting relevant activities, such as local administrators participating in field trips to learn about the iconic species, citizens engaging in birdwatching, or newspapers reporting on related events. Hence, SNA dovetails with other methods overviewed in this report, such as behavioural mapping (box 2.12).

Box 4.5: More-than-Human Network Analysis

Social Network Analysis (SNA) is a well-established quantitative method that explores the structure of interactions between agents and their implied properties, such as relative power within the network. The mathematical framework of SNA is neutral, meaning that the nodes in a network can represent not only individuals but also themes, events, or other non-agential entities. This flexibility allows for a seamless integration of SNA with Animal Social Network Analysis (ASNA), a well-developed area within ecology (Sosa et al., 2021).

Various metrics, such as centrality, can help identify the roles and significance of stakeholders in a network. However, utilizing SNA requires a prior decision regarding which actors to include and which types of connections to consider. This means that the list of stakeholders must be predetermined, which is particularly important when incorporating non-human entities. In ecological networks, certain species that are mostly unseen by humans can be crucial. Thus, constructing the network necessitates an overview of the relevant connections from the beginning.

One approach is to start with ego-centric networks, where individuals are asked about their connections within the context of the NBS. Another method involves ecological repertoire analysis to reconstruct the perspectives of specific non-humans. Advanced ASNA techniques (e.g., Smith and Pinter-Wollman, 2021) can enable the recording of movements and interactions of non-humans in a particular area. This data can be combined with results from behavioural mapping of humans.

Another critical decision in employing SNA is determining which types of connections to consider. This can be challenging and is a limitation of the method, as it often reduces the complexities of interactions to a few dimensions. For instance, if we focus solely on "meetings," we might overlook other forms of joint participation in events. When including non-humans, careful consideration of connection types that are meaningful to both humans and non-humans is essential. Co-presence in a specific location, for example, can be applicable to both. Only after these foundational steps have been established can the mathematical tools of SNA be effectively deployed. In the context of NBS, SNA can be particularly useful for measuring the marginalization of certain actors (Mitincu et al., 2023).

The flexibility of Social Network Analysis (SNA) makes it a powerful tool for identifying new types of actors through specific clustering effects. Actor-Network Theory has been partially inspired by the SNA perspective, although it employs a different approach (Latour, 2005). A crucial step in this process is recognizing new assemblages of entities as actors, which starts by identifying their regular co-occurrences in the data, such as through interviews (Youn and Baek, 2024). For instance, rather than viewing dogs and their owners as separate actors, we can consider them as an assemblage with distinct agential powers. This perspective encourages us to investigate the networks between "dog-humans" and other actors. Given the significant presence of dogs in modern urban environments, it would be more appropriate to regard "dog-humans" as stakeholders, rather than simply categorizing them as dog owners.

The neutrality of methods arises from the direct applicability of the stakeholder concept to non-humans, which is, however, hampered by the complexity and variety of definitions of the concept (Miles, 2017). A broad definition of stakeholders is that they both affect and are affected by certain organizations. In the context of NBS, this definition implies that non-humans function as stakeholders just as humans do, as they influence and are influenced by the NBS. This concept is often understood through the duality of passive (being affected) and active (affecting) stakeholders. However, there are significant differences when applying this duality to non-humans. In human contexts, an active stakeholder might not also be a passive one. For instance, a higher-level administration may have significant influence over an NBS but may not be affected by it. Similarly, many participants in environmental concerns define themselves as stakeholders without being directly impacted, such as an

environmental NGO that intervenes locally despite not having members in the area (see box 4.6).

The simplest way to identify stakeholders is to focus on passive stakeholders—those entities that are affected by an NBS, either positively or negatively. This approach tends to be anthropocentric, as the identification of these stakeholders typically relies on assessments made by human experts on local ecology. This method can be enriched transdisciplinarily by incorporating citizen science methods or other local knowledge holders' perspectives. However, in this case, although the method is neutral, the application lacks neutrality. Humans ultimately assign value to the stakes, determining their significance.

When considering active stakeholders, we encounter challenges regarding the neutrality of methods. This arises from the ambiguity of what “active” means: it may refer to agents who affect the NBS or those who express their interests actively through voice. If we adopt the latter view, language becomes a significant issue.

There are two key considerations related to voice (Reed et al., 2009). First, it raises the question of legitimate versus illegitimate stakeholder claims. This concept is well-established in business literature, where shareholders are often viewed as legitimate stakeholders, while environmental activists may be deemed illegitimate. Hence, stakeholder analysis can become critical and normative, especially when confronting the shareholder perspective versus the stakeholder perspective. The latter aims to address power imbalances that obstruct justice norms. In the case of NBS, this dynamic is also relevant, as NBS designers may define stakeholders based on specific functional members, disregarding others as illegitimate. For instance, an NBS may be designed with a specific plan that intentionally excludes certain plant species, even if those species flourish at the NBS site.

In human contexts, the distinction between legitimate and illegitimate stakeholders can be contested by voices seeking recognition. Additionally, the question arises of whose perspective counts in identifying legitimate stakeholders. In business literature, this often aligns with the company's interests, considering those stakeholders whose concerns are crucial for the company's survival and profitability. In the case of animals, a similar logic may apply, even if the animals themselves do not intentionally claim

stakes (Smart, 2022). For example, cows are stakeholders of the dairy industry, and hence their concerns matter, to a degree (see box 4.2). As the case of box 4.6. reveals, stakeholder analysis of non-humans needs to adopt a dynamic perspective in which the diverse concerns and interests may change, with a strong impact of frames that humans negotiate and implicitly adopt, as we scrutinized in the previous chapter.

Box 4.6: New stakeholders on the block

An interesting case illustrates the complexities of stakeholder analysis and highlights the important point that stakes evolve with a project and are highly idiosyncratic (Tryggestad et al., 2013). In a real estate construction project endorsed by local authorities, workers discovered two waterholes on the site that were covered by vegetation. The initial decision was to fill these holes. However, upon noticing the presence of many protected frogs, activists intervened and demanded the protection of the waterholes, a request that was legitimate under environmental law. The construction company attempted to refute the activists' arguments but was unsuccessful. Consequently, they adopted a new strategy, advised by biologists, which involved either relocating the frogs to another lake or protecting them on-site with fences and other means. The activists opposed the idea of moving the frogs, and the company complied. As a result, a protection system for the frogs was implemented. Ultimately, the waterholes became an attractive feature of the development and were highlighted in advertising as offering a natural environment for residents.

In this scenario, the frogs can be considered stakeholders, as they are both affected by the project and able to influence it. However, this relationship is mediated by human actors. Interestingly, the role of stakeholders cannot be reduced merely to the activists advocating for the frogs. The company, in developing strategies to address the issue, became more involved with the frogs, creating various ways to interact with them, such as returning stray frogs to the waterholes and regularly monitoring their population. While the activists initially seemed to represent the frogs, they were also advocating for the waterholes themselves, since the frogs could thrive in other locations. Over time, employees of the company began to form individual attachments to the frogs, going so far as to collect those that wandered off and return them to the waterholes. Thus, as events progressed, the stakes evolved, and the frogs became active participants—not merely through representation—but by engaging the company in practices that benefited both parties. Initially regarded as protected wildlife, the frogs eventually became somewhat “domesticated”, in the sense that the company actively cared for them while simultaneously reaping benefits from their cultural ecosystem services. This political process in the human domain resulted in the recognition of the frogs' status, which also transformed that very status.

Most methods for identifying stakeholders primarily rely on language. For example, Q analysis uses vignettes to uncover discourses through which stakeholders become visible. Similarly, stakeholder-led identification relies on categorizations that emerge

from interviews or other methods involving cards. However, these approaches typically do not allow for the inclusion of non-humans as autonomous subjects.

To address linguistic limitations, researchers can focus on methods that are less biased by language. One such method is snowball sampling. In one approach, researchers still depend on humans, but use them solely as intermediaries. For instance, researchers may ask individuals to identify non-human stakeholders of an NBS. This method leads researchers to non-humans, who cannot be directly asked to name other stakeholders. However, researchers can then approach another human who has also identified this stakeholder, along with others. Through these indirect mentions and their frequencies, a comprehensive list of non-human stakeholders can emerge. A key requirement is that the human respondents should be diverse, including experts, various demographic groups, and marginalized individuals.

In cases involving humans, stakeholders are often seen as active participants—at least in the sense that they express the value of their stakes. For example, if a worker has a stake in her job, what matters is her valuation, not the judgment of expert economists who argue that the job is non-competitive and that the worker could easily find a better position elsewhere. Active stakeholders operate based on subjective evaluations. The question then arises as to whether and how this concept applies to non-humans. The example of the worker illustrates a significant difference between human and non-human stakes, which can be understood through the concept of vulnerability. A worker who can easily find a new job is less vulnerable than one who cannot move freely, perhaps due to caregiving responsibilities for a relative who cannot relocate.

4.2.2. Stake specificity and vulnerability

In economics, the concept of asset specificity helps to illustrate the relationship between vulnerability and stakes (Williamson, 1985). We can introduce the idea of "stake specificity," which refers to what is valuable to an agent for various reasons. Stakes can often exist in a substitutive relationship with similar stakes in other contexts, such as a worker who might find another job if they lose their current one.

While the value of these stakes may ultimately be the same, certain stakes are specific to particular situations. Specificity can manifest in different forms, including spatial (the stake is only realizable in its current location), temporal (the stake can only be realized at a specific point in time), relational (the stake relies on unique relationships with other agents), and more (Herrmann-Pillath and Hederer, 2023, p. 100ff). When stake specificity is high, the agent becomes vulnerable, as they cannot easily realize the stake elsewhere and would suffer significant harm if that stake is jeopardized. Stake specificity is often highly individualized; for example, a worker caring for a relative may be more vulnerable than others. This suggests that using a group approach in stakeholder analysis can be misleading when examining stake specificity.

Vulnerability itself is a complex concept (Honkasalo, 2019). It is primarily a disposition determined by the environment, forming a structural possibility of harm rather than a realization of harm. A worker may feel secure in her job but remains vulnerable to job loss if her stake is specific. Furthermore, there is a distinction between *feeling* vulnerable and *being* vulnerable: an optimistic worker may not feel threatened by job loss, while an economist might diagnose the underlying vulnerability. Vulnerability also serves as a necessary condition for relationality, as being vulnerable to others grounds relationships in intercorporeality. Therefore, we must distinguish between stakes and vulnerabilities; while stakes can be objectified and categorized by groups, vulnerabilities are embodied individual experiences.

When we consider non-humans, we can infer that, compared to humans, non-humans typically exhibit higher stake specificity. This is because the ecosystems in which they exist often have idiosyncratic characteristics and involve locally unique forms of ecological networks and mutual adaptations among ecosystem elements. This holds true for humans in situations where place-related identities are significant. For instance, a worker may become vulnerable to job loss if relocation strips them of his place-related embeddedness. The same applies to many other living beings that cannot easily relocate. In comparing humans and non-humans, we see important cases where similar forms of stake specificity exist. For example, groups with limited mobility, such as the elderly or young children, share a similar vulnerability. If a local

green space is destroyed for urban development, non-humans cannot easily escape, and the elderly in the neighborhood may struggle to find a substitute.

Stake specificity aligns with the subjective value of a stake. Methodologically, it is possible to evaluate stakes from the perspective of a detached observer, such as an economist valuing a job or an ecologist assessing species-specific resources. Subjective value aligns closely with vulnerability compared to a group-level perspective, as it refers to uniquely individual features of the stake. In humans, this often entails the personal significance of the stake, as a job is more than just a source of income. For non-humans, this dimension may be overlooked, yet it is also relevant, as evidenced by non-human territoriality, which displays similar aspects to human place-boundedness. The common thread is the embodied relationality with the place of territory.

These observations reinforce the importance of individualization. Non-human stakeholders, like humans, should be treated as individuals rather than merely categorized by species. This approach is crucial for interpreting innovative actions to establish stakes. These actions can be seen as "subjective" but can also be linked to scientific knowledge, thereby becoming more objectified (box 4.7).

Box 4.7. Integrative more-than-human stakeholder analysis: Stakeholder personas

The method of stakeholder personas incorporates various elements from CEA-NBS methods, such as individualization through naming and storytelling. This approach is well-developed in participatory design (Tomitsch et al., 2021) and is applicable to both human and non-human stakeholders.

A persona represents a specific stakeholder, emphasizing an exemplary individual rather than merely identifying a group. Each persona includes a picture, a biography, major activities, and concerns, along with a narrative that illustrates how the individual is affected by the design issue. Personas are instrumental in organizing the participatory design process through various media, including focus group discussions. In the context of NBS, personas can inform the design of role-playing games, for example (see box 1.1). Non-human personas can represent individualized animals, such as Angie the sparrow. While human personas are often portrayed as speaking directly to the audience, it is usually recommended that non-human personas be represented in the third person to avoid anthropomorphism. However, in CEA-NBS, a first-person perspective may be more effective in certain contexts, such as in letter-writing (see box 3.6).

The creation of personas can draw from diverse resources, including ecological data, local narratives, and citizen science. This process can also take place during participatory workshops. Developing these personas may yield new insights similar to a snowball effect, as the narratives might highlight related individuals. A key aspect of the persona approach

is that engaging with these personas can initiate a deliberative process that fosters coalitions among stakeholders, including vulnerable groups like young children and animals affected by an NBS. Additionally, it is possible to assign personas to assemblages, such as the aforementioned "dog-humans," which function as a dyadic persona, especially when agency is distributed within the assemblage.

4.2.3. Stakeholder representation and stewardship

An important issue in practice is determining how far humans can act as stakeholders for other beings. This raises questions about the legitimacy of activism. Often, humans claim to represent stakeholders, but they may actually be independent stakeholders themselves. For instance, an NGO dedicated to nature protection might be a generic stakeholder that asserts contingent stakes on behalf of non-humans. In the case of frogs (see Box 4.6), NGOs do not represent frogs directly; instead, they have relationships with various entities beyond the local NBS and the specific species involved.

Representation can be multidirectional. For example, local activists may first represent the NGO and then, in turn, represent a non-human entity in a specific local context. The issue with these multidirectional representations is that the valuation of stakes becomes a subject of local political discourse, as various parties can challenge valuations that non-humans cannot express directly. In the worst-case scenario, claims regarding non-human stakes may merely serve as placeholders for other interests pursued by humans, blurring the lines between different valuations.

To avoid these complications, the stewardship model is valuable because it allows for individualizing stakeholder representation. This model requires a legitimate process for assigning and recognizing stewards. Stewards would focus on specific non-humans within a local context rather than representing them generically or on a species level. Thus, stewardship is a key component in place-making and -shaping (Johnson et al., 2020). This suggests that stewards do not just represent stakeholders; they also help create the stakes themselves (see Box 4.8). Paradoxically, this can increase vulnerabilities due to the high specificity tied to particular places.

Box 4.8: Biocultural stewardship in New York

Researchers, activists, and concerned citizens have developed a model of biocultural stewardship inspired by Hawaiian Indigenous beliefs, rituals, and concepts of relatedness, known as *Hālau ʻŌhiʻa* (McMillen et al., 2020). Similar to other Indigenous cosmologies, the Hawaiian perspective emphasizes relationality through embodied kinship with places, which includes not only other living beings but also non-living entities. As a result, stewardship is closely tied to the specific characteristics of these places and how people relate to them in physical, embodied ways. This approach incorporates a strong spiritual component, breaking down the boundaries between humans and non-humans. In practice, this means that human well-being and the flourishing of non-human entities are seen as intimately connected; caring for nature is also an act of self-care. Stewardship activities can take various forms, such as maintaining public parks and organizing urban gardens. In the New York case, Hawaiian rituals play a crucial role in activating stewardship. A Hawaiian leader and facilitator introduces Indigenous ritual practices to participants, such as the traditional ritual of initiating meetings (*mele komo*) and sharing mythical stories (*kaʻao*). These rituals encourage participants to create their own stories and myths about the places they engage with. Through collective reflection on these narratives, participants deepen their connection to the place and draw inspiration from other locations. Beyond storytelling, the rituals also involve creative activities, such as crafting objects from local plants and materials, which are then ritually acknowledged as sacred.

An important aspect of these Hawaiian rituals is the creation of images on various scales, which contributes to expanding stewardship efforts. While rooted in the embodied relationship with the local area, these images connect to broader themes of regional embeddedness and global interconnectivity. This connection ties stewardship to global issues, such as climate change and migration.

Stewardship is a model of governance that is polycentric, adaptive, and participatory, rooted in the principle of individualization. In the context of NBS, stewardship fosters a relationship with the natural environment and invites creative expressions of commitment, concern, and care. As such, stewardship fundamentally differs from interest-based stakeholder relations. Stewards can activate local stories, myths, and, when relevant, indigenous knowledge. For example, in modern cities like New York, the diverse demographic composition may enable the activation of various traditions from past and present immigrant communities, even if the area is not originally associated with Indigenous cultures (which, however, in the New York case is also true).

4.3. Nature-based governance

4.3.1. Stakes, goals and governance

Indigeneity is often celebrated as a fundamental form of environmental governance (Grabowski et al., 2022; Hankins, 2024). We refer to this as an exemplary model of “nature-based governance” (NBG). This term still lacks a clear definition, beyond the formula of governing with and for nature. Governance is often categorized into different modes, such as market versus hierarchy (Pahl-Wostl, 2019) or market versus stakeholder (Albert et al., 2021). In these frameworks, “nature” would suggest just another mode of governance. However, this perspective reflects anthropocentric views, as we typically do not consider the behaviour of other beings as being governed by institutions. This raises the question of whether we can extend the concept of governance beyond human beings in the context of NBS.

Traditionally, the governance of NBS focuses on human behaviour, where the manipulation of nature is viewed as an engineering process that adheres to nature's principles. This perspective highlights a hierarchical aspect of governance, which suggests a distinction between those who govern and those who are governed. Even concepts of participatory governance imply that a group voluntarily agrees on certain rules and also enforces them. In relation to nature, the NBS may indicate a similar hierarchical relationship, where non-human elements are subject to human objectives. This raises the question of who governs in NBG? Moreover, are the behavioural foundations across the various modes of governance the same, especially when including non-humans?

Most theories of governance—even those emphasizing participation and polycentricity—implicitly rely on an economic approach. This approach considers how rational individual actors respond to an institutional context designed to guide their behaviour in a specific direction, often through regulations or incentives. This is particularly evident in fields like environmental economics or political science (Bennett and Satterfield, 2018).

The implicit focus on economics reflects the fact that governance is always goal-oriented. For instance, in the context of NBS, there are established ideas about how

these solutions should function and how their performance is assessed. This leads to questions about which behavioural rules can ensure their proper operation. Governance failures, in many cases, are identified as causes of dysfunction. However, the conceptual link between NBS and governance is often unclear due to the complexity of NBS (box 4.9). Strictly speaking, an NBS is a specific solution to a particular problem. Yet, this instrumental relationship is rarely straightforward, as NBS often encompass multiple goals. For example, a rain park designed for water management may also aim to enhance biodiversity, while also serving recreational purposes. This results in multiple stakeholders becoming involved, complicating the governance of their behaviours and necessitating their inclusion in the governance framework. Moreover, many NBS cannot be considered in isolation, particularly when biodiversity is involved. The required connectivity among individual NBS means that many actors in different locations may also play a role. For instance, a green roof cannot significantly contribute to biodiversity if there are no pathways connecting it to a nearby park.

Box 4.9: Governance challenges to complexity of NBS: A Stockholm case

Three municipalities in the Stockholm area are undertaking urban development projects of varying sizes and scopes, specifically aimed at achieving ecological goals that benefit both humans and biodiversity (Brokking et al., 2021). In these projects, the concept of NBS has emerged as a key idea that shapes the understanding of "ecology" in discussions among experts, planners, and the public. The term "ecosystem services" has become an essential framework for making ecological aspects relevant to people by highlighting their own interests.

NBS relates to urban green spaces in various forms, such as parks and green corridors that connect different locations. A common theme across these projects is the management of connectivity among NBS and the integration of ecological aspects. Importantly, "greenery" is often viewed primarily as a way to meet human needs and preferences, rather than directly contributing to biodiversity. Thus, the first challenge was to realign these projects, which were initially treated as integrative urban development initiatives combining green spaces with other uses—like residential and recreational areas—without considering ecological expertise.

Urban development projects typically involve private developers, posing another challenge: motivating them to prioritize ecological considerations. Governance issues are significant here, as the complexity varies based on whether a project is a public tender that can include ecological criteria in its contracts or an independent initiative led by private investors. This complexity has necessitated early engagement with the public. For effective project governance, developing a shared mindset among all stakeholders about the importance of ecological goals proved crucial—especially for the public, as users and

potential buyers of residential units near these green spaces. However, trade-offs remain important, particularly concerning investors' interests in value creation. Additionally, the connectivity of different green spaces requires coordination beyond individual project boundaries, taking into account pathways linking various locations. For urban planners, this also involves creating mobility corridors for walking, cycling, and movement without cars.

In summary, the complexity of these issues has led to the emergence of a polycentric governance approach, which is uniquely tailored to each location and must be coordinated by urban authorities.

Governance can pertain to various stages of a project, including the design, production, and maintenance of NBS. Experience shows that these distinctions are crucial, particularly when a local authority decides to implement an NBS for the first time. Discussions about participatory governance often focus heavily on the design stage while neglecting the maintenance stage, which can jeopardize the sustainability of the NBS (Diep et al., 2022). The stewardship model is particularly relevant during this maintenance phase. However, there is criticism that involving citizens in creating and maintaining the NBS may simply be a strategy to offload costs onto them.

Since governance is inherently goal-related, there is a direct connection to the previous discussion on stakeholders. We previously distinguished between legitimate and illegitimate stakes, emphasizing that the translation of these stakes into goals is also a matter of governance. This highlights the importance of clearly translating stakes into goals, as there is often a lack of transparency regarding the objectives of different stakeholders. For instance, the local finance department plays a critical role as a stakeholder, as it could decide to halt an NBS for financial reasons, even though it may lack specific goals tied to the NBS itself. This raises key questions in designing governance for NBS: which actors' goals are included? Consequently, some stakes may be deemed illegitimate.

To illustrate, consider whether dog owners should have a say in creating an urban forest, given their interest in using it for dog walks. Excluding their input could lead to designs unfavourable to them, prompting dog owners to engage with local authorities to request changes. This scenario raises additional questions about non-human stakeholders. Should the dogs have a voice in determining governance goals? For example, if a rule requires dogs to be kept on lead, how might that decision change if

dogs were included in the design process? Dog owners, often acting as stewards, might disregard such a rule on behalf of their pets.

In general, stakeholder analysis can reveal the diverse goals various actors have concerning the NBS, which may not align with its primary purpose. The finance department might support the NBS solely because it is less expensive than conventional grey infrastructure. Additionally, governance during the design and early implementation phases often differs significantly from governance in later stages. This issue is particularly pronounced in Living Labs funded externally, as this temporary governance structure may not be sustainable or scalable in the long term.

Regarding non-humans, their goals are typically not represented in formal governance frameworks. Representation usually occurs through participatory governance facilitated by NGOs, such as animal protection groups, or certain environmental offices that consider non-human objectives. The diversity of goals can sometimes justify the NBS for reasons unrelated to its primary function. For example, a city might promote urban biodiversity to attract tourists while primarily pursuing economic development goals. However, what happens if ecologists recommend greenery that is not appealing to tourists? The devil, indeed, lies in the details. One approach that sets the scene for deliberative processes that lead to inclusion of non-humans while making the diversity of goals and stakes explicit is engaging actors that play an important role in governance in strategic games that enhance awareness and understanding of the complexities of governance (box 4.10).

Box 4.10. From role board game to ecosemiotic experimenting **coevolvers**

Role-based board games (RBG)* have their origins in agent-based modeling (ABM), a computational method used to simulate the individual and collective behaviour of agents. This approach is applicable in both ecology and social sciences, as well as in common-pool resource experiments that explore the social dilemmas of collective action.

Role-playing has been integrated into the second generation of common-pool resource board games, as demonstrated by researchers at Arizona State University (Cardenas et al., 2013; Janssen and Baggio, 2017; Poteete et al., 2011). This innovation enhances the original design of common-pool resource experiments by incorporating repeated interactions among human agents. This approach increases the validity of field experiments, allows for the testing of governance innovations, and stimulates the learning process. These versions of RBGs focus on decision-making scenarios in which a group

of users of natural resources makes a series of choices regarding use or protection, all while facing changes in socio-ecological systems, such as climate events and social rules or incentives. The game employs monetary fees to encourage economic behaviour, in contrast to societal (collective) rewards that are adjusted to local circumstances. Overharvesting and individual strategies typically result in a loss of the resource quantity. The repeated interactions and assigned roles serve as an interactive ABM, fostering learning and reinforcing the importance of collective action for community sustainability. The CETIP network group (Kluvankova et al., 2020) has expanded upon this concept to enhance the dynamics of sustainable provision of forest ecosystem services. They introduced an additional agent—external to resource use—representing authority figures with monitoring and regulatory power, such as national parks, regional offices, or government institutions. In these RBGs, nature is represented as a variable that affects socio-ecological systems and group payoffs, but it lacks agency. To address this, the experimental design of RBGs is being innovated by CETIP and IFE SAS as part of the COEVOLVERS program (Kluvankova et al., in preparation). This will involve adding two new players assigned the roles of non-humans, such as animals or plants. These roles aim to create agencies for non-humans within the game algorithm, enabling them to express their influence (Joli cards). In the game Ecopoly, the traditional social dilemma is transformed into a multispecies (institutional) arena where these multispecies agencies interact to test and potentially change habits, practices, meanings, and affordances. Ecopoly is currently being tested outside of laboratory settings under the COEVOLVERS initiative and is planned to be further developed as a virtual reality educational tool.

* The Role Board Game (RBG) has been developed by Tatiana Kluvankova, Martin Špaček, Marco A. Janssen et al, and it is now under co-development and operative modification to fit and address the multiple settings and circumstances studied in COEVOLVERS project.

Figure 38: Eco semiotic experiment Ecopoly in Coevolvers LLs Beskydy and Cagliari; Foto: CETIP

In summary, while governance is a term frequently used in the literature on NBS) there is currently no coherent and universally accepted conceptual framework to clearly define Nature-Based Governance (NBG). A key question arises: Are we discussing traditional governance of human actions through mechanisms that exist within the human conceptual realm, as described in Chapter 1? Or are we considering more-

than-human governance mechanisms, where “nature” plays a role in governing human actions?’

4.3.2. More-than-human governance

Theories of governance have recently expanded to encompass governance through environmental cues. This perspective aligns with behavioral economics, which emphasizes how environmental signs can influence behavior (Lindenberg, 2018). In this context, governance becomes embodied—a concept familiar from Foucault’s idea of governmentality (Foucault et al., 2004). Governmentality suggests that governing institutions are internalized, similar to public hygiene norms established since the 19th century. Hence, one interpretation of nature-based governance (NBG) is that “nature” refers to human nature in terms of following rules that are internalized (Manheim and Spackman, 2022). This embodied rule-following is linked to the formation of habits. As Descola (2011) has argued, the term “nature” has been interpreted in two different ways in European intellectual history: One is “nature” as referring to “human nature”, and the other is “nature” as being different from the domain of human culture and hence including a vast territory of non-human natural entities. For understanding NBG it is illuminating to refer to both meanings.

The concept of internalization means that governance is embodied, which still means that NBG can adopt strategies of governmentality that establish a hierarchical relationship between rule-makers and rule-followers. For instance, in the case of NBS, a local authority might issue guidelines about expected behaviours in a public park and implement various strategies to encourage the habitual adoption of these behaviours among the population. This is similar to how "no litter" policies have been internalized by most people today. NBG would still imply that a human governing organization implements the governance mechanism, and not “nature” in the sense of a non-human entity or process.

In the context of NBS, it is crucial to understand that the concept of "habit" extends beyond individual behaviours to include organizational practices. In organizational theory, this is referred to as "routines" (D’Adderio, 2008). This understanding is

particularly useful for addressing challenges such as the "silo" effect in NBS governance (European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation., 2023), which often arises from diverse goals across different organizations. Silo effects do not only pertain to the differing objectives of various departments within local administrations; they also involve distinct practices related to task execution and evaluation. For example, there may be significant differences between the approaches of a financial analyst, a social worker addressing homelessness, and a manager at a city promotional agency. Such practices become deeply ingrained through the use of artifacts like forms and formalized procedures outlined in organizational handbooks (D'Adderio, 2011).

For NBS research, identifying these silo effects is often essential. Preferred methods for exploration include focus group interviews where members from different organizations discuss these phenomena, as well as on-site participatory observations. It is important to recognize that these issues can vary across stages of implementation: during the experimental phase of an NBS, routines may be disrupted as a side effect. However, as the project transitions back to business as usual, established routines tend to resurge.

NBG, in terms of human "nature," extends beyond the individual to encompass complex assemblies of humans, as understood in approaches like Actor-Network Theory. This makes NBG self-referential; there is no autonomous or external entity that implements governance mechanisms without being affected by and embedded within an existing governance structure. One way this manifests is through framing effects at the behavioural level, where individuals from different governance organizations—such as finance departments or environmental agencies—adopt varying cognitive perspectives toward the NBS.

Exploring the alternative interpretation of NBG, especially in light of gardening, suggests that human behaviour may be governed by nature as the "other." This concept requires careful examination, as "natural laws" could be misconstrued as a form of governance. By focusing on the regularities of life, particularly the behavioural patterns of animals, extensive research on animal-human interactions demonstrates that animals, even when economically exploited, possess agency and impose

constraints on humans. For instance, a dog trainer must adapt to the dog's behaviour, which means the trainer is partially governed by the animal (Fox et al., 2023).

Traditionally, the behavioural regularities of non-humans are not viewed as governance. However, humans can institutionalize these regularities by granting rights to non-human entities. For example, a stork may regularly build a nest on a rooftop, and humans not only accept this but also grant the stork the right to nest there. This illustrates that a significant aspect of NBG involves assigning property rights to other beings, transforming their natural functions into rights to essential resources and spaces (Hadley, 2015). Such ideas have faced criticism for projecting a neoliberal understanding of rights onto non-humans; this critique is valid and highlights the potential for institutional alternatives, such as employing a commons model to assign rights to various members within the commons (Herrmann-Pillath, 2023b). The Indigenous perspective raises critical questions about whether rights imply alienability, particularly concerning market forces. If commons are not alienable, this limitation extends to all other associated rights.

Looking at the model of Indigeneity, an essential question arises: Can NBG, through institutions, create and sustain relationality? As previously discussed regarding framing, it is crucial to recognize that governance modes can be performative, thereby altering the motivations of actors. Human institutions often lead to significant disembodiment. This is especially evident when considering reciprocity as a governance scheme. Reciprocity can be exhibited through disembodied forms, such as financial transactions, or through embodied forms, like mutual assistance.

We propose that the ongoing and varied debates about governance can also be examined through the lens of embodiment versus disembodiment (Herrmann-Pillath, 2024). Governance through laws, regulations, or administrative actions is typically disembodied. While many forms of participatory governance may be categorized as embodied, this is not always the case. For instance, public deliberations tend to lean towards disembodiment since rational discourse often prevails. As mentioned in section 4.1, a key criterion for embodiment is the primacy of action. Stewardship serves as a paradigmatic example of embodied governance, particularly when it aligns with Indigenous practices (Grabowski et al., 2022). In this context, rituals emerge as

an alternative form of governance and as a essential mode of NBS which also differs in principle from a rights-based approach informed by disembodied conceptions of institutions.

4.3.3. Ritual as paradigmatic form of Nature-based governance

We propose that a prime form of NBS is ritual (Kealiikanakaoleohailani et al., 2018). While ritual can be institutionalized, its essential characteristic is action. In the Durkheimian view, ritual action embodies values and creates a shared reality (Mc Graw, 2015). This concept is evident in recent developments in ecological stewardship. As highlighted in Box 4.11, the ritualization of stewardship serves as a key medium for mobilizing and sustaining emotional energy, which helps in establishing regular behaviours and habits over time. Notably, this idea is increasingly acknowledged in business literature, which points to a potential connection between NBS, rituals, and local businesses—particularly in the context of leisure and tourism (Massa et al., 2017). Ritual is a critical medium of commoning, that means, the formation and sustaining of a community that is grounded on shared flourishing.

Box 4.11: Rituals of sheepville coevolvers

The distinction between disembodied and embodied forms of relating to nature can be illustrated through the hypothetical case of Sheepville (Box 1.14), where sheep are utilized as workers in a NBS for fire protection along the borders between human settlements and forests (Figure 40). In the disembodied model, herders receive compensation from municipal authorities for their services. However, neighborhoods that are most at risk from wildfires may not even recognize this connection. If they are expected to contribute financially, it could lead to resistance. Additionally, some residents might find the sheep to be a nuisance due to noise or smell, especially if the animals graze close to their homes (Figure 39).

Figure 39: Goats and sheep as a nuisance (Barcelona Living Lab)

In the fictional town of Sheepville, neighborhoods actively engage with and support the herders, recognizing the sheep as valued members of the community who provide significant benefits to everyone (see fig. 39). The bond with the sheep is celebrated through various rituals, such as neighbours welcoming newborn lambs and giving them names, seasonal festivals that prominently feature sheep, and storytelling and artistic performances. The herders are acknowledged not only as owners of their flocks but also as stewards of the sheep and the surrounding forest. The rituals of Sheepville enact the commoning of the firebreak in building a community of all engaged members of the NBS.

Figure 40: Embodied versus disembodied governance

In the real case of the COEVOLVERS Barcelona Living Lab, these structures are gradually emerging as citizens increasingly engage with sheep and shepherds (see Figure 41). A key group involved in this engagement is children, who participate in various educational activities. Modern technology has also helped bridge social barriers between

shepherds and the community, as some shepherds have established a social media presence and act as stewards in this space. These efforts contribute to the creation of roles such as community liaison activists. We can regard all these activities as steps towards commoning the firebreak NBS.

Figure 41: Educational events and activists

Rituals differ from institutions in that they represent a form of governance shared between humans and non-humans (Stephenson, 2015) (see Chapter 1, Figure 9). In the Durkheimian tradition, rituals are fundamental to forming community among humans (Rossano, 2016). The concept of emotional energy explains why rituals possess performative powers distinct from those of institutions (Collins, 2005). For decades, institutional and organizational theories have largely overlooked emotions, being dominated by a rationalist perspective prevalent in much of contemporary social science (Zietsma et al., 2019). The mobilization and maintenance of emotions play a crucial role in stabilizing specific patterns of behaviour over time, especially in relation to particular assemblages of entities, such as NBS. Rituals serve as a medium for both inward and outward embodiment of emotions: they can induce certain emotional states in individuals, such as Durkheimian effervescence (Gabriel et al., 2020), while also allowing these states to be expressed collectively, especially through embodied valuations. Often, rituals enact sacred values within a community.

This creation of the sacred by rituals is pertinent to enacting intrinsic values of nature (Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, IPBES, 2022). Biodiversity goals can be difficult to measure quantitatively in the short

term, and pursuing these goals often requires perseverance and the ability to cope with psychological setbacks (Box 4.12). Consequently, rituals frequently serve as a primary means of demonstrating care, acting as recurrent activities that express concern for others. They are essential for connecting people to specific places. In this context, ritual theory has also highlighted the importance of novelty and innovation in creating rituals (Bell, 1997). This is particularly relevant given that NBS can introduce new features to a location, making emotional commitments less certain (Raymond et al., 2023a).

Box 4.12: The mushroom at the end of the world

In her acclaimed book on the Matsutake mushroom, Tsing (2017, p. 257ff) discusses citizen activism in Japan aimed at restoring Satoyama landscapes. Historically, Satoyama forests served as rural commons in pre-modern Japan, utilized by communities for various purposes, including logging and Matsutake harvesting (Berglund et al., 2014). The Matsutake mushroom is particularly sensitive and cannot be cultivated through agricultural methods; it thrives in symbiosis with red pine trees. During industrialization, many Satoyama forests were destroyed for industrial forestry operations that focused on growing other types of trees, leading to a decline in Matsutake availability and causing it to become rare and costly. The rise of cheaper imported mushrooms contributed to the decline of industrial forests, which were then left to return to a wild state, resulting in negative consequences for local fauna and flora. Additionally, the red pine faced serious threats from imported diseases. Satoyama forests held ritual significance due to their association with animistic worship in Shinto practices. Recently, various initiatives have emerged to restore these landscapes, including the revival of ritual practices as concerned citizens work to reestablish harmony between people and nature (Ishizawa, 2018). In this context, Matsutake possesses a deep spiritual value that motivates the emotional commitment of activists. After all, Matsutake is embodied also in the sense of ritualized culinary practices, literally making the mushroom part of the body. The activists face the challenge that restoring a Satoyama landscape is a long-term process that can take decades, and it is unpredictable whether and when the Matsutake mushroom will reappear. The spirituality of both the landscape and the mushroom sustains their efforts.

Ritual combines the two perspectives on nature that we introduced in the previous section. We can speak of ritual affordances manifesting this synthesis: Natural entities and processes become ritual affordances in evoking and sustaining ritual practices that are grounded in embodied valuations. Hence, summarizing the discussion in this subsection, we define NBG as: Nature-based governance grounds governance mechanisms in embodied more-than-human practices with normative force. Ritual is

the paradigmatic social phenomenon that enacts this type of governance. NBS is a key element in creating an NBS community, hence of commoning (Federici and Linebaugh, 2019; Leitheiser et al., 2022). NBS activates environmental features of places and the emerging habits of cohabitation for governing the behaviours of humans and non-humans. As such, NBS raises similar issues of justice like when considering human institutions.

4.4. Justice in a multi-species community

The concept of justice is fundamental in the context of CEA-NBS (Cousins, 2021). We have already explored various aspects, allowing us to focus on the essentials here. Justice is often differentiated along several dimensions, such as procedural, distributive, and retributive justice, or regarding specific domains, such as intergenerational justice (Miller, 2023). In the context of NBS, multi-species justice has become a critical concern, in the sense of transcending the limitations of environmental justice, which remains an anthropocentric concept. However, within that specific domain, we can still refer to the various analytical types of justice.

Let us start with retributive justice, which is the least familiar even within the multi-species justice literature. This aspect often arises in discussions with experts who are not advocates for the multi-species cause. The question at hand is whether, and to what extent, justice implies that other species have responsibilities toward humans, such as when migratory species damage crops on their way (see box 3.10). In contrast, the prevailing debate typically focuses on enhancing and deepening human responsibilities and empathy towards other beings, acknowledging the human guilt in driving the planet toward the brink of collapse (Celermajer et al., 2021). However, the very concept of ecosystem services, which is essential to NBS, indicates that nature primarily serves human interests, often implying trade-offs. If an NBS fails to provide its intended ecosystem service but still unexpectedly enhances biodiversity, what should human do in response? The situation becomes even more complex when NBS is combined with rewilding strategies, as this can lead to various harms for humans.

Indigenous perspectives offer valuable insights into the relationship between humans and non-human entities. Relationality and reciprocity do not suggest that human interests are less important than those of non-human beings. In fact, hunting and harvesting animals play a crucial role in many Indigenous practices and worldviews. Before colonial dispossession, the abundance of wildlife benefited not only non-human species but was also celebrated by Indigenous communities. Today, for instance, First Nations and tribal laws do not prohibit hunting; rather, these practices are steeped in rituals that convey respect and gratitude toward the animals that are hunted. Additionally, humans take on the responsibility of caring for other species (Trospen, 2022).

There is an additional aspect, rarely discussed, regarding the extent to which multi-species justice encompasses justice in inter-species relations among non-human beings. Many people argue against the idea of judging animal behaviour based on human notions of justice. In fact, the concept of multi-species justice primarily focuses on how we can include other species in morally evaluating and guiding human actions. However, this limitation should be examined both empirically and theoretically (Rowlands, 2012). Animals are moral subjects; therefore, we can also engage with them in terms of retributive justice and ethical judgment. This implies that we can demand justice from other species, just as they can demand justice from one another. We address this point because it has significant implications for the theory and practice of stewardship in NBS. A central issue is how to manage invasive species that threaten local ecosystems. Animal rights theorists often argue that humans do not have the right to kill these invasive species. In contrast, ecological scientists and conservationists prioritize ecosystem interests, thereby justifying such actions. The perspective outlined here aims to reconcile this conflict by extending the notion of justice to inter-species relations: it is not merely the ecosystem that suffers due to invasive species but also the interests and moral rights of native individuals that are infringed upon by the invading species. Consequently, human stewards take on the role of judges and enforcers in regulating the behavior of all members within the ecosystems for which they are responsible. In fulfilling this role, they must act

impartially, although this does not preclude them from taking necessary actions, including the culling of certain species (box 4.13).

Box 4.13. Humans as judges in inter-species conflicts among non-humans

The Island of Cres, Croatia is an almost laboratory case of multi-species justice in the sense championed here. Ugo Toic, the Advisory Board member of COEVOLVERS, initiated the idea of conducting a Small-Scall Pilot on the island of Cres, Croatia. It is a COEVOLVERS' strategy to involve AB members in such active ways in actual research work, especially through co-designed Small-Scale Pilots. Cres has been home to sheep and goat husbandry for centuries, with local culinary traditions. A side effect is the low incidence of wildfires, which is beneficial to the local olive tree agriculture. However, with the decline of traditional sheep farming, the sheep roam freely, thus threatening the ecological balance of the traditional agroecosystem. At the same time, in recent decades, a conflict arose after humans introduced wild boar and deer to the island who also left the confines of hunting areas.

Figure 42: Sheep farming and wild boars on the island of Cres (Cres COEVOLVERS pilot)

The wild boar are increasingly damaging the sheep herds on the island. However, completely expelling the wild boar is likely an unrealistic goal. A stakeholder group, consisting of recreational and professional hunters, has emerged because the island provides an ideal setting for their activities. While sheep owners are facing rising costs to protect their herds, the hunters contribute to mitigating the threat through their culling efforts.

This situation exemplifies a multi-species social dilemma, involving conflicts of interest between human and non-human stakeholders that must be resolved through a deliberative process. There is a clear connection between the human and non-human groups; one might even describe this relationship as an assemblage of hunters and wild boars on one side, and herd owners and sheep on the other. From the human perspective, both animal groups can significantly contribute to enhancing tourism and high-value food processing on the island, thereby creating economic synergies. Achieving this requires institutional solutions that all stakeholders must discuss and agree upon,

wildlife. Most NBS are situated within human jurisdictions, and multi-species justice entails recognizing all living beings as eco-citizens. This raises complex questions about the rights and responsibilities of various members in relation to human design, which can only be addressed through a co-evolutionary process of collective deliberation.

One significant challenge is ensuring justice for all human stakeholders, acknowledging that not everyone adheres to vegetarianism. This observation highlights the intricate question of how intra-human justice fits within the framework of multi-species justice. A dilemma faced by this approach is the risk of being labelled as "woke" or, more seriously, imposing an expert or activist perspective on others who may not share that viewpoint. For instance, the iconic species approach, which seeks to make biodiversity goals inclusive, often elevates specific species—such as salmon—due to their historical significance to human activities like hunting. Building NBS around a species that is central to local cuisine can conflict with the idea of recognizing each animal's right to live. In multi-ethnic human communities, culinary practices are often key to defining cultural identities, which means that multi-species justice might challenge these identities and could be perceived as ethnic discrimination.

Consider the example of Sheepville: producing local sausages and other products from sheep and goats can financially sustain an NBS by creating more opportunities for shepherds, and these local products can be showcased at festivals. However, the practice of killing sheep also constitutes a significant violation of their animal rights. Such dilemmas can only be addressed gradually as new habits form. A critical precondition for progress is to prevent any expansive market-driven approaches that would fundamentally alter the nature of these activities. Historically, such constraints were a vital institutional feature of traditional commons in Europe (de Moor, 2018).

This means that multi-species justice must be grounded in a rigorous application of procedural justice. We have already discussed various related issues concerning the recognition and representation of non-human entities. In essence, multi-species justice embodies a type of multi-species democracy, where all affected parties should have a voice and participate in collective decision-making. This principle is not even

fully realized within human democracies, especially regarding children, highlighting that multi-species justice is an ideal to strive for, though it will likely face many challenges.

While procedural justice may encounter numerous obstacles, distributive justice presents a more feasible avenue for human interactions with other species. We have also highlighted these aspects in discussing the capability approach in justice theory. Importantly, the design of NBS is ethically significant, as it necessitates an impartial balancing of the interests of all beings involved. This implies that, despite recognizing other species and moving away from an anthropocentric framework, humans bear a heightened ethical responsibility that includes thoughtfully ordering inter-species relationships. Ultimately, ecological engineering of NBS represents a quest for multi-species justice.

Chapter 5: Outlook - Beyond actionable knowledge: The coevolution of knowledge and action

5.0. Chapter summary

1. The coevolutionary approach moves beyond simple propositional definitions of knowledge and encompasses all forms of embodied and distributed knowledge. This includes organizational structures and assemblages that involve non-human entities.
2. The concept of actionable knowledge is paradoxical; it refers to experiences transformed into propositional forms that can then be made actionable. In contrast, the coevolutionary approach embraces a pragmatist view, suggesting that knowledge (in the sense of (1)) coevolves with action, never reaching completion, and accumulates within iterative participatory communities of inquiry.
3. Coevolutionary knowledge should be shared through non-propositional means, such as experiences in co-presence fostering creative imitation, narratives (including movies), or multidimensional dynamic maps and other artistic media.
4. The coevolutionary approach to nature-based NBS emphasizes the uncertainty of the future, which suggests the idea of actionable ignorance. This perspective entails the concept of entrepreneurship. In economics, the duality of general and local knowledge aligns with the pragmatist conception of knowledge. A key aspect of implementing and sustaining a NBS is to institutionally enable a new form of entrepreneurship.
5. The idea of “nature-based social entrepreneurship” revives the classical notion of phronesis, or practical wisdom, as an alternative to actionable knowledge. This highlights the normative essence of a type of entrepreneurship focused on the shared flourishing of the eco-community.

5.1. Actionable knowledge or different kinds of knowledge?

In a classical definition, Argyris (Argyris, 2005) defines actionable knowledge as propositions that actors can use intentionally to produce actions with the desired effects. Scientific knowledge can lack this property because the scientific method often prescribes certain methodological standards that implicitly convey internal contradictions, unrealistic assumptions, or abstractions that create distance from reality. These factors create friction in taking actions based on that knowledge: The knowledge is not “actionable”. Hence, creating actionable knowledge is a distinct task of research.

In this brief chapter, we explore how knowledge can be made actionable within the context of CEA-NBS. We take a view that somewhat contrasts with the common

approaches in sustainability sciences, where this topic is often linked to concepts like co-production of knowledge and participatory methods for implementing NBS (Wickenberg et al., 2021). Our goal is to expand the range of relevant insights by treating NBS as a form of technology, as developed in D 2.1. This involves incorporating connections from disciplines beyond sustainability sciences, particularly two areas vital for making NBS “actionable” as a socio-political-technological practice: economics and engineering. One limitation of the Living Lab approach is its dependency on funding from external agencies, as seen in the case of COEVOLVERS. This reliance can hinder the scaling up and dissemination of NBS developed within that context, particularly due to restricted funding sources or limited organizational capacities at other sites where the knowledge might be applied. Additionally, the implementation of NBS is often influenced by the specific environmental conditions of a given location. Therefore, transferring these solutions may require new knowledge, which can be both financially and technically demanding to generate. For instance, the iconic species approach requires thorough ecological knowledge that applies at other locations.

However, in this concluding outlook chapter, we will not delve deeper into these issues. Our primary intention is to place the concept of “actionable knowledge” within a broader cross-disciplinary framework that is needed deal with them and develop adequate solutions. Economics is intriguing for several reasons. The “economics of NBS” is a key element in making knowledge actionable, in the sense of the economic conditions and resources that are needed to realize an NBS. However, the science of economics often presents challenges in translating theoretical knowledge into practice. For example, most economic propositions are based on the assumption of rationality, which can hinder their application. In Chapter 4, we noticed that theoretical ideas about governance are often at least implicitly shaped by this economic notion of rationality. However, this assumption has internal contradictions and does not accurately reflect the behaviour of real-world actors. As a result, there is often a significant gap between knowledge and action in economics (giving rise to new subdisciplinary fields like behavioural economics which inform some methods considered in this report, such as Role Board Games). As we see, despite a rich

reservoir of economic knowledge, economic action remains notoriously difficult in real life.

These cursory observations raise a fundamental question: How do knowledge and action relate to each other? The term “actionable knowledge” seems to suggest a clear separation between knowledge and the action resulting from that knowledge.

From the perspective of the CEA-NBS, the term “actionable knowledge” is problematic in several ways:

1. Knowledge is only seen as manifest in propositions, a stance following the definition of “knowing that” but ignores non-propositional forms of “knowing how,” such as tacit and embodied knowledge (Pavese, 2022). This includes knowledge that is not even accessible to actors in any form, and is only manifest in their capabilities of doing an action.
2. Knowledge is not necessarily available to an individual actor but is incorporated in the structures and processes of the environment in which the actor is embedded, such as, for example, the organization of which she is a member. We have referred to organizational routines in the previous chapter.
3. Knowledge is also an integral part of action, so we cannot assume a simple linear and causal flow that leads from knowledge to action, with the latter adding nothing to the knowledge. The flow itself embodies evolving knowledge. For example, learning by doing means that actors self-imitate successful actions even without “knowing that” why they are improving.
4. Knowledge is intimately connected to agency if it should be “actionable”; however, as we discussed in the first chapter, the agency is often distributed across assemblages of entities, where individual human actors may even be marginal as centres of the agency.

These limitations of the propositional account of knowledge are widely recognized in fields such as action research (Reason, 1999). Hence, we may question whether the notion of “actionable knowledge” is useful to guide the search for successful practice. We may even adopt a deflationary view on the term, arguing that it emerges from the research process as relating to the mundane need to document what works in practice and present it in propositional form. This documentation is a fundamental requirement

for funding agencies, which prioritize accountability and transparency. Additionally, these agencies seek “policies” that are informed by research findings, placing economics and engineering within the larger context of various disciplinary perspectives relevant for formulating policies. Therefore, we can define "actionable knowledge" as a specific type of output that research produces: "Actionable knowledge" refers not to the knowledge that effectively enables and generates actions in the real world, but rather to a construct created by the researcher for specific audiences. This definition reveals its limitations, much like the everyday issues encountered with instruction manuals. Similar to these manuals, the text of "actionable knowledge" may fail to convey information in a way that allows someone else to successfully apply it. Consequently, we find ourselves back at square one.

These challenges suggest that the term "actionable knowledge" creates problematic boundaries between knowledge and action. A paradox raises its ugly head: Actionable knowledge finally takes the form of knowledge in propositional form, thus recreating what it is intended to overcome, namely the knowledge-action gap.

A radically different perspective can be found in Greek antiquity, where philosophers made distinctions among various types of knowledge. The term "actionable knowledge" is implicitly linked to what is known as "episteme" in this context, which refers to theoretical and universal knowledge. Another type of knowledge is "phronesis," which can be translated as practical knowledge (for a modern reception and overview, see (Kristjánsson, 2022)). Phronesis is not simply episteme applied in practice; it represents a different kind of knowledge that is embodied in actual practices—essentially, the "knowing how" of modern analytical philosophy. However, there is an additional aspect we will discuss in the final section, which elucidates why phronesis is often translated as "practical wisdom." Phronesis encompasses a strong normative component. Hence, we may conclude that we should not look for “actionable knowledge”, but for a radically different kind of knowledge.

These distinctions are crucial for understanding modern cross-disciplinary relationships. The most relevant case for us is the distinction between engineering and science (Mitcham, 1994). While engineering frequently utilizes scientific knowledge, referred to as episteme, it is typically regarded as a distinct type of knowledge because

most scientific insights cannot be directly applied in practice. Engineering primarily involves a series of actions aimed at resolving emerging issues during the design process of creating new technologies (Petroski, 2002). As a result, it is often impractical or even impossible to replicate solutions solely based on scientific knowledge. For instance, consider modern chip production: leading companies possess vast knowledge resources that are not generic but highly unique to their historically evolved and collective practices. Thus, actionable knowledge resides within these practices, representing a type of phronesis in the technological age.

The distinction between science and engineering is particularly relevant when discussing NBS. There exists a gap between scientific disciplines, such as general biology and ecology, and the task of creating an NBS tailored to a specific local ecosystem within a sociopolitical context. However, an important difference lies in the nature of creating an NBS as technology compared to developing technology within competitive firms. Companies often have incentives to protect their unique knowledge, avoiding its transformation into generic knowledge to prevent imitation by competitors. In contrast, successful NBS should be shared as widely as possible. This provides a significant economic insight: actionable knowledge of NBS is a public good. This highlights the need for instructional manuals, evident in various handbooks and guides available on EU-sponsored websites. How can we disseminate the phronesis of an NBS created by a Living Lab?

5.2. Constructing knowledge in action

The gap between propositional knowledge and knowledge that is embodied in practices is salient in one economic example that is close to the LL approach, namely Elinor Ostrom's research on the commons (Ostrom, 2015). Indeed, some NBS have the structure of a commons, and we have also seen that "commoning" is a critical process in doing CEA-NBS. Traditional economics failed to produce actionable knowledge to address the so-called "tragedy of the commons," often relying on a misleading, theory-driven interpretation of the problem. Ostrom contended that economics misrepresents the issue and overlooks the diverse practices that have

evolved in many communities to manage their resources effectively. To address this, Ostrom studied these practices and developed a list of necessary conditions for a successful and sustainable commons. But is this knowledge truly actionable? In 2001, Agrawal (Agrawal, 2001) argued that Ostrom's list cannot encompass all factors that ultimately determine the success of common-pool resources. He noted that applying the list in real situations reveals various contextual factors essential for its effectiveness. Agrawal recommended moving beyond case studies and utilizing statistical analysis with large samples of cases. This approach has become a standard in economics, particularly with the rise of randomized evidence-based research (Duflo, 2020)). However, the limitations of these methods are apparent, as they require stringent implementation of controls and only apply to specific types of actions that can be clearly identified and distinguished across the sample.

Obviously, this critique directly applies to Living Labs as these are case studies. Similar to the commons case, Agrawal's critique would mean that actionable knowledge can only emerge from conducting a large number of randomized experiments and then reaching conclusions from statistical analysis. Obviously, this is neither feasible in practice nor can reasonably be made operational in terms of the required rigour of statistical methods.

For the co-evolutionary approach to NBS, there is even a fundamental issue that results from the orientation towards an unknown future of changing environmental conditions. Karl Popper once famously argued that evolutionary theory is not science (he later retreated from this position). The reason given was that evolutionary theory cannot predict future events and, therefore, cannot be falsified by testing predictions. However, evolutionary theory can exclude certain phenomena as impossible, so that it would be falsified by their occurrence. If we conceptualize NBS as a coevolutionary technology, the same applies. It is impossible to predict which solutions will be the best practices in the future. We can make statements about what will possibly not happen: For example, we are safe in assuming that stopping decarbonization will enhance biodiversity on Earth. The conclusion for constructing actionable knowledge about NBS are sobering: We can learn from failures, but we cannot learn from success. As we will see, this is an important insight, as it means that reporting about

obstacles, blind alleys, destructive conflicts, and all that might be more important for the dissemination of LL practices than reporting perceived factors of success.

Our discussion highlights the complex nature of constructing actionable knowledge. We can approach this by understanding that actionable knowledge is distinct and coevolves with actions, existing within the dynamic process of knowledge creation (Räsänen et al., 2024). It is not merely the presentation of knowledge as propositions; rather, it is fluid and creative throughout the flow of action. Practically, this requires a well-designed process, organized systematically as an iterative sequence that leads to the accumulation of knowledge. This process should involve continual deliberation among all relevant parties, such as stakeholders in NBS.

It is important to note that this knowledge may never reach a final state. As we discussed in the context of governance, the structures conducive to creating an NBS may differ from those needed to maintain it. Maintenance is an ongoing process that extends well beyond the funding horizon of a living lab, particularly regarding biodiversity goals. Therefore, knowledge may need to accumulate over an extended period, while dissemination should begin early.

More specifically, we can draw the following lessons from doing NBS in LL practice. The first lesson is to approach the concept of knowledge in a way that adequately represents all forms of knowing. In CEA-NBS, this involves adopting a transdisciplinary approach that also includes non-human knowledge. Before attempting to express this knowledge in propositional form, it is essential to emphasize recognition, thereby ensuring epistemic justice by giving voice to all knowledge holders. In transdisciplinary research, this is often understood as providing equal recognition to both scientific and local knowledge, which means acknowledging the insights of trained experts alongside those of local knowers. Furthermore, it is important to recognize the knowledge embodied in non-humans. This report has illustrated various ways to achieve this.

The second lesson is that knowledge is not solely expressed and should not only be recorded in propositional form. This form serves as a limited way to communicate knowledge among certain groups, such as researchers and policymakers. This becomes particularly clear when we consider the transmission of cultural knowledge.

While this is often conveyed through texts and speech, one of the most powerful methods is imitation. Even linguistic forms may not strictly adhere to propositional structure, as seen when a myth is recounted in a song. Imitation necessitates the physical co-presence of individuals who are engaged in sharing knowledge.

The third lesson is that knowledge exists in various forms beyond just individuals. This idea is well-recognized in organizational theory, particularly through the concept of routines. In its broadest sense, this means that knowledge is embedded in the habits of individuals, groups, artifacts, the material environment, and even non-human entities. In essence, knowledge is found in the interactions of different elements that participate in actions, even when those actions are performed by individuals. This aligns with the concept of distributed cognition, particularly in its embodied form.

The fourth lesson concludes from the previous points: "actionable knowledge" cannot be presented in the standard format of a research report, like the one we currently have. Instead, the form of actionable knowledge should reflect the complexities of real-world knowledge. This lesson is vital for this report: the way information is presented is itself a powerful form of knowledge creation, aligning with the famous saying, "The medium is the message." Let us explore this in more detail.

5.3. Reporting and archiving coevolutionary knowledge

What do these four lessons imply for reporting on CEA-NBS research? We will provide a few examples based on the hypothetical case of a Living Lab that has been evaluated as successfully implementing a NBS, reflecting the current state of transdisciplinary research. The community agrees that actions have been taken that contribute to its shared flourishing.

We emphasize that this stage is already complex and challenging, as the evaluation is a political decision that must adhere to the principles of multi-species democracy and multi-species justice outlined in this report. A positive evaluation is a normative action governed by established norms. For instance, it would be insufficient to use expert-based evaluation methods that take an external position regarding the community (for example, as developed in (Chairat and Gheewala, 2024)). A minimal

requirement for such a report is that it must be confirmed and supported by all knowledge holders in the community, which is inherently difficult due to accessibility challenges for many members. Consider, for example, an evaluation based on biodiversity metrics. While increasing biodiversity is a goal, it does not eliminate the possibility that some local species may suffer or even go extinct—species that have a stake in the current status of the NBS. How can we weigh these different concerns? This may require accepting current losses for potential future gains under the uncertain conditions posed by climate change (Thomas, 2020). There is no way to decide such deeply normative questions based on scientific knowledge as episteme.

If we complete this stage, we can explore how the community's experiences can be shared in a way that helps others learn from its successful actions. We previously noted that imitation is a powerful way to achieve this. However, imitation is only motivated by texts and other media: in practice, it must be based on sharing experiences in interactions. While this approach is clear, implementing it is challenging because it requires the physical co-presence of individuals from different communities. For instance, a transdisciplinary delegation from one community might visit another for an extended period to conduct hands-on research, with applications in mind for their home community. The interesting aspect of this interaction is that it will not lead to simple copying but rather to creative imitation. The visiting individuals will interpret their experiences through their own lenses, constantly making comparisons. This physical presence also allows for the creation of embodied knowledge that may differ from that of the local community.

The role of imitation reveals a limitation of the LL approach highlighted in the literature (Van Der Jagt et al., 2019), but also shows a solution that is already found in practice, such as in COEVOLVERS. Developing successful practices is only possible in translocal networks of learning communities where a continuous flow of experiences is enabled via recurrent interactions across the LLs. To an important extent, this point reflects basic mechanisms in human cultural history where inter-community exchange has always been a driving force of knowledge generation. However, we emphasize that such a process is also creative in the sense that it is not necessarily converging to one single paradigm of doing an NBS. On the contrary, the record of cultural history

suggests that processes of “schismogenesis” will be ubiquitous, meaning that local communities will form identities and practices which are defined in opposition to other communities (Graeber and Wengrow, 2022).

This comparison with cultural history leads to the conclusion that reporting about LL experiences may require the literary form of writing history. That means, considering written media, using a narrative instead of a standard research report can be effective. This shift of genre is necessary because many researchers in the NBS domain have a background in the sciences, broadly speaking, and adopt formats that they are familiar with in these fields. In contrast, the LL narrative about the NBS weaves together various resources, such as storytelling samples, researchers' reports, and news items, creating a cohesive flow of descriptions and arguments that reflect the dynamic nature of successful actions and their context. This report demonstrates that narratives can also include non-human voices. Many of the methods discussed here can be transformed into artistic elements within a narrative.

Two key features distinguish narratives as a literary form from standard reports. First, narratives have a plot and can be presented in different genres, such as detective or romance: Enhancing biodiversity can be told as a detective story about citizen sciences, or as people falling in love with immigrating liminal species. The plot structure aligns with the idea of actionable knowledge by illustrating how various actions and contexts work together to produce outcomes. This structure also allows for a clear exploration of obstacles and failures, which often create tension and suspense. Hence, narratives are a medium that dovetails with the epistemic structure of evolutionary theory as briefly discussed in the previous section. Moreover, narratives can present multiple perspectives by intertwining subplots and stories from diverse actors, including non-humans.

A powerful non-textual narrative form is a movie about the Living Lab (LL), which can be co-created by the community and researchers. This approach allows for the inclusion of non-human elements beyond just written text and spoken language. One effective format for this is a documentary that incorporates a diverse range of perspectives and artistic expressions. However, this is not the only possibility. The role of the arts in developing NBS also applies to reporting formats. For example, a film

can vividly portray the various emotions associated with an NBS while using music inspired by nature to create moods that contextualize and motivate action.

A report about the LL can take many non-textual forms that utilize artistic means to depict reality, as exemplified by films. One significant aspect highlighted in this report is the role of mapping. Following the example of Indigenous mapping, the transdisciplinary community engages in mapping NBS. This approach goes beyond conventional mapping, if using virtual reality tools. It structures space by identifying processes, events, causes, outcomes, and various perspectives. Most importantly, it reflects the diverse Umwelts of community members through multi-layered mapping, allowing viewers to navigate the many worlds of the NBS.

The mapping example illustrates that the methods outlined in this report can serve as tools for co-creating actionable knowledge through comparisons across different communities. For instance, we have introduced the concept of co-creating an NBS avatar. This avatar can be co-created multiple times during the implementation of an NBS, potentially uncovering knowledge about the necessary capabilities and potentials for successful execution. This process enables comparative exercises, such as those that took place during field visits by other learning communities. When another community creates its own avatar, the two groups can discuss the differences and what these differences may indicate about the conditions required for effective NBS implementation.

These examples illustrate alternative ways of reporting LL experiences to make knowledge actionable, both in human and non-human contexts. These reporting methods align with the diverse approaches highlighted in this report. For instance, statistical analyses are presented through tables, numbers, and accompanying comments. However, processes like data refinement and strategies for addressing missing information often remain in the background. In contrast, CEA-NBS reporting incorporates methods that are also reflected in its research formats, such as art-based approaches. Eventually, the reporting becomes a knowledge-generating process of its own status, and does not simply describe knowledge that originated in a previous experiential and experimental process, as in the sciences.

5.4. Actionable ignorance and nature-based social entrepreneurship

Knowledge of CEA-NBS is in the action. This principle is central to pragmatism and indicates that all knowledge is experimental; there is never a point where an experiment is complete and reporting begins. This is especially relevant for NBS. The NBS we develop today must be adaptable to environmental conditions that are currently unknown, including those unpredictable factors often referred to as "unknown unknowns." Therefore, we need a significant shift in perspective. Rather than discussing "actionable knowledge," we should consider the concept of "actionable ignorance" to avoid the illusion of certainty and the pretence of knowledge. Actionable ignorance is a form of behaviour that copes with uncertainty and ignorance in taking riskful actions that simultaneously pursue practical goals and generate knowledge that reduces ignorance.

This shift in perspectives allows us to draw another connection to our previous discussion about economics and engineering, which we already ventilated in Chapter 1, section 1.5.1. Different types of knowledge play a crucial role in theories of entrepreneurship, as seminally argued by Hayek (Hayek, 1945). We encounter another variation of the theme that contrasts general knowledge with practical or local knowledge. The essence of entrepreneurship lies in making knowledge applicable within specific contexts of time and place, as well as activating knowledge that exists only in these local settings. Moreover, entrepreneurship involves navigating an uncertain future, for which no general knowledge can fully prepare us. Beyond their actions, entrepreneurs typically also reflect and communicate their activities in the medium of narratives, with the standard "business plan" just being a form of rationalization (Beckert, 2016).

As we can see, these themes are often sidelined in sustainability science, yet they clearly highlight the conditions necessary for creating NBS as new technologies that must align with the specifics of local ecosystems. Therefore, we suggest relating the CEA-NBS to the concept of entrepreneurship in economics. In recent decades, this concept has been expanded to include not-for-profit entrepreneurship that engages

with social innovation. Only recently has this connection been established within the NBS literature (Gültekin, 2024).

Focusing on entrepreneurship brings to light a range of other themes that are also marginalized, such as the critical topic of leadership separate from governance (Case et al., 2015). Indigenous scholars especially emphasize leadership when considering Indigenous practices of sustainability; chiefs play a pivotal role in bridging Indigenous spirituality and community practices (Trosper, 2022). NBS entrepreneurs are leaders who bridge the gap between human and non-human domains, encompassing both social and political entrepreneurship. This highlights the growing recognition that NBS require diverse forms of private sector engagement, extending beyond just NGOs and citizen organizations. A notable example is forestry, where a significant portion of forests is privately owned. This principle is also evident in urban redevelopment projects, which often involve real estate firms and various types of businesses.

Private sector engagement often leads to a conflict between business interests and long-term ecological concerns. This conflict can be alleviated by locally supporting various forms of social entrepreneurship, for which specific legal structures are available in many countries today. Here, we revisit the concept of “phronesis,” which refers to practical wisdom. Nature-based social entrepreneurship harnesses local knowledge that encompasses more than just human interests, thus fostering the collective well-being of the eco-community. In this context, the normative aspect of phronesis becomes apparent, emphasizing the importance of a multi-species community of inquiry.

The institutional framework for nature-based social entrepreneurship plays a crucial role in resolving conflicts related to multi-species justice, which we discussed in the previous chapter. For instance, consider the conflict between animal rights and traditional hunting of iconic species. To ensure the economic sustainability of an NBS, it may be necessary to promote local eco-tourism, which can include activities like hunting and fishing. In this model, the non-human animals that are hunted are considered co-producers of the NBS, and their inclusion is integral to its production. An ethical compromise could involve organizing such eco-tourism as a community-controlled social NBS enterprise that implements governance mechanisms similar to

Indigenous practices for managing hunting territories. In this way, nature-based social entrepreneurship becomes a form of nature-based governance.

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